

Member Book 2024-2025

**Academic
Data Science
Alliance**

March 2025

Academic
Data Science
Alliance

ADSA Member Book 2024-2025

2024-2025 ADSA Member Book

The Academic Data Science Alliance is a professional association for data science and AI in academia. Our community is made up of data science leaders, practitioners, and educators who take responsibility for a just, equitable future where data science approaches are thoughtfully applied in all domains for the benefit of all.

ADSA membership is open to academic programs, departments/schools, centers, full institutions, academic consortia, and non-profits that support higher ed. Our member institutions represent a range of models, maturity levels, and audiences at academic institutions in the US and beyond. The ADSA Member Book highlights these institutions that have 1) provided funds for ADSA through membership dues, 2) support ADSA as a leading organization for academic data science, and 3) agree with the guiding principles in ADSA's [Mission, Vision, and Values](#).

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2024-2025 ADSA Member Book

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RESEARCH \ ENGAGEMENT \ INNOVATION

Renaissance Computing Institute

SUMMARY

RENCI is a highly collaborative research institute at UNC-Chapel Hill that develops and deploys advanced technologies to enable innovative research and discovery in high performance computing (HPC), informatics, data mining, data linking, and secure computing.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Cross-departmental Institute

DATA SCIENCE SPECIALIZATIONS

- Clinical Informatics & AI
- Data Science & Analytics
- Earth Data Science
- Network Research & Infrastructure
- Software Architecture

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Operations Staff: 49
- Research & Teaching Staff: 63
- Domain Scientists: 10

SOCIAL

Email: comms@renci.org

Web: renci.org

X: @RENCI

LinkedIn: Renaissance Computing Institute

Facebook: Renaissance Computing Institute (RENCI)

YouTube: @rencimedia9122

LOCATION

100 Europa Dr, Suite 540
Chapel Hill, NC 27517

RENCI'S DATA SCIENCE COMPUTATIONAL PLATFORM

RENCI researchers have developed HeLx, a flexible computational workspace for any scientific domain. The tool allows researchers to bring together tools specific to their work in a secure, scalable portal. A version tailored for educational use, EduHeLx, has been developed and deployed in a pilot capacity in Fall 2021 and Spring 2022 in the UNC-Chapel Hill course, COMP 116: Introduction to Scientific Programming. EduHeLx is being used again in the course, CHIP 690: Foundations of Clinical Data Science, in Spring 2023. As UNC-Chapel Hill continues to develop its School of Data Science and Society (SDSS), EduHeLx has the potential to serve as a primary data science computational platform for data science education at the University.

The **South Big Data Hub** (South Hub or SBDH) serves the Southern U.S. Census Region (16 States: Delaware - Texas,

SOUTHBDHUB

including Washington D.C., Puerto Rico, the U.S. Virgin Islands, and territories). It is part of a network of four regional Big Data Hubs, launched by the National Science Foundation, including the Midwest, Northeast, and West Big Data Hubs, to engage local or regional stakeholders in big data research and permit a focus on regional issues. The South Hub is managed jointly by the Georgia Institute of Technology and RENCI, with more than 1300+ members from universities, corporations, foundations, and cities. For more information, visit southbigdatahub.org/about.

The **National Consortium for Data Science (NCDS)**, founded by RENCI, is a collaboration of leaders in academia, industry, and government formed to address

the data challenges and opportunities of the 21st century. The NCDS helps members take advantage of data in ways that result in new jobs and transformative discoveries. We connect diverse communities of data science experts to support a 21st-century data-driven economy by: 1) Building data science career pathways and creating a data-literate workforce, 2) Bridging the gap between data scientists in the public and private sectors, and 3) Supporting open and democratized data. For more information, visit datascienceconsortium.org.

The **iRODS Consortium**, founded by RENCI, brings together businesses, research organizations, universities, and government agencies to ensure the sustainability of iRODS by: to ensure the sustainability of iRODS by:

- Guiding further development of the software;
- Growing the user and developer communities; and
- Facilitating iRODS support, education, and collaboration opportunities.

The iRODS Consortium maintains and supports a commercial-grade distribution of iRODS. Additionally, the Consortium fields a team of software developers, application engineers, and support staff housed at RENCI. Each year, the Consortium hosts the iRODS User Group Meeting, a symposium that draws 100+ participants to share iRODS technologies and case studies. For more information, visit irods.org.

SCHOOL OF DATA SCIENCE AND SOCIETY

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

Although Carolina is not the first to establish a data science school, we believe the way we approach this growing field makes our program unique and especially relevant in our constantly evolving world.

Over the past decades, Carolina has developed and cultivated world-renowned scholarship and research in data science. We are honored to have the opportunity to build upon that foundation by creating an innovative curriculum and research portfolio through the school to serve our students and community, the state of North Carolina, and the nation. We will change the field of data science as we know it and better prepare students for the workforce of the 21st century.

CAREER OPPORTUNITIES AT UNC-CHAPEL HILL'S SCHOOL OF DATA SCIENCE AND SOCIETY

We are excited to announce multiple faculty openings, including open rank, tenure-track positions and tenure-track joint positions with Math, Computer Science, Statistics and Operations Research, Biomedical Engineering and Environmental Sciences and Engineering. Additionally, we have two Teaching Assistant Professor positions available. For more details and to apply, visit: datascience.unc.edu/careers.

SOCIAL

Email: sdss@unc.edu

Web: datascience.unc.edu

X: @UNCSDSS

LinkedIn: UNC School of Data Science and Society

YouTube: @UNCSDSS

SUMMARY

We envision a world made healthy, safe, and prosperous for all through data-informed decisions. Our school's focus on society will allow us to utilize innovative ways to use foundational and translational data science for the public good.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

School partnering with other schools, departments, centers and institutes

DEGREES, PROGRAMS AND SPECIALIZATIONS

The School of Data Science and Society (SDSS) offers a B.S. in data science as well as an online master of applied data science (MADS). Additionally, SDSS is in the process of developing an M.S. and a Ph.D. in data science.

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 31
- Professional Staff: 28
- Affiliated MADS Members:
 - Lead Faculty: 8
 - Section Instructors: 19
 - Adjunct Faculty: 6
- Students:
 - B.S. in Data Science: 103
 - MADS: 100

LOCATION

Chapel Hill, North Carolina

American Statistical Association

SUMMARY

The American Statistical Association is the world's largest community of statisticians and data scientists.

It is the second-oldest continuously operating professional association in the country.

Since it was founded in Boston in 1839, the ASA has supported excellence in the development, application, and dissemination of statistical science through meetings, publications, membership services, education, accreditation, and advocacy.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Professional Association

LOCATION

American Statistical Association
732 North Washington Street
Alexandria, VA 22314-1943

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

ASA is a professional society. It does not grant degrees; rather, it supports departments, programs and individual professionals through journals, meetings, professional development, networking and advocacy.

ASA champions the data science community in a variety of ways beyond its membership in ADSA. For instance, ASA is a member of CSAB, which as part of ABET accredits undergraduate programs in data science. ASA provides input into the accreditation criteria and ASA members are trained to serve as program evaluators.

ASA has sections which provide members with the opportunity to network, research, and develop as professionals with others who are interested in the same topic. Our largest section is Statistics Learning and Data Science. Our Statistics and Data Science Education section is also large and active.

ASA publishes or co-publishes 16 leading journals in statistics and data science, among which are Statistical Analysis and Data Mining, the Journal of Computational and Graphical Statistics, and the Journal of Statistics and Data Science Education.

CONFERENCES, MEETINGS AND WORKSHOPS

ASA's professional meetings are highly regarded. The flagship meeting for the statistics profession is the Joint Statistical Meetings, held in late July or early August. The ASA manages this meeting, which includes representation from 10 other statistical and data science organizations. The Symposium on Data Science and Statistics (held in May) and the Women in Statistics and Data Science Conference (October) are among our other high-quality meetings.

ASA promotes data science and statistics in the statistical agencies of the federal government and in state and local government as well through advocacy and through our "Count on Statistics" platform.

SOCIAL

Email: asainfo@amstat.org

Web: www.amstat.org

LinkedIn: American Statistical Association - ASA

Facebook: @AmstatNews

Instagram: @AmstatNews

EDUCATION AND OUTREACH

ASA supports students through competitions and outreach. ASA DataFest is an annual 48-hour competition in which teams of undergraduate students work to reveal insights into a rich and complex data set. ASA hosts data challenges in the fall and spring through our "This is Statistics" program, which is our outreach to high school and undergraduate students.

ASA also supports K-12 and college instruction by providing guidelines for teaching at various levels, resources for teaching, and networking for instructors.

PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT

ASA provides professional development through in-person and online instruction in a wide variety of topics. Professional development coursework spans everything from basic overviews to advanced instruction in cutting-edge topics and includes courses in non-technical skills as well.

The board and staff leadership of the ASA welcomes suggestions for additional ways to support and advocate for the data science community.

Faculty of Computing & Data Sciences

SUMMARY

Founded in 2019, the Faculty of Computing & Data Sciences (CDS) is a transdisciplinary, degree-granting academic unit created to connect BU's 17 schools and colleges through the language of computation and data. The mission of CDS is to lay the foundation for innovation-driven, civic-minded computing, data science, and AI.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

The Faculty of Computing & Data Sciences is a degree-granting academic unit embedded in the provost office.

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- Undergraduate Major in Data Science
- Undergraduate Minor in Data Science
- Combined BS and MS in Data Science
- Graduate Professional MS in Data Science
- Graduate Professional MS in Bioinformatics
- Graduate Professional Online MS in Data Science
- Graduate PhD in Computing & Data Sciences
- Graduate PhD in Bioinformatics

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 23
- Professional Staff: 11
- Affiliated Members: 37
- Students: 1,300+

LOCATION

665 Commonwealth Ave.
Boston, MA 02215

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

Boston University (BU) is one of the largest private institutions in the US with 37,000+ students, 4,000+ faculty and staff, spread across 17 schools and colleges. The mission of CDS is to be an integrative cross-cutting academic unit, facilitating the movement of ideas, research, and educational programs across the University and building bridges between established departments, schools, and colleges.

OUR VISION, MISSION & VALUES

- Our **vision** is to improve the human condition by bringing computational and data-driven technologies, systems, and processes to bear on the greatest challenges facing our world.
- Our **mission** is to conduct cutting-edge research that matters to society; we provide students with rigorous education and vibrant academic experiences that unleash their innovative capacities; and we democratize access by learners, researchers, practitioners, and the public to the transformative power of computation and data.
- Our **values** lead us to reward creativity and excellence; we recognize collaborative endeavors; we respect and trust each other; we celebrate our diversity of perspectives and lived experiences; and we uphold our moral and ethical responsibilities to the fullest.

DYNAMIC AND STATE-OF-THE-ART

Our home, located in the center of BU's campus, provides exceptional workspace and unmatched teaching and learning environments. The 19-story structure, which is shared with the Computer Science and Mathematics & Statistics departments, and the Rafik B. Hariri Institute for Computing, features a convention-bending design inside and out – making it an iconic presence on our Central Campus. The design is state-of-the-art in every way: striking architecture, inspiring classrooms and collaboration spaces, advanced resources, and open, flexible interior spaces. And, most impressive is the building's unmatched sustainability profile, featuring zero-carbon heating and cooling provided by thirty-on 1,500-foot geothermal wells, making it the largest such building in the Northeast.

SOCIAL

Email: cds-admin@bu.edu

Web: bu.edu/cds-faculty

X: @bu_cds

LinkedIn: Faculty of Computing & Data Sciences at Boston University

Facebook: @BUCDS

Instagram: @bu_cds

A DATA SCIENCE HUB

We are the home for data science at BU, a deeply inclusive, collaborative and cooperative place with porous boundaries. A hub for data science, CDS is the convener and amplifier of university-wide interdisciplinary research centers, including the Rafik B. Hariri Institute for Computing—an incubator that accelerates data-driven research in various disciplines by leveraging BU's strengths in existing centers and new initiatives focused on data science, artificial intelligence, software engineering, computational science, cloud computing, digital health, data privacy, cybersecurity, and the nexus of computing, society, and law.

MEETING THE AI DEMAND

Industry experts say professions such as AI-solution architect, machine-learning engineer, computer-vision expert, and roboticist are in high demand. To train the next generation of data scientists and AI practitioners, BU launched a three-year AI cluster hiring initiative in fall 2022. Led by CDS, in collaboration with other academic units across the University, the initiative covers foundational, methodological, and use-inspired dimensions of AI, and resulted in nine new hires.

COMMUNITY & CONNECTION

The CDS community is comprised of both faculty from cognate units and tenured and tenure-track faculty appointed through CDS with shared interests in the many aspects of data science. As such, CDS is a self-governing autonomous academic unit and not merely a division or institute that acts as an administrative overlay to coordinate the priorities of other academic units.

HUBS FOR IMPACT

Rather than clustering faculty, students, and programs around computing and data subspecialties (e.g., machine learning, data mining, cloud computing), CDS centers around thematic areas of impact, currently equity, sustainability, health, and civic tech. Much of our work is done through co-Labs that involve faculty, students, and external partnerships around applied research, curricular, and co-curricular collaborations. The experiential learning component of these collaborations is delivered through the BU Spark! program leveraging a shared infrastructure and staff support.

UNIVERSITY OF AMSTERDAM

Data Science Centre

SUMMARY

The University of Amsterdam Data Science Centre mission is to enhance the university's research by developing, sharing and applying data science methods and technologies.

As a coordinating hub within the UvA Library, the centre is uniquely positioned to facilitate knowledge exchange as well as training in data-driven research.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Cross-departmental Center

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- Masters in:
 - Information Studies: Data Science
 - Behavioral Data Science
 - MBA Big Data & Business Analytics
- We also offer 10 Bachelor's degrees and 14 Master's degrees related to data science.
- Certificates:
 - AI for Executives
 - AI for Managers
 - AI Foundation Models
 - Health Informatics
 - Introduction to Machine Learning
 - Introduction to Quantum Computing
 - MBA in AI, Data and Analytics
 - Introduction to Quantum Computing
 - Data Governance

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Affiliated Members: 84
- Students: 2,742 (year 2020)

LOCATION

UvA University Library
Singel 425, 1012 WP
Amsterdam, The Netherlands

ABOUT US

The UvA's Data Science Centre is focused on accelerating data driven research across the university's entire research landscape. To do so, the centre is embedding data scientists and engineers throughout the university directly in research groups. These affiliated data scientists and engineers share knowledge and experience through weekly sessions at the library. The library has always served as an intellectual crossroads within universities where scientists acquire knowledge and skills making it a natural home for the DSC. We currently have 84 affiliated members (2025) and are growing every year.

SOCIAL

Email: dsc@uva.nl

Web: dsc.uva.nl

LinkedIn: [UvA / AUAS Library](#)

FOSTERING CROSS-FACULTY AND INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH

The University of Amsterdam has a strong foundation of cutting-edge research in AI and data science. Building on this foundation, the DSC funds and supports a range of positions and initiatives with the aim of strengthening data science expertise across all faculties of the University of Amsterdam. The DSC supports several interdisciplinary PhD projects performing research into new data science methods that help to tackle challenging problems. In the Human Aligned Video-AI Lab, researchers from all 7 UvA faculties investigate how to align video-AI with human values and ethical principles. The project aims to incorporate cognitive, ethical, and legal perspectives in the development of video-AI algorithms.

Other interdisciplinary PhD projects supported by the DSC include:

- The GPU Dentist: Instilling Domain Knowledge in Deep Networks through Hyperbolic Geometry
- Building better vision models using pre-cortical inductive biases
- Natural Language Processing and Responsible Data Management for Mental Health Research

Learn more: <https://dsc.uva.nl/programmes/programmes.html>

PROUD PARTNER OF THE AMSTERDAM AI NETWORK

Amsterdam AI aspires to generate impact and contribute towards a better, healthier society. Thanks to the thriving Amsterdam AI ecosystem, we are able to combine in-depth technological research with practical applications. This is accompanied by research into the societal, ethical and legal aspects of AI. Amsterdam AI's unique projects and initiatives make Amsterdam a strong magnet for AI talent.

The Amsterdam AI coalition includes Amsterdam UMC, Netherlands Cancer Institute/Antoni van Leeuwenhoek Hospital (NKI-AvL), Centrum Wiskunde & Informatica (CWI), Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences (AUAS), Sanquin, the University of Amsterdam (UvA), Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, the City of Amsterdam and the Amsterdam Economic Board. Many of these partners have been working on AI since the early 1990s, often in multidisciplinary forms. This produces valuable input for research, education and innovative applications. Learn more: <https://www.amsterdamai.com/>

THE UNIVERSITY
OF ARIZONA

Data Sciences and Computation

SUMMARY

The University of Arizona is a globally recognized research leader. The Data Science Institute enables research collaborations and expands the base for experiential learning and research innovations. Data Sciences Academy provides academic programming and K-14 Teacher Development. The Institute for Computation and Data-Enabled Insight complements these activities with workforce development.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Cross-departmental Institute

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- BS Artificial Intelligence
- BS Computer Science
- BS Systems and Industrial Engineering
- BS/MS Statistics & Data Science
- MS Geographic Information Systems Technology
- MS Human-Centered Computing
- MS Information Science
- MS Information Science - Machine Learning
- Graduate Interdisciplinary Program in Applied Mathematics
- **Certificates:**
 - Geographic Information Science
 - Professional Geographic Information Systems Technology
 - Data Science for Health Professionals
- **Specializations:** ML/AI, Engineering, Life Sciences, Genomics, Healthcare

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 2
- Professional Staff: 25
- Affiliated Members: 86

LOCATION

1230 N. Cherry Avenue
Tucson, AZ 85721

DATA SCIENCE INSTITUTE (DSI)

DSI facilitates collaborative interdisciplinary research providing ML/AI tools and training, cyberinfrastructure through CyVerse, and support for data-intensive research. By connecting U of A researchers and aligning institutional expertise, computational resources, and infrastructure, DSI enables investigators to achieve outcomes not easily attainable as individual investigators or within purely disciplinary teams.

UA DATALAB

Founded by DSI, the UA DataLab provides training, consulting and hands-on experience on ML/AI tools and resources for students, faculty, and industry partners. The DataLab focuses on skills and tools required when working with modern computing languages, ML/AI models for analyzing large multi-modal datasets and in support of open, reproducible science.

U OF A RESEARCH SOFTWARE ENGINEERS/PROFESSIONALS (RSE/P) GROUP

DSI and other campus units support structure for a newly forming RSE/P group. The group provides professional development workshops selected and taught by RSE/Ps, identifies development of career paths, and advocates the need to have RSE/Ps included early in the research lifecycle.

CYVERSE - THE OPEN SCIENCE WORKSPACE FOR COLLABORATIVE DATA-DRIVEN DISCOVERY

CyVerse is an easy-to-use cyberinfrastructure platform enabling researchers to do and share their computational research faster.

CyVerse offers:

- **Data Store** - a federated data grid enabling storage, discovery, access, and sharing of data with research teams globally
- **Discovery Environment** - an easy-to-use data science workbench that enables researchers and instructors to create, perform, share, and replicate data science analyses in the cloud
- **CACAO (Cloud Automation)** - simplifying multi-cloud applications and deployments for researchers and educators
- **Collaborative Research Services** - expertise to architect, deploy, manage, and integrate cloud and on-premise cyberinfrastructure solutions
- **Education** - CyVerse training, webinars, and workshops; instruction also offered through the DSI UA DataLab

CyVerse is a partner of the Data Science Institute, BIO5, and the Institute for Computation and Data-enabled Insight at the University of Arizona. Learn more at www.cyverse.org.

SOCIAL

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Web: datascience.arizona.edu

LinkedIn: UArizona Institute for Computation and Data-Enabled Insight

Instagram: @uazdata

YouTube: @uarizona-dsi

INSTITUTE FOR COMPUTATION AND DATA-ENABLED INSIGHT (ICDI)

ICDI is committed to making advanced information technologies accessible, adaptable, and impactful for all communities. Using open science and ethically sourced data, we drive culturally inspired, human-centered innovation to foster educational and economic opportunities across Arizona and beyond.

BREAKING DOWN RESEARCH BARRIERS

ICDI supports groundbreaking, interdisciplinary research with cyberinfrastructure designed for open science. We enable global data access, supporting the entire data lifecycle for projects in AI, precision health, digital twins, and the science of science. Our work strengthens the university's leadership in data-driven science, guided by CARE data principles that honor Indigenous rights, self-determination, and data sovereignty.

SUPERCHARGING ARIZONA'S WORKFORCE

We bridge academia and industry to build workforce capabilities through experiential learning and professional development in emerging technologies, cybersecurity, and semiconductor manufacturing. By connecting students with businesses and mentors, we foster internships and real-time exploration of AI

integration and cybersafety. Collaborating with community colleges, units across the U of A, and local organizations, we deliver education programs tailored to Arizona's evolving industries, boosting the state's economic competitiveness.

EDUCATING K-12

We nurture data literacy early through bootcamps, credentialing, curricula support, and hands-on experiences in data science, cybersecurity, and AI. Our programs equip educators with best practices while promoting culturally relevant approaches for Arizona's Indigenous communities, emphasizing local knowledge, partnerships, and ownership in education.

BUILDING COMMUNITIES

ICDI connects academia, public agencies, and local governments to ensure Arizona benefits from advances in information technology. Partnering with Arizona State University and Northern Arizona University, we share best practices, expand statewide computing infrastructure, and support trustworthy data stewardship. At the university, we facilitate and support initiatives like the Artificial Intelligence Working Group, AI Hardware Design League, Women in Data Science, and research software engineering communities.

Learn more: www.datainsight.arizona.edu

THE UNIVERSITY OF BRITISH COLUMBIA

Data Science Institute
Faculty of Science

SUMMARY

The UBC Data Science Institute is a Faculty of Science initiative designed to incubate and accelerate research, innovation and training in data-intensive science. The UBC DSI equips researchers and external partners with the approaches, tools and expertise they need to fully leverage the potential of big data.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Faculty-wide institute with university-wide partnerships

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 1
- Professional Staff: 9
- Affiliated Members: 47

LOCATION

EOS Main Building
6339 Stores Road, Room 113C
Vancouver, BC V6T 1Z4
Canada

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

The DSI provides a hub for UBC researchers who require more than standard analyses to participate in interdisciplinary teams that both push the forefront of data science and accelerate their own research. We offer expertise in assessing, cleaning and integrating data, modelling data, and help in interpreting data. To help UBC researchers tackle major challenges in data-intensive research, the DSI builds a supportive training and mentoring environment for post-doctoral fellows.

DATA SCIENCE FOR SOCIAL GOOD

The Data Science for Social Good (DSSG) Program at the University of British Columbia is an interdisciplinary summer research program that brings together data providers and domain experts to work with talented students (i.e., DSSG Fellows) on data-intensive projects that have the potential to benefit society.

Highlights:

- Summer data science capstone projects
- Interdisciplinary and immersive research experience environment combining technical data science training with social and ethical awareness
- Collaborative projects with government or non-profit organizations with aim to benefit society
- Diverse teams of undergraduate and graduate students from STEM and non-STEM fields
- Hands-on data science training with open and secure data sets
- Understanding of broader implications of data and data-derived insights on society
- Awareness of various ethical issues around use of citizen data
- Mentoring by industry data scientists and UBC faculty
- First program of its kind in Canada

SOCIAL

Email: dsi.admin@science.ubc.ca

Web: dsi.ubc.ca

X: @UBCDSI

LinkedIn: UBC Data Science Institute

YouTube: @ubcdatascienceinstitute7628

POSTDOCTORAL FELLOW MATCHING FUND

The DSI provides a hub for UBC researchers who require more than standard analyses to participate in interdisciplinary teams that both push the forefront of data science and accelerate their own research. We offer expertise in assessing, cleaning and integrating data, modelling data, and help in interpreting data. To help UBC researchers tackle major challenges in data-intensive research, the DSI provides funding for UBC researchers looking to hire postdocs to collaborate on selected projects.

RESEARCH COLLABORATIONS

The Data Science Catalyst Program aims to support Faculty of Science PIs in enhancing the data science aspect of their research endeavors, thereby increasing their potential for securing future research grant funding. Through the Data Science Catalyst Program, funded projects are paired with a DSI resident data scientist for a duration of one year, focusing on data-intensive projects.

Revolutionizing the impact of data

through
research

SCHOOL OF DATA SCIENCE AND SOCIETY

Learn more at
datascience.unc.edu

M.S. AND PH.D. PROGRAMS IN DEVELOPMENT*

FIVE TRACKS

- 1 Advanced data science foundations
- 2 Physical, biological and health sciences
- 3 Social sciences and humanities
- 4 Data engineering
- 5 AI and ML

**Pending approval from the UNC System*

UCI Master of Data Science

Empowering Innovation

SUMMARY

As the only computational-focused school in the UC System, the UC Irvine Donald Bren School of Information and Computer Sciences has a unique perspective on the information technology disciplines that allows us a broad foundation from which to build educational programs and research initiatives.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Cross-departmental Institute

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- Master of Data Science
- B.S. in Data Science

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Professional Staff: 4
- Affiliated Members: 50
- Students: 69

SOCIAL

Email: mds@ics.uci.edu

Web: mds.ics.uci.edu

LOCATION

University of California, Irvine
6210 Donald Bren Hall
Irvine, CA 92697-3425

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

The Donald Bren's School of Information and Computer Science Master of Data Science (MDS) prepares you to develop your understanding of the cornerstones of modern data science through a dual framework in Statistics and Computer Science. It was ranked #7 Best Master's in Data Science by Fortune in 2022.

The MDS program offers two pathways (Part-Time and Full-Time) taught by pioneering faculty and researchers in the field of data science, anchoring the curriculum in hands-on training in applied probability and mathematical statistics, statistical modeling and computing, machine learning, data management and visualization, and artificial intelligence.

"Industry is learning quickly that people can scrape and analyze data, but to do something truly meaningful with data - to make decisions that will drive the industry forward you need the foundations of data science and understanding the statistics and computing methods. "

*-Dan Gillen, Ph.D.
Chair of Department of Statistics*

The MDS program provides an immersive education and experiential learning. Your time at the ICS School is focused on developing your skills and gaining exposure to the foundations of data science.

Between our Orange County corporate and tech connections and our combined faculty experience, the ICS School's global network is prominent. A large number of our alumni stay in Southern California, and our vast network spans across the world. No matter where your education takes you, the connections you make here will positively impact your life and career. We focus on the quality of professional and academic relationships that you build while here.

SUMMARY

The School of Data Science at UNC Charlotte commits to excellence in education, research, community engagement, and inclusion to shape and lead the future of data science. We teach students to be responsible and ethical data science practitioners, leaders, and researchers in an increasingly data-driven and global society.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

University-wide school housed under six colleges

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- B.S. in Data Science
- M.S. in Data Science and Business Analytics
- M.S. in Health Informatics and Analytics
- Ph.D. in Data Science
- B.S. in Sports Analytics
- Specializations in Engineering, Health and Human Services, Computer Science, Business, Humanities, Social Science, Statistics

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 19
- Professional Staff: 6
- Affiliated Members: 73
- Students: 851

LOCATION

Suite 1028 Colvard
9105 University Rd
Charlotte NC 28223

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

As the Carolinas' first School of Data Science, we tap into the region's expansive ecosystem of research, industry, and community engagement to apply a visionary lens to the education and application of data science. We strive to meet the demands of our region and nation's workforce head-on through the School of Data Science. We commit to excellence in education, research, community engagement, and inclusion to shape and lead the future of data science education and practice. Our students are taught to be responsible and ethical data science practitioners, leaders, researchers, and innovators in an increasingly data-driven and global society. Our students may choose from several programs, including a **B.S. in Data Science**, graduate degrees in **Data Science and Business Analytics** or **Health Informatics and Analytics**, a new **B.S. in Sports Analytics**, and a new **Ph.D. in Data Science**.

ETHICS IN DATA SCIENCE

Ethics was designed into data science courses and scaffolded learning objectives across all four years. As an interdisciplinary program rooted in a six-college partnership, our commitment is to incorporate liberal arts and science principles into a traditional math and computing-heavy major, specifically to address complex ethical issues embedded in data science. "The ethical use of data is central to our mission," said Dr. Marco Scipioni, Associate Professor in the School of Data Science. "All of our undergraduate data science courses rigorously address ethical issues, whereas many other programs typically include just one elective on ethics or add it as a module in either introductory or advanced courses." The major not only informs students about data ethics in the classroom, but will also enable them to engage with community partners to observe the impact of data, privacy, and their work in real life. Students begin with the basics of data ethics, gradually adding the evaluation of ethical debates and arguments, and then concluding with learning how to conduct an ethical audit of real-world scenarios within data science.

SOCIAL

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Facebook: @UNCCharlotteSDS

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INDUSTRY PARTNERSHIPS

We have powerful industry partnerships. Community is one of the four central pillars in the **School of Data Science's (SDS) mission statement**. Specifically, our goal is to, "Engage the Charlotte and campus communities by creating accessible pathways for research and practice." From the inception of our first-degree offering in Health Informatics, we have relied on the support and counsel of an industry advisory board made up of industry and non-profit leaders in the region. As we added degree programs and the Data Science Initiative has grown into the School of Data Science, our **Industry Advisory Board** has evolved. Over 25 companies and community organizations are represented on our board. They are local, regional, and national entities representing healthcare, financial services, energy, manufacturing, and retail. Our success is predicated on their support and engagement.

INTERDISCIPLINARY PROGRAM

We are committed to providing consistent innovation with new programs in **Sports Analytics**, a new interdisciplinary PhD research in Data Science, and the ongoing support of **world-class research**. The sports analytics program is designed to extend meaningful collaborations among local and national businesses and sports franchises while attracting students not normally found in STEM fields to a career in Sports Analytics. As we face the increasing demand at the high end of the marketplace for data scientists, the **Ph.D. program in Data Science** will provide doctoral-level education to students seeking data science careers both in academia and within the industry. Additionally, the **Center for TAIMing AI** strives to be an international research hub in the emerging area of identification and management of risks associated with the adoption of AI. Overall, our faculty focuses mainly on AI and machine learning, science-based solutions for inclusive organizations, online misinformation behavior, impact, detection and mitigation, and urban health.

SHAPING WHAT'S NEXT

The **FIRST** School of Data
Science in the Carolinas

School of Data Science
@ UNC Charlotte

SCHOOL *of* DATA SCIENCE

FIRST IN THE NATION

The University of Virginia School of Data Science—the first of its kind in the nation—is guided by common goals: to further discovery, share knowledge, and make a positive impact on society through collaborative, open, and responsible data science research and education.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

School

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- B.S. in Data Science
- M.S. in Data Science (full-time residential and part-time online formats)
- Dual Degrees (MD, PhD, MBA)
- Ph.D. in Data Science

SCHOOL STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 47
- Professional Staff: 46
- Affiliated Members: 17
- Students: 347

LOCATION

Charlottesville, VA

A NEXUS OF DISCOVERY

The School of Data Science moved into its new home in 2024. The 61,000-square-foot building features open, collaborative spaces that transcend traditional boundaries and spark interdisciplinary connections between learners, researchers, and innovators. The four-story facility includes adaptive classrooms, faculty offices, collaborative meeting spaces, and research areas. Public spaces are open to the University and broader communities alike.

A SCHOOL WITHOUT WALLS

The University of Virginia School of Data Science—the first of its kind in the nation—is guided by common goals: to further discovery, share knowledge, and make a positive impact on society through collaborative, open, and responsible data science research and education. Founded in fall 2019 through the largest gift in UVA history, the School positions the university and our community to play a national and international leadership role in the global digital future.

SOCIAL

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YouTube: @uvaschoolofdatascience571

Podcast: UVA Data Points

DATA SCIENCE RESEARCH

The School of Data Science pursues high-impact research to further discovery, share knowledge, and transform society. Through their research, our faculty and students are building a better world. Research areas include education & human development, health & medicine, cybersecurity, environment, democracy, and business.

TRANSCENDING BOUNDARIES

The UVA School of Data Science views data science as more than just computation and machine learning, embracing an interdisciplinary approach through its 4+1 model. This model integrates AI, data engineering, data and society, and data design, with their intersection focused on practical application.

The School emphasizes that data science transcends disciplines and works as a “School Without Walls,” encouraging collaboration across fields to address societal challenges and improve lives. With a strong focus on ethical, responsible, and impactful data use, SDS prepares students to harness the power of data for the greater good.

The School hooded its first three doctoral students in May 2024 since it launched the Ph.D. in Data Science in fall 2022. The program currently enrolls 40 students.

DEGREE PROGRAMS

By working with experts in diverse domains, applying data science to real-world issues, and learning both the practical application of data science and the principles behind it, our students are poised to become leaders and pioneers in the field. Our goal is to educate students in data science throughout their academic journey and as lifelong learners, from undergraduate to professional.

Degrees and programs offered:

- Ph.D. in Data Science
- M.S. in Data Science (online and residential formats)
- B.S. in Data Science
- Minor in Data Science
- Professional Programs (non-degree)

CHAMPIONING EQUITY

Our society faces immense challenges related to the COVID-19 pandemic, systemic racism, and broad economic uncertainty. At the School of Data Science, our mission remains clear. From our inception, we have sought to center ethics, inclusion, and transparency in all we do. The urgent challenges of this moment have prompted our school to accelerate and reallocate our resources and efforts in this area. Data can uncover systemic inequities and injustices—yet our field cannot solve these issues without diverse voices. We recognize that like institutions everywhere, we still have much room for growth in this area, and we welcome new partnerships that share our vision of equity and innovation.

Data Science @ UW

UNIVERSITY OF WISCONSIN-MADISON

SUMMARY

Data is reshaping our world, and Data Science @ UW strives to bring the power of fundamental and applied data science to all fields of study at UW–Madison and beyond. We are committed to fostering an inclusive culture in data science that fuels creativity and discovery.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

We are a collaborative team including institutes, centers, departments, and a school at UW-Madison

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- Undergraduate Minor (certificate) in Data Science
- Undergraduate Major in Data Science
- MS Data Science
- MS Statistics: Statistics and Data Science
- MS Industrial Engineering: Systems Engineering and Analytics
- Master's in Engineering: Data Analytics (online program)
- MS Business Analytics
- MS Psychology: Data Science in Human Behavior
- MS Educational Psychology: Learning Analytics (online program)
- MS & PhD Biomedical Data Science

PROGRAM STATISTICS

Over 1,000 Data Science majors and over 600 undergraduate Data Science certificate (minor). Hundreds of other students are enrolled in the rich array of data science graduate education offered at UW-Madison.

LOCATION

Madison, WI

DATA SCIENCE INSTITUTE

The Data Science Institute, powered by American Family Insurance, performs cutting-edge research, bridging theory and practice, in collaboration with people across the UW–Madison campus and around the world. Three primary functions drive the work of DSI: innovation, translation, and collaboration. Cutting-edge research projects bring people together to develop innovative data science methodology. Teams of data scientists and domain research scientists translate frontier research methods into practical, adaptable resources. Facilitators, working through the Data Science Hub, connect researchers from all disciplines with available data science resources, experts, and efforts. The campus-wide scale of DSI enhances the university's productivity in today's data-rich research environment.

DSI is central to UW-Madison's strategic priority to grow its research enterprise and expand its global impact, supporting the scholarship of faculty, staff, and students. Our leadership extends to the campus RISE initiative addressing challenges of importance to Wisconsin and the world, including AI. Our strategy is informed by the Wisconsin Idea: Research and education should influence people's lives beyond the boundaries of the classroom, lab, and campus.

DATA SCIENCE HUB

The Data Science Hub in the Wisconsin Institute for Discovery collaborates closely with DSI to provide training and implement data science practices into research across campus. The Data Science Hub executes its mission of community engagement and learning opportunities for researchers across campus through a variety of services. The Data Science Hub hosts trainings and workshops around fundamental data science and computational skills, to help researchers learn to reproducibly write software and analyze data. It offers consultations with data science facilitators who can recommend learning pathways and project strategies, and liaise contacts with collaborators and data science experts.

The Data Science Hub organizes seminars and events, including UW-Madison's annual Data Science Research Bazaar, where researchers and data scientists from different disciplines and industries have opportunities to share their work, collaborate, and discuss their data science interests.

SOCIAL

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LinkedIn: UW–Madison Data Science Institute AND UW–Madison CDIS

SCHOOL OF COMPUTER, DATA & INFORMATION SCIENCES

The School of Computer, Data & Information Sciences (CDIS) was launched in 2019 and brings together the top-ranked departments of Computer Sciences, Statistics, and the Information School. CDIS is lighting the way forward for research and discovery, magnifying the power of medicine, engineering, agriculture, business, and more. CDIS is educating versatile, multi-talented graduates across all majors on campus—who form a uniquely prepared talent pipeline that is driving economic growth in the region and beyond. CDIS collaborates across campus, regionally, and nationally to produce cutting-edge, transformative research, educate leaders and critical thinkers, and accelerate innovation that tackles societal issues. Our departments are renowned for the groundbreaking research that our faculty, staff, and students do. From undergraduate and graduate degrees to certificates, professional development, and workshop opportunities, CDIS helps students earn the tech skills they need to be successful leaders and strategic thinkers in their fields.

OTHER DATA SCIENCE-FOCUSED ORGANIZATIONS AT UW-MADISON

Department of Biostatistics and Medical Informatics (BMI) advances data science for medicine and public health through collaboration with biomedical scientists.

Institute for Foundations of Data Science (IFDS), funded by NSF's TRIPODS program, focuses on fundamental, theoretical issues in data science. IFDS faculty are involved in applications-focused projects.

Machine Learning and Optimization Research Consortium (MOR) works with industry partners to solve machine learning and optimization challenges in data analytics, healthcare systems, manufacturing, transportation, and other commercial applications.

Machine Learning for Medical Imaging (ML4MI) fosters interdisciplinary collaboration between machine learning experts and medical imaging researchers in order to solve problems in medical imaging.

MADLab is a University Center of Excellence supported by the Air Force Office of Scientific Research and the Air Force Research Lab to develop the next generation of machine learning theory, algorithms, and applications.

Wisconsin Institute for Discovery (WID)'s expertise in data science spans disciplines, with the goal of developing end-to-end strategies for data collection, analysis, management, privacy, security, and decision-making.

The American University of Paris

SUMMARY

Chartered as a liberal arts college in 1962, AUP is today an urban, independent, international university. Data science at AUP spans topics such as machine learning, artificial intelligence, algorithms, statistics and geographical information systems. Teaching and research cover a wide variety of application fields such as law, astrophysics, and literature.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Data Science at AUP spans across several disciplines and departments, including Computer Science, Mathematics, Environmental Science, and Politics, with contributions from faculty in departments across the university.

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- MSc in Human Rights and Data Science
- Undergraduate minor in Data Science

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 5
- Affiliated Members: 36

LOCATION

5, Boulevard de La Tour-Maubourg
75007 Paris, France

DATA SCIENCE AT AUP

AUP students have many occasions to explore the vibrant world of data science. They may dive into a cutting-edge Human Rights and Data Science master's program, opt for an undergraduate minor in Data Science, or just take an Environmental Data Science course.

In the real world

AUP students have regularly interned with institutions such as UNESCO, OECD, the International Chamber of Commerce and many NGOs and private companies. They have, for example, assisted CIOs in ensuring GDPR compliance, contributed to empowering young immigrants with data management skills, and analyzed data about education in war zones.

With responsibility

Data Science at AUP not only brings students to the City of Light but also to the country's home for one of the most effective watchdog organizations for technology on the continent, the CNIL, which has developed the most advanced regulatory frameworks for data, the GDPR and the AI Act. AUP students collaborate directly with these industry professionals in the classroom, ensuring an immersive and hands-on experience.

MASTER IN HUMAN RIGHTS AND DATA SCIENCE (HRDS)

The Master in Human Rights and Data Science (HRDS) at AUP prepares students to confront ethical questions at the forefront of emerging high-tech industries, exploring how technological development may complement human rights protections rather than impinge upon them. Courses combine a rigorous foundation in data science techniques with the legal and philosophical considerations necessary to ensure regulatory compliance and ethical implementation. The program concerns itself as much with the use of data centered software as it does with its development, with the human and social costs of emerging digital technologies as much as with the benefits.

SOCIAL

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THE HRDS CURRICULUM

The curriculum includes courses in data science and human rights law, as well as workshops allowing students to build a professional network and apply their knowledge on practical cases. Past workshops have been run by lead data scientists and data protection officers of large organizations, including MasterCard, the International Committee of the Red Cross, OECD, French Data Protection Authority, etc. Additionally, students have a chance to collaborate with the UNESCO Chair in Artificial Intelligence and Human Rights.

AUP's HRDS graduates will help alleviate the considerable shortage of experts in ethical AI confronting government and industry, thanks to their deep understanding of the fast-changing landscape of data-related technology and regulations.

STUDENTS WORK ON INTERDISCIPLINARY PROJECTS THAT HAVE REAL IMPACT

Their work has been presented at conferences worldwide; recent examples include, the Challenging Borders conference 2023 at Albion College, and the 2024 Conference of the Association for the Study of Ethnicity and Nationalism's (ASEN) on Nationalism and Memory.

DISTANT READING PROJECT

Development of Jupyter notebooks introducing Comparative Literature students to new counter-intuitive forms of literary analysis.

ML APPLICATIONS IN ASTROPHYSICS

Using data from ALMA, the largest telescope on the planet, to develop ML algorithms to detect spectral lines in multidimensional spectroscopic data-set.

MISSING AND MURDERED INDIGENOUS WOMEN (MMIW)

The project addresses the dearth of data and studies related to MMIW cases. Multiple sources of collection, analysis, localization, etc.

DEMOCRACY IN THE DIGITAL AGE

Re-framing Tocqueville's society of individuals for analysis in the digital age. Are technologies potentially disruptive to traditional democratic structures?

MINOR IN DATA SCIENCE

Data science can be applied to all fields of human endeavor – such as understanding environmental data or clinical trial data, building economic models, undertaking psychological studies or political and marketing analyses, or simply making sense of the huge swathes of data generated by our social media. Everyone is familiar with examples of how the interpretation of this data may be affected by biases and errors that result in unexpected and undesirable effects on particular groups. AUP's Minor in Data Science gives students the opportunity to learn about this burgeoning area, taking a critical approach. Students in the minor learn how to apply the data science process to their field of interest, discovering along the way the Python programming language, the essential notions of statistics and probability which underlie data science, and the ethical concerns surrounding the application of data science.

SUMMARY

NC State University is based in Raleigh, North Carolina. We're ranked in the top 1% of universities on the planet. NC State is a public institution with a duty to open the doors of education for everyone. We're a Research 1 university, recognized worldwide for big ideas and bigger impact.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

The DSA is a part of the Office of University Interdisciplinary Programs (OUIP) within the Provost Office at NC State.

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- Masters in Foundations of Data Science
- Masters in Analytics - Institute of Advanced Analytics
- Data Science in Business - Undergraduate Minor
- Data Science with Graphic and Experience Design - Undergraduate Minor
- Mathematical Data Science - Undergraduate Minor
- Many majors with concentrations in data science and AI
- Undergraduate Certificate of Data Science in Business
- Undergraduate Minor of Data Science in Analytics and Decision-Making

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Professional Staff: 8
- Affiliated Members: 50
- Students Enrolled: ~400 per semester

LOCATION

2 Broughton Drive
Campus Box 7111
Raleigh, NC 27695

DATA SCIENCE AT NC STATE

The Data Science and AI Academy (DSA) is the first academy at NC State and supports all aspects of the university's land-grant mission: research, teaching, and outreach. The courses, consulting, research enablement, and programming offered by the DSA reach all university colleges and facilitate conversations with communities beyond campus.

NC State is a leader in interdisciplinary teaching and learning, research, and outreach. The university's first academy reflects that leadership, signaling the importance of data science and AI around and across campus.

With the Data Science and AI Academy, NC State is better positioned than ever to provide opportunities and credentials to meet the needs in education and innovation.

The Data Science and AI Academy provides collaborative data science support to researchers and students at NC State. Working in coordination with the NC State University Libraries, graduate RAs with expertise in programming, data manipulation and cleaning, statistical and quantitative analyses, and data communication are available to consult on a broad range of projects on campus.

SOCIAL

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NC STATE UNIVERSITY

Data Science and AI Academy

THE ADAPT MODEL

The Data Science and AI Academy designs and delivers instruction through the ADAPT model: All-campus Data science through Accessible Project-based Teaching and learning model. Our courses are open to all learners and have included undergraduates, graduate students, faculty, staff, alumni and community members. Our courses have homework and projects, but no quizzes, tests or exams. Students complete projects, sometimes as a series of assignments or as a final project. Projects are hands-on, workforce-relevant ways to engage and retain ideas and skills.

DATA AT WORK

Data at Work is the Data Science and AI Academy's suite of training opportunities through continuing and executive education. The Data at Work courses provide deep dives into topics such as analytics with SAS and JMP, advanced Excel and Power BI, introductions to R and Python and the exploration of machine learning and artificial intelligence. All of the courses are customized, so participants use data and tools from their workplace and complete projects relevant to their jobs. All courses are designed and delivered through the DSA's All-campus Data science through Accessible Project-based Teaching and learning model (ADAPT Model) to prioritize learning experiences in which participants have the ability to make genuine choices from data-driven decision-making.

Uganda Institute of Information and Communications Technology

"In Quest of Excellence"

SUMMARY

UICT has enhanced its data science capacity through STEM recruitment and targeted training. It has developed an NCHE-accredited Diploma in Data Science Management and Analytics and professional short courses launching in 2025, alongside spearheading an Open Education Data Portal to drive evidence-based decision-making and innovation in Uganda's education sector.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Public Tertiary Institution

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- Diploma in Data Science Management and Analytics (DSMA)
- A variety of short courses targeting professionals seeking credentials in areas like ICT, cybersecurity, and digital transformation
- New short courses in 2025:
 - Data Management and Analytics
 - Data Science and Artificial Intelligence

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 15-20
- Professional Staff: 5
- Affiliated Members: 10-15
- Students Enrolled: ~150

LOCATION

Plot 7-21 Port Bell Road
P.O Box 7187
Kampala, Uganda

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

The Uganda Institute of Information and Communications Technology (UICT) offers a range of ICT and engineering courses designed to equip students with practical skills and theoretical knowledge. These include diploma programs in Computer Engineering, Telecommunications Engineering, Data Science Management and Analytics, and Information Technology. Short professional development courses are also available, focusing on e-governance, digital transformation, cybersecurity, software development, and networking.

What sets UICT courses apart is their emphasis on hands-on learning, industry-aligned curricula, and exposure to real-world challenges. Students gain practical experience through internships, lab-based projects, and collaboration with industry partners. The incorporation of emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence, mixed reality, and IoT ensures graduates are well-versed in the latest advancements.

Additionally, UICT fosters innovation and entrepreneurship through programs at the National ICT Innovation Hub, offering mentorship, funding opportunities, and a platform for showcasing student projects. These efforts produce graduates who are not only technically proficient but also problem solvers, innovators, and industry-ready professionals, highly competitive in Uganda's ICT sector and beyond.

THE ROLE OF DATA SCIENCE MANAGEMENT AND ANALYTICS IN UGANDA'S DEVELOPMENT

The Diploma in Data Science Management and Analytics (DSMA) stands out as a specialized program tailored to meet the growing demand for data-driven decision-making in Uganda. With industries like banking, telecommunications, manufacturing, and government generating vast datasets, the DSMA equips professionals with the expertise to extract actionable insights, enabling informed decisions and fostering innovation.

SOCIAL

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Aligned with Uganda's Vision 2040 and National Data Strategy, this program addresses the critical skills gap identified in the National Development Plan III/IV, focusing on areas such as business intelligence, artificial intelligence, and big data. Graduates of the DSMA are uniquely prepared for diverse career opportunities, including roles as Data Analysts, Artificial Intelligence Developers, Cybersecurity Specialists, Data Engineers, and Statisticians. This program's blend of technical rigor, practical application, and alignment with national priorities makes it a pivotal pathway for individuals and organizations aiming to thrive in a data-centric world.

EMPOWERING UGANDA'S DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION: UICT'S NEW PROGRAMS FOR 2025

In 2025, UICT will introduce a range of innovative diploma programs and short courses aimed at equipping students and professionals with cutting-edge, industry-relevant skills. These offerings, developed in collaboration with renowned international organizations, address emerging needs in key sectors. Notable programs include Software Engineering for Modern Applications, e-Government and Digital Transformation, and Mixed Reality for Teaching STEMI Subjects, alongside courses in Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence applied to agriculture, healthcare, education, finance, tourism, and oil and gas.

Additionally, UICT will provide specialized training such as Digital Literacy under the Parish Development Model, Digital Skills for Employability, IT Service Management, ICT for Non-ICT Professionals, and ICT Practitioners Certification Courses. Other offerings include Data Management and Analytics, ICT in Education Management, Teaching, Learning, and Testing, and Digital Marketing.

These programs are designed to empower participants with practical competencies for enhanced productivity, career advancement, and contributions to Uganda's digital transformation goals.

EMPOWERING INNOVATORS THROUGH THE NATIONAL ICT INNOVATION HUB AND ADVANCED TECHNOLOGY LABS

UICT manages the National ICT Innovation Hub in Nakawa on behalf of the Ministry of ICT and the Government of Uganda, creating a dynamic space for innovation and collaboration. The hub brings together tech entrepreneurs, software developers, data scientists, and creative designers to address local and global challenges in areas such as e-governance, fintech, agritech, healthtech, and digital transformation. It offers state-of-the-art facilities, expert mentorship, funding opportunities, and networking platforms to connect innovators with investors and collaborators.

Through training programs, hackathons, and expos, the hub fosters capacity building and supports scalable solutions. Additionally, UICT has established a Regional Mixed Reality Centre and the recently launched UCC Testbed Lab for emerging technology innovations and AVR Lab. These facilities provide students and professionals access to cutting-edge technologies in areas like augmented and virtual reality, enabling hands-on learning and innovation. This innovative ecosystem positions students to gain industry-relevant skills and drives growth in Uganda's ICT sector by nurturing talent and supporting transformative projects.

UNIVERSITY OF DELAWARE

DATA SCIENCE INSTITUTE

SUMMARY

The Institute aims to accelerate research in data science, serving as a nucleating effort to catalyze interdisciplinary research collaborations across fields impacting our society.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Cross-departmental Institute

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- Bioinformatics Data Science
- Business Analytics and Information Management
- Cybersecurity
- Data Science
- Economics
- Educational Statistics
- Electrical & Computer Engineering
- Epidemiology
- Financial Services Analytics
- Geospatial Data Science
- Hospitality Business Analytics
- Interdisciplinary Neuroscience
- Mathematics and Data Science
- Statistics
- Water Science and Policy

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 190+
- Professional Staff: 10
- Affiliated Members: 130+
- Students: 200+

LOCATION

590 Avenue 1743, Suite 147
Newark, DE 19713

INSTITUTE OVERVIEW

Serving as a hub for interdisciplinary research, collaboration and excellence, the DSI brings together faculty and students from ten colleges across campus to work effectively with big data and address problems and opportunities facing society—from health sciences, physical sciences, environmental sciences, to behavioral and social sciences and public policy. The Institute further involves partnerships with industry and other institutions in the region.

INSTITUTE PURPOSE AND DESIGN

DSI aims to accelerate collaborative research in, and application of, data science. The DSI operates through four working groups (WGs): **Research WG** to foster multidisciplinary collaborations and joint grants, **Infrastructure WG** to provide data and compute infrastructure, **Training WG** to facilitate training and development opportunities, and **Networking & External Relations WG** to host events and connect faculty, students, and industry and government partners.

DSI facilitates student training and education through support from federally funded training grants including **NSF HDR DSC**: Delaware and Mid-Atlantic Data Science Corps, **NSF NRT-HDR**: Computing and Data Science Training for Materials Innovation, Discovery, Analytics, and **NIH T32**: Graduate Training program in Computational Biology, Bioinformatics & Biomedical Data Science (CBB).

OUR FACULTY

DSI brings together more than 190 faculty from ten colleges and schools across campus to work collaboratively in a wide range of topics in foundations and applications of data science. DSI faculty at UD combine expertise in statistics, computer science, mathematics, information sciences and numerous related fields.

14 Resident Faculty across **8 colleges** were hired as a Presidential Strategic Initiative to complement the **130+ DSI Affiliated Faculty**. Resident Faculty lead the Certificate in Urban Data Science, PhD in Educational Statistics and Research Methods, and the NSF-funded Delaware and Mid-Atlantic Data Science Corps.

SOCIAL

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DSI STUDENT ASSOCIATION AND DSI FELLOWS

Students engage via the Data Science Student Association and DSI Fellows. The Data Science Student Association is a newly established student group open to all students interested in Data Science. DSI Fellows are graduate students and postdocs who serve as student leaders to help drive data science initiatives and student-hosted events such as the Data Science Community Hour and the Data Science Student Symposium.

DATA SCIENCE TRAINING AND EDUCATION

The interdisciplinary data science programs are offered through 12 graduate, undergraduate, and certificate programs including >110 data science-related courses. With a flexible set of core and elective courses, our data science programs facilitate expertise across a wide range of potential application areas. By offering a solid background in the theoretical and methodological underpinnings of data science, these programs also provide our graduates with a deep understanding of data, data science techniques, and associated ethical challenges. Together this ensures that our graduates are effective users of, and leaders in, the latest data science methods in their chosen field. Our degree programs and training grants are preparing students for an extensive variety of data science positions. Data analysts use mathematical, statistical, and modeling techniques to solve problems; data engineers design, build, and maintain an organization's data and analytical infrastructure; and data scientists create sophisticated analytical models to build data sets and derive new insights from data.

A more recent example includes the NSF-SCIFE funded Democratizing Access to Research Software Engineering (DARSE) initiative. This cyberinfrastructure professionals-oriented grant is working to create an educational pipeline for research software engineers (RSEs), building a team of RSE professionals and trainees, and engaging them in the advancement of computational, data-intensive, and AI-enabled science projects in the Mid-Atlantic region and beyond.

INDUSTRY ENGAGEMENT

DSI has established an **Industry Affiliate Program** to broaden industry engagement. Leveraging expert faculty across the University and cutting-edge data science capabilities and unique resources, industrial partners can:

- Address industry-wide problems through collaborative research projects
- Demonstrate, test, and improve high-risk / high-return concepts in a protected environment
- Gain access to powerful computational resources and expertise
- Participate in and co-host special events, e.g., lectures, seminar series, workshops, trainings, hackathons
- Access resources for workforce development, including certificates, short courses, and degree programs

The DSI-Fintech Consortium, launched in 2023, brings DSI's capabilities and resources to the Fintech community centered at the University's Fintech Innovation Hub.

DATA-INTENSIVE & COMPUTATIONAL SCIENCE (DiCoS) CORE FACILITY

The **Data Intensive & Computational Science (DiCoS) Core** supports interdisciplinary research collaborations and team science. DiCoS aims to advance both the research frontiers and the underlying infrastructure at the nexus of computational and data science, enabled by high-performance computing and big data.

DiCoS develops and guides the use of shared resources, such as the **DARWIN High Performance Computing System**, and scientific expertise to support data science and computational research. DiCoS identifies the needs of the research and education community, providing infrastructure support for computational and storage resources, research data sets, and scientific expertise.

SUMMARY

The power of data and models emerges from their uses and applications. RDS@Pitt innovates responsible teaching and research in data science that coherently fuses together computation with context to make positive impacts in our region and the world.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

University-wide initiative focused on responsibly applied data science across and between disciplines.

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- Data Science, BS
- Business Analytics, BSBA
- Computational Social Science, BS
- Computational Biology, BS
- Digital Narrative and Interactive Design, BA
- Actuarial Mathematics, BS
- Computational Modeling and Simulation, MS
- Professional Masters in Data Science, MDS
- Applied Statistics, MS
- Intelligent Systems, MS
- Business Analytics, MS
- PharmacoAnalytics, MS
- Biostatistics, MS
- Computational Biomedicine and Biotechnology
- Masters in Quantitative Economics, MQE
- Biomedical Informatics MS and PhD
- PharmacoMetrics and Systems Pharmacology, PhD

LOCATION

University of Pittsburgh
Responsible Data Science Initiative
Office of the Provost
801 Cathedral of Learning

INTERDISCIPLINARY RESPONSIBLE DATA SCIENCE (RDS) STUDENT SCHOLARS PROGRAM

The RDS Student Scholars Program at RDS@Pitt offers undergraduate students an interdisciplinary, extracurricular opportunity to explore the societal impacts of data and technology. Students from diverse fields—including humanities, social sciences, natural sciences, computer science, and engineering—collaborate to understand and apply fairness, transparency, and accountability principles to real-world data challenges. Through case studies and guided frameworks, participants gain practical insights into what defines responsible data science and its importance for communities and social good.

In the spring semester, students put their knowledge into action by creating a framework to assess responsible data science in a context of their choice, such as privacy in healthcare, generative AI, or university data policies. This hands-on learning experience equips students with the tools to approach data challenges thoughtfully and responsibly, preparing them to lead in shaping ethical practices in their future careers.

FLEXIBLE, ACCESSIBLE WORKFORCE TRAINING IN RESPONSIBLE APPLICATIONS OF DATA SCIENCE

The University of Pittsburgh received a generous grant from the Richard King Mellon Foundation to fund the creation of a diverse and networked workforce throughout Southwestern Pennsylvania. Designed to transform career paths by providing relevant, practical applications and accessible, impactful content certifications, Responsible Data Science@Pitt will build an innovative, coordinated set of professional training programs in responsible data science — using a synthesis of insights from both data and people to improve lives and communities at every scale.

These online programs will provide relevant tools and training to workers in Southwestern Pennsylvania who will learn responsible data science and management practices in industries that cover 80% of the top 20 employers — retail and marketing, banking and finance, government and the nonprofit sector, manufacturing and supply chain operations and public health — in Allegheny, Westmoreland, Washington, Butler, Beaver and Cambria counties.

SOCIAL

Email: mcolaresi@pitt.edu

Web: datascience.pitt.edu

LinkedIn: [Responsible Data Science@Pitt](https://www.linkedin.com/company/responsible-data-science-at-pitt)

PROFESSIONAL MASTERS IN DATA SCIENCE DEGREE

University of Pittsburgh has started a fully online Professional Master of Data Science (MDS) degree program, in partnership with Coursera. Through the program, participants will develop a deep understanding of core computational, mathematical and statistical concepts, responsible data management, and data curation skills (ethically cleaning, interpreting, and using big data across a variety of contexts). The program instructs professionals in programming, interpretation, and communication of data analytics through access to large, real-world data sources from campus, community and corporate partners.

DATA SCIENCE DAY AT THE UNIVERSITY OF PITTSBURGH

Data Science Day at the University of Pittsburgh is a one-of-a-kind event that brings together a diverse community of students, faculty, industry professionals, and community leaders to explore the transformative power of data. What sets this event apart is its emphasis on interdisciplinary collaboration and real-world impact. Showcasing innovative research, hands-on workshops, and engaging panel discussions, the day is designed to spark dialogue on how data science can address pressing societal challenges.

Attendees gain unique insights into the ethical and responsible use of data, with a strong focus on inclusivity, transparency, and community-driven solutions. From cutting-edge academic research to practical applications in health, industry, and the social sector, Data Science Day highlights how data science is shaping the future while empowering participants to lead in this dynamic field. This event is not just about showcasing advancements—it's about building connections, fostering innovation, and inspiring actionable change.

SUMMARY

Established in 2016, the University of San Francisco Data Institute (DI) advances data science and AI through research, education, and global partnerships. As a leader in innovation, the DI fosters industry-academia collaboration and drives social impact, shaping the future of technology in the Bay Area and beyond.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Interdisciplinary institute situated in the Office of the Provost

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- M.S. in Data Science (MSDS)
- B.S. in Data Science (BSDS)
- Certificates:
 - Advanced Python for Data Analysis
 - Applied Machine Learning
 - Data Science for Marketing
 - Digital Marketing Analytics
 - GenAI for Coders
 - Introduction to Data Ethics
 - Introduction to Machine Learning
 - Introduction to Probability and Statistics
 - Large Language Models for Coders
 - Machine Learning Operations
 - Mathematical Foundations for Data Science
 - Practical Deep Reinforcement Learning
 - Python for Data Analysis
- Specialization in Data Engineering (MSDS+DE)

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 7
- Professional Staff: 5
- Affiliated Members: 12
- Students: BSDS - 65, MSDS - 95

LOCATION

101 Howard Street, Suite 500
San Francisco, CA 94105

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

Established in 2016, the University of San Francisco's Data Institute serves as a central hub for interdisciplinary research, degree programs, and continuous education in applied data science and artificial intelligence. The institute offers a Master of Science in Data Science (MSDS) program, featuring a concentration in Data Engineering, a Bachelor of Science in Data Science (BSDS), and various professional certificate courses. It is home to the Center for AI & Data Ethics (CAIDE) and the Clinical Neuroinformatics & AI Laboratory, focusing on ethical AI practices and healthcare innovations, respectively.

Annually, the Data Institute collaborates with organizations in the Bay Area and beyond to address real-world data challenges, fostering partnerships that bridge industry and academia. With a diverse faculty from data science, mathematics, health informatics, and computer science, the institute is dedicated to advancing research, nurturing talent, and leveraging data-driven solutions to tackle pressing social, economic, and environmental issues.

SOCIAL

Email: datainstitute@usfca.edu

Web: usfca.edu/data-institute

X: @datainstitutesf

LinkedIn: The Data Institute, University of San Francisco

Facebook: USF Data Institute

Instagram: @USFDataInstitute

EMPOWERING CHANGE: THE DATA INSTITUTE'S CENTERS AND INITIATIVES

The University of San Francisco Data Institute's Centers and Initiatives provide resources, education, and services to support the campus community and external organizations alike. These efforts bridge academic research with practical applications, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and innovation in data science and artificial intelligence.

The **Center for AI and Data Ethics (CAIDE)** focuses on understanding and addressing the ethical challenges surrounding data, machine learning, and generative AI. CAIDE's work explores key aspects of Responsible AI, including bias, discrimination, human-AI interaction, explainable AI, data privacy, and regulation. Through research, public programming, and educational materials such as case studies and online courses, CAIDE seeks to raise awareness about the risks and opportunities of AI, promoting its responsible use across sectors.

The **Clinical Neuroinformatics and AI Lab (CNAIL)** is dedicated to advancing healthcare through artificial intelligence, with a focus on mental, neurological, and neurodevelopmental disorders. Led by Professor William Bosl, Ph.D., CNAIL leverages AI to develop clinically actionable tools that prioritize a holistic understanding of individuals, aligning with USF's mission of Cura Personalis. By collaborating with clinical partners such as the integrated health lab (iHealth Lab) at the School of Nursing and Health Professions, CNAIL is working to improve personalized healthcare. Its research emphasizes inclusion, ensuring AI algorithms represent marginalized populations while addressing critical health challenges. This innovative work strives to create AI technology that is not only impactful but also scalable for real-world clinical use.

SUMMARY

Established in 2018, the UTSA School of Data Science, now in a purpose-built building since January 2023, leads data science and AI programs. As the sole data-intensive institution at a Carnegie R1 U.S. Hispanic Serving Institution, it plays a pivotal role in UTSA's strategic growth plan, promoting impactful contributions.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

The UTSA School of Data Science is an academic support unit consisting of multi-disciplinary faculty offering graduate level degrees and data-intensive research

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- MS in Artificial Intelligence
- MS in Computer Science – Data Science Concentration
- MS in Data Analytics
- MS in Statistics and Data Science
- PhD in Applied Statistics
- UTSA also offers five BS degrees in scope of data science and AI
- Undergraduate Certificate in Data Science
- Graduate Certificate in Data Science
- Bootcamps in Coding and UX/UI

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 30
- Professional Staff: 12
- Students: 954

LOCATION

506 Dolorosa Street
San Antonio, TX 78204

NEW COLLEGE, SECOND NEW BUILDING:

In January 2024, UTSA announced its plan to evolve the school into a new college that embraces data science, cyber security, computing, and artificial intelligence. The new college will benefit from a second purpose-built building that will more than double the school's footprint of classrooms, collaboration and research spaces at the urban core of San Antonio, where its civic, cultural and technology districts intersect. The college should be fully established in 2025.

BEYOND THE CLASSROOM:

The School of Data Science makes possible interdisciplinary learning and discovery through:

- 17 research projects and spaces advancing AI safety and security, the Internet of Things (IoT), data engineering, ML optimization, robotics, and more.
- Immersive data science and AI summer programs for students, partnering with:
 - Public service agencies/not-for-profits in Texas
 - International universities – Tecnológico de Monterrey and Instituto Tecnológico Autónomo de México
- Research collaboration centers:
 - City of San Antonio
 - U.S. Census Bureau
- A conference center to host local, regional, and national events – in 2023, over 10,000 people attended events and programs at the school.
- Cutting-edge Dell Technologies Roadrunner Data Center handling tens of AI and ML appliances and hundreds of virtual server applications.

SOCIAL

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X: @utsadata

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BEYOND OUR BORDERS:

The School of Data Science is a committed and contributing member to the national Academic Data Science Alliance, for which it hosted the 2023 Annual Meeting. The conference featured three full days of parallel sessions covering topics from basic data science concepts to advanced biomedical analysis. Keynote speakers included Chief Data Scientist of the United States Dr. Dominique Duval-Diop, internationally acclaimed artist and sculptor Sebastian, and AI expert Dr. Besa Bauta.

ANNUAL OPPORTUNITIES FOR THE NATIONAL DATA SCIENCE COMMUNITY AND ASPIRING STUDENTS

Los Datos Conference: This annual conference unites data science professionals, fostering collaboration and innovation. This event showcases insights, advancements, and knowledge-sharing in data science, AI, and related fields. The 2024 conference, on **April 9-10**, emphasized AI security through informative sessions, workshops, and networking opportunities.

Draper Data Science Business Plan Competition: This annual competition, backed by venture capitalist Tim Draper, spotlights innovative student entrepreneurs in North America and encourages and recognizes exceptional startups leveraging data science. Students can network with potential investors, industry leaders, and fellow entrepreneurs. The competition was **April 12, 2024**.

Rowdy Datathon: Hundreds of students from Texas and beyond gather each Fall at the UTSA School of Data Science for an exciting weekend of competition at the annual Rowdy Datathon. Organized by the Association of Computing Machinery (ACM) at UTSA in collaboration with the National Security Agency, the Datathon provides a platform for students to engage in a weekend-long data science exploration.

SUMMARY

Knowledge Enterprise, in partnership with ASU Research Computing, provides data science solutions for research that collects, analyzes or visualizes data. We can assist with the identification and collection of data, undertake technology needs assessments for your project, co-create machine learning solutions and visualize complex datasets. Data and Data Sciences also connects with faculty labs across the University.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

We operate as team of data scientists and project managers along with embedded faculty partners and advisors.

SOCIAL

Email: msimeone@asu.edu

Web:
cores.research.asu.edu/data-and-data-sciences/about

LOCATION

Fulton Center
300 E University Drive
PO Box 877205
Tempe, AZ 85287-7205

THE DATA AND DATA SCIENCES CORE

Data and Data Sciences Core is a hub for data science research opportunities that combines student mentorship, faculty engagement, and data science services to provide a central place for the advancement of data science research.

The Data and Data Sciences Core specializes in the following areas:

Devise and plan early data science research

DDS assists researchers in formulating approaches and strategies for their data-driven work. Researchers can collaborate with DDS experts to devise tailored plans that align with their research objectives, ensuring a strong foundation for research that uses data and/or machine learning.

Request data science advice for a proposal

DDSC provides consultations for researchers crafting proposals. Whether refining research questions or outlining methodology, researchers can work with DDS to devise a scope of work, project timeline, and budget to meet research objectives and grant requirements.

Hiring for data science research and work

Comprising a diverse cohort of students and staff dedicated to ongoing learning and professional development, DDSC provides an environment for recruiting individuals passionate about advancing data-driven research and innovation. Researchers seeking skilled collaborators or support staff can leverage DDSC's network to identify candidates with the expertise and enthusiasm to contribute meaningfully to their projects.

Discuss building or acquiring research datasets

DDSC assists researchers in sourcing, organizing and curating datasets tailored to their specific research needs. Moreover, DDSC fosters collaboration and knowledge exchange, enabling researchers to explore opportunities for dataset acquisition through partnerships with other research units, industry partners and external organizations.

Learn more at:

<https://cores.research.asu.edu/data-and-data-sciences/about>

ADSA EVENT SPONSORSHIP

Sponsorship enables ADSA to bring you productive and engaging projects and events, including the **Data Science Leadership Summit** and **ADSA Annual Meeting**. Sponsorship also promotes access to a wider, more diverse audience by enabling video recording, travel funding, scholarships, and more.

WHICH EVENTS CAN I SPONSOR?

- Data Science Leadership Summit
- ADSA Annual Meeting
- Special Topics Workshops

WHAT ARE THE BENEFITS OF SPONSORSHIP?

- **Tiered pricing** for different sectors
- **Free or discounted registration** at your sponsored event
- **Shout-outs** in digital and print communications
- **Custom sponsorships** - contact us with your ideas

I'M READY! WHAT'S NEXT?

Send an email to
info@AcademicDataScience.org
and let's discuss the options!

Sponsoring an
ADSA event is
easy as 1, 2, 3!

STEP 1:
Choose which
meeting to sponsor

STEP 2:
Choose a sponsorship
level

STEP 3:
Contact us to kick off
your sponsorship!

See a full list of sponsorship
opportunities at
tinyurl.com/ADSA-sponsorship

Learn more:
tinyurl.com/ADSA-sponsorship

BROWN

Data Science Institute

SUMMARY

Brown's DSI strives to stimulate innovation and support people aspiring to improve lives in our data-driven world. Reaching across Brown's campus and beyond, we educate all in data science and data fluency; Stimulate large-scale multidisciplinary research; and ensure that the power of data be leveraged toward a more equitable society.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

The DSI is an interdisciplinary institute with research centers and academic programs for undergraduate and graduate students.

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- Master's in Data Science
- Undergraduate and doctoral certificates

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 7
- Affiliated Members: 82
- Students: 80

LOCATION

164 Angell St., 3rd Floor
Providence, RI 02912

THE DSI COMMUNITY

The DSI community consists of core and affiliated faculty, and the graduate students, postdocs, and undergraduates who work with our faculty and in our research centers, the Center for Technological Responsibility, Re-imagination and Re-design (CNTR) and the Center for Computational Molecular Biology.

The CNTR's mission is to redefine computer science education, research, and technology to center the needs, problems and aspirations of all those that technology has left behind. Its work is transdisciplinary, incorporating insights and scholarships from all relevant disciplines to have the most impact. The CNTR collaborates with units across campus with an emphasis on research to affect policy.

The prime intellectual mission of the CCMB is to promote the development, implementation, and application of analytical and computational methods to foundational questions in the biological and medical sciences. The research programs of the core faculty in CCMB lie fundamentally at the intersection of computer science, evolutionary biology, mathematics, and molecular and cellular biology. The CCMB offers Ph.D. and Sc.B. degrees in Computational Biology.

SOCIAL

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X: @Brown_DSI

LinkedIn: Data Science Institute, Brown University

Facebook: Brown University Data Science Institute

Instagram: @brown_dsi

YouTube: @browndatascienceinstitute

ACADEMIC PROGRAMS

In addition to the Computational Biology programs, we offer an undergraduate certificate in Data Fluency, as well as a master's degree and a doctoral certificate in data science.

The undergraduate certificate is for undergraduate students who wish to gain fluency and facility with the tools of data analysis and its conceptual framework, but who are not pursuing a concentration in a data-intensive discipline. The program provides fundamental conceptual knowledge and technical skills to students with a range of intellectual backgrounds and concentrations, while emphasizing a critical liberal learning perspective.

Brown University's Data Science Initiative offers two master's programs. The residential program (12-24 months) provides comprehensive training in data science methods and algorithms through mathematics, statistics, and computer science, covering topics such as machine learning, deep learning, and database engineering, along with ethical considerations. Brown Ph.D. students can also pursue a master's or certificate. The 16-month online master's focuses on Policy, Governance & Society, featuring an interdisciplinary curriculum that strengthens technical expertise while fostering an ethical mindset for driving innovation responsibly.

DATA SCIENCE FELLOWS

The Data Science Fellows program is a collaboration between the DSI and Brown's Sheridan Center for Teaching and Learning, modeled on Brown's Writing Fellows program. Data Science Fellows are undergraduate students who each partner with a participating faculty member to infuse data science tools and practice in existing undergraduate courses. Fellows work with faculty in all disciplines, from neuroscience and chemistry to German and Arabic language instruction to the visual arts. A related program is the Data Science Course Design Institute—a workshop offered to faculty from any discipline who wish to develop new, or enhance existing data science related content in their courses.

Carnegie Mellon University

Statistics & Data Science

SUMMARY

A private, global research university, Carnegie Mellon stands among the world's most renowned educational institutions, and sets its own course. Data science is no exception. The Department of Statistics & Data Science is a leader in statistical theory, interdisciplinary applied research, large-scale computing, and prepares you to innovate with data.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

The Department of Statistics & Data Science is housed within the Dietrich College of Humanities and Social Sciences.

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- BS in Statistics
- BS in Statistics and Machine Learning
- BS in Economics and Statistics
- BS in Statistics (Mathematical Sciences Track)
- BS in Statistics (Neuroscience Track)
- MS in Applied Data Science
- PhD in Statistics
- Joint PhD Programs in:
 - Statistics and Machine Learning
 - Statistics and Public Policy
 - Statistics and Engineering and Public Policy
 - Statistics and Neural Computation
- Foundations of Data Science Online Graduate Certificate

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 30+
- Professional Staff: 15
- Students: 750+

LOCATION

5000 Forbes Ave
Pittsburgh, PA 15213

UNDERGRADUATE PROGRAM

The Statistics & Data Science undergraduate curriculum offers an engaging, flexible, and high-quality experience. Emphasizing modern statistical and computational methods, strong communication skills, and extensive hands-on experience with the analysis of data from real, interdisciplinary problems, we offer several majors and tracks that can be tailored to meet different goals and interests. Data skills and statistical thinking are increasingly sought after by corporations, government, and researchers in many areas. A degree in Statistics & Data Science at Carnegie Mellon will prepare you to meet that demand.

MASTER OF SCIENCE IN APPLIED DATA SCIENCE (MADS)

The primary focus of our 9-month, two-semester professional master's degree is to develop industry-valued competencies in our students by emphasizing data analysis, statistical computing, and professional skills. The MADS program builds foundational skills in statistical computing and data analysis, and it is also intended to assist students in identifying and focusing on industries and positions relevant to their aptitudes and interests, navigating the job market, and positioning graduates to successfully navigate careers post-graduation. MADS graduates have successfully gained positions as data scientists, data analysts, and data engineers in diverse industries such as banking, sports, health care, government, and tech.

SOCIAL

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LinkedIn: Carnegie Mellon University - Statistics & Data Science

Carnegie Mellon University
Statistics & Data Science

PH.D. PROGRAM

Our Statistics & Data Science Ph.D. programs enable students to pursue a wide range of research opportunities, including constructing and implementing advanced data analysis methods to address crucial cross-disciplinary questions, along with developing the underlying foundational theory and computational methods. We also offer four joint Ph.D. programs for students who want to specialize in machine learning, public policy, neuroscience, and the link between engineering and policy.

Our faculty have deep involvement in a range of important, data-rich scientific collaborations, including in the areas of genetics, neuroscience, astronomy, and the social sciences, allowing students to have easy access to both the crucial questions in these fields, and to the data that can provide the answers.

SUMMER UNDERGRADUATE RESEARCH EXPERIENCE

The Summer Undergraduate Research Experience provides students with hands-on experience working with real data, on real problems, in a stimulating, collaborative, and supportive environment. Over the course of a two-month period, students attend daily lectures and build their data science portfolio with projects partnered with external clients. The program exposes undergraduates to a variety of topics in statistics and data science, with previous application themes including sports analytics and healthcare technology.

FOUNDATIONS OF DATA SCIENCE GRADUATE CERTIFICATE

With fundamental skills in data science, professionals can make more data-informed decisions and lead with confidence to help their teams (and ultimately, their companies) achieve goals and reach targets more efficiently.

You don't need a technical background to think like a data scientist. You just need the right education and support. In Carnegie Mellon's new online Graduate Certificate in Foundations of Data Science, professionals from all backgrounds (both technical and non-technical) will learn how to unlock the power of data through graduate-level, credit-bearing coursework taught by expert CMU professors.

COLUMBIA UNIVERSITY DATA SCIENCE INSTITUTE

SUMMARY

The Data Science Institute (DSI) advances the state-of-the-art in data science and AI; transforms all fields, professions, and sectors through the application of data science and AI; and promotes the responsible use of data and ethical AI to benefit society. We train data scientists, develop innovative technology, foster research collaborations, work with industry to bring promising ideas to market, and are the operational home for the university-wide Columbia AI initiative.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Cross-departmental Institute

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- M.S. in Data Science
- Ph.D. with a specialization in Data Science
- Certification of Professional Achievement in Data Sciences

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Staff:
 - 4 Research Scientists and Scholars
 - 19 Postdoctoral Researchers
- Affiliated Members: 400+
- Students: 410 Graduate Students (Fall 2024)

SOCIAL

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Web: datascience.columbia.edu

LinkedIn: The Data Science Institute at Columbia University

Instagram: @DataSciColumbia

LOCATION

Northwest Corner Building
550 West 120th Street Suite 1401
New York, N.Y. 10027

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

Founded in 2012, Columbia's Data Science Institute (DSI) brings together the university's expertise in computer science, statistics, and industrial engineering and operations research to integrate data science and the application of artificial intelligence into every discipline - from hard science and social science to law, policy and everything in between. DSI also leads the Columbia AI initiative, which coordinates and showcases the breadth of interdisciplinary research and application of AI that exists in every school and department of the University.

As a pioneering force in these fields, DSI is uniquely positioned to drive innovation and expand the reach of data science across the university and beyond. Our mission is guided by the principle of "Data for Good"—leveraging data science and AI to address some of society's most pressing challenges, including healthcare, climate adaptation, and more - with the goal of using data and AI to benefit society. By fostering interdisciplinary collaboration, we harness data-driven insights from diverse domains to create meaningful impact in a rapidly evolving, data-rich world.

DEGREE, SPECIALIZATION, AND RESEARCH OPPORTUNITIES

MS in Data Science - One of the most highly-rated and competitive data science programs in the world, our data science students learn both theory and application through technically rigorous coursework, capstone projects, participation in original research, and interactions with our industry partners and world-class faculty.

PhD with a specialization in Data Science - The Data Science PhD specialization offers candidates pursuing PhDs in Applied Mathematics, Computer Science, Electrical Engineering, Industrial Engineering and Operations research, and Statistics the opportunity to pursue cutting-edge research and innovation and join leading experts on the frontiers of basic and applied data science.

Certification of Professional Achievement in Data Sciences - This certification is a non-degree, part-time program focused on preparing students to expand their career prospects or change career paths by developing foundational data science skills.

Postdoctoral Research Scientist Program - The Data Science Institute fosters cutting-edge research through this program that brings newly minted PhDs to the university to engage in cutting-edge, transdisciplinary research at the intersection of data science and other domains. This prestigious program draws top-tier data science research talent to work closely with Columbia faculty to advance novel research agendas.

KEY INSTITUTE INITIATIVES

DSI's flagship annual event, Data Science Day, showcases expertise through keynote presentations, research lightning talks, live demonstrations, and posters. Keynote speakers have included Alfred Spector (Two Sigma), Diane Greene (Google Cloud), Brad Smith (Microsoft), Eric Schmidt (Google), Pat Bajari (Amazon), and Prabhakar Raghavan (Google).

The **DSI Seed Fund Program** supports and awards funding for novel and transformative research collaborations between data scientists and domain experts across Columbia University.

The **Collaboratory**, co-founded by The Campbell Center for Entrepreneurship Columbia Entrepreneurship and DSI, supports the development of innovative, interdisciplinary curricula to embed data or computational science into traditional domains and embed business, policy, cultural, and ethical topics into data and computer science.

The **DSI Scholars Program** provides undergraduate and graduate students with enriching research opportunities led by faculty, industry, non-profits, and community based organizations. to projects led by faculty, nonprofits, community organizations, and government agencies.

M.S. in Data Science Capstone Projects connects faculty, industry, and government representatives with graduate students to build data science solutions across a range of fields.

The **DSI Campus Connections** initiative matches data science students to collaborate on both short-term, discrete projects and ongoing, complex work.

The **DSI Industry Affiliates Program** facilitates interactions between companies and Columbia faculty and students. DSI Industry Affiliates participate in a range of programs, including research opportunities, events, and talent recruiting.

DSI works with **Columbia Technology Ventures** and **Columbia Entrepreneurship** to support students and faculty with an interest in developing data science startups. DSI provides support with venture creation and attracting investors.

The **Northeast Big Data Innovation Hub** addresses societal and scientific challenges using data science approaches, spurs economic development, and accelerates innovation in the national big data ecosystem.

WHAT PEOPLE ARE SAYING ABOUT DSI

"I love how students are encouraged to branch out across departments and engage in projects with faculty and other students across the university."

- Kailande Cassamajor, Class of 2023, B.S., Biology and Psychology, Howard University

"I found it to be a well-rounded program—not just technical, but also applied. I appreciate how students are given the opportunity to use cutting-edge tools on real problems."

- Alberto Munguia Cisneros, Class of 2021, VP, Risk Management @ Morgan Stanley

"I ended up picking Columbia for the rigorous academic curriculum and the fact that the New York City area is a prominent tech hub."

- Carlo Provinciali, Class of 2020, Data Scientist @ Latch

Georgia Tech

Institute for Data Engineering and Science

SUMMARY

The Institute for Data Engineering and Science supports research in data science foundations and data-driven discovery. Foundational areas of focus include machine learning, artificial intelligence, high-performance computing, algorithms, statistics, and optimization. The institute supports data-driven research in many areas including astrophysics, chemistry, biology, medicine, materials science, energy, and smart cities.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Cross-departmental Institute

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- M.S. in Analytics
- M.S. in Analytics - online
- Ph.D. in Machine Learning
- Computational Data Analysis Minor
- Computing and Intelligence Minor
- B.S. in Industrial Engineering - Analytics and Data Science

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 50
- Professional Staff: 12
- Affiliated Members: 200
- Students:
 - M.S. in Analytics:
 - 154 on campus
 - 5,239 online
 - Ph.D. in Machine Learning: 123

LOCATION

CODA Building, 12th Floor
756 W Peachtree St NW
Atlanta, GA 30308

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

The institute operates the NSF South Big Data Regional Innovation Hub, in collaboration with the Renaissance Computing Institute at UNC. The Hub serves the Southern U.S. census region (16 Southern states from Delaware to Texas, Washington DC, Puerto Rico, the U.S. Virgin Islands, and territories). The Hub nurtures multi-stakeholder big data partnerships to find data-driven solutions to regional, national, and societal challenges. Areas of particular focus include health disparities, environment, materials and manufacturing, smart cities and communities, team science, data sharing and cyberinfrastructure, and data science education and workforce development. The Hub has an extensive network of more than 1300 members from universities, government labs, corporations, and foundations.

For more information, please visit <https://southbigdatahub.org/>

SOUTHBDHUB

SOCIAL

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X: @IDEaSatGT

LinkedIn: Georgia Tech Research

MACHINE LEARNING PH.D. PROGRAM

The machine learning (ML) Ph.D. program is a collaborative venture between Georgia Tech's colleges of Computing, Engineering, and Sciences. The curricular requirements include four core and five elective courses, a qualifying exam, and a doctoral dissertation defense. Students are admitted through one of eight participating home units. More information can be found at ml.gatech.edu/phd.

ANALYTICS M.S. PROGRAM

The Master of Science in Analytics is an interdisciplinary analytics and data science program that leverages the strengths of Georgia Tech in statistics, operations research, computing, and business by combining the world-class expertise of the Scheller College of Business, the College of Computing, and the College of Engineering. By blending the strengths of these nationally ranked programs, graduates will learn to integrate skills in a unique and interdisciplinary way that yields deep insights into analytics problems. Students can join the program on-campus or through the online offering. More information can be found at analytics.gatech.edu.

COMPUTATIONAL SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING M.S. AND PH.D. PROGRAMS

The Computational Science and Engineering (CSE) M.S. and Ph.D. programs are interdisciplinary programs offered by the College of Computing, the College of Engineering, and the College of Sciences. These graduate programs emphasize the integration and application of principles from mathematics, science, engineering and computing to create computational and data-driven models for solving important real-world problems. Students will be required to obtain a breadth of knowledge across a set of core areas, depth of knowledge in a specific computational specialization, and knowledge to apply computational and data-driven techniques in a domain of application. For the Ph.D. program, students will be expected to create significant computational artifacts (e.g., software), and complete independent research that advances the state-of-the-art. More information can be found at cse.gatech.edu/academics.

URBAN ANALYTICS M.S. PROGRAM

The M.S. in Urban Analytics (MSUA) program is a joint venture between the School of City and Regional Planning, the School of Industrial and Systems Engineering, the School of Computational Science and Engineering, and the School of Interactive Computing. MSUA is a one-year program (three semesters), designed to give graduates a core of computing, urban planning, and data analysis and visualization skills to identify, analyze, and solve urban problems. Students will integrate those skills in an interdisciplinary way that other, single-discipline-oriented urban analytics degrees might not, and will experience a depth of urban problems addressable with data analytics. More information can be found at planning.gatech.edu/master-science-urban-analytics.

IOWA STATE UNIVERSITY™

Data Science

SUMMARY

Iowa State University is a leading R-1 public research university in science and technology. Iowa State is recognized for its innovative research, commitment to student success, and contributions to economic development through hands-on learning and real-world experience.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Cross-departmental Institute

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- B.S. in Data Science
- Undergraduate Minor in Data Science
- Data Science Certificate

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Affiliated Members: 10
- Students: 145 total
 - 94 Majors
 - 51 Minors

SOCIAL

Email:

datascience@iastate.edu

Web: datascience.iastate.edu

LOCATION

2438 Osborn Dr
Ames, IA 50011-1090

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

Data science students at Iowa State University gain skills, knowledge, and career preparation through undergraduate research, internships, capstone projects, and other real-world experiences. Iowa State is also recognized nationally for its many student innovation programs and is ranked #12 nationally (Princeton Review) for undergraduate entrepreneurship.

DATA SCIENCE FOR PUBLIC GOOD

One way Iowa State students shape the future is through the Data Science for the Public Good (DSPG) Young Scholars program. This immersive summer program engages students from across Iowa to work together on projects that address local and state government challenges around critical social issues relevant in the world today. DSPG resident scholars conduct research at the intersection of statistics, computation, and the social sciences to determine how information generated within every community can be leveraged to improve quality of life and inform public policy. This program provides an excellent opportunity to develop a professional portfolio, expand your networks, and learn about the application of data science.

Academic
Data Science
Alliance

March 31 - April 2 in Columbus, OH

DATA SCIENCE LEADERSHIP SUMMIT

The DSL convenes leadership and faculty of current and nascent data science programs to share best practices where they face similar challenges and opportunities; and to take collective responsibility in preparing next-generation data scientists to contribute in the best interests of society.

Keynote Speaker

Dr. Kyle Cranmer

is the Director of the UW-Madison Data Science Institute, a Professor of Physics, and Editor-in-Chief of *Machine Learning Science and Technology*. In 2021 he became a Fellow of the American Physical Society for his work at the Large Hadron Collider. Professor Cranmer developed a framework that enables collaborative statistical modeling, which was used extensively for the discovery of the Higgs boson in 2012. His current interests are at the intersection of physics, statistics, and machine learning.

Learn More:

tinyurl.com/2025-Leadership-Summit

SUMMARY

In addition to the Institute for Data Science, NJIT established the Department of Data Science in 2021 as the newest addition to the Ying Wu College of Computing. The Department of Data Science offers undergraduate and graduate degrees, as well as graduate certificates, giving students the knowledge and skills needed to find success in the rewarding field of data science. To learn more about the programs offered please visit ds.njit.edu/programs.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Cross-departmental institute

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- B.S. in Data Science
- M.S. in Data Science
- Ph.D. in Data Science
- Certificate in Big Data Essentials
- Certificate in Data Mining
- Certificate in Data Visualization

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 11
- Professional Staff: 1
- Affiliated Members: 9

LOCATION

Newark, New Jersey

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

Headed by Distinguished Professor David Bader, the Institute for Data Science focuses on cutting-edge interdisciplinary research and development in all areas pertinent to digital data. Beyond academic research, the institute interacts closely with the outside world to identify and solve important problems in the modern data-driven economy.

RESEARCH AT NJIT

The Institute houses four research centers:

- The Center for Big Data;
- The Cybersecurity Research Center;
- The Structural Analysis of Biomedical Ontologies Center (SABOC);
- The Center for AI Research.

MISSION OF THE DEPARTMENT OF DATA SCIENCE

The Mission of the Department of Data Science is to:

- Educate students in a field that has ushered in a once-in-a-generation revolution, comparable to the industrial revolution and the original computing revolution.
- Provide an environment for leading-edge research that has a strong and rapid impact on the economy and that reestablishes New Jersey as a world leader in technological advancement.
- Create a source of scholarship on the many technical, ethical, and privacy issues that ubiquitous data creation is constantly confronting us with.
- Establish a center of technology knowledge and a "go-to organization" to service data creators, providers, managers, curators, and users of the State and the Nation.

SOCIAL

Email: info.datascience@njit.edu

Web: datascience.njit.edu

Vision Statement:

The data revolution has created novel challenges and unprecedented opportunities. The vision of the Department of Data Science is to create a first-class academic department that trains the next generation of students as data scientists who will solve these grand challenges and innovate through world-class research to take advantage of these opportunities.

M.S. AND GRADUATE CERTIFICATES IN ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

The M.S. in Artificial Intelligence and Graduate Certificate in Artificial Intelligence equip students with the theoretical and practical knowledge in applied machine learning and AI techniques to formulate solutions to real-world problems.

AI uses computers and modern software technology to achieve the outcomes of human problem-solving and decision-making abilities, and comprises methods to solve problems that are easy for humans but hard for digital computers. Numerous industries, including manufacturing, healthcare, finance, and even the fight against climate change, use AI. Students will have the opportunity to collaborate with faculty on projects involving applications in bioengineering, healthcare, cybersecurity, data analytics, finance, and many other fields.

**Impact the Present
Innovate the Future**

M.S. in

**Artificial
Intelligence**

**Graduate Certificates in
Artificial Intelligence**

PennState

Institute for Computational and Data Sciences

SUMMARY

The Institute of Computational and Data Sciences (ICDS) at Penn State advances knowledge through computational methods and data analytics. We foster interdisciplinary collaboration, provide cutting-edge resources, and support innovative projects to solve complex problems and drive scientific discovery and societal impact.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Cross-departmental Institute

PROGRAM STATISTICS

Core Faculty: 45
Professional Staff: 49
Affiliated Members: 325

LOCATION

University Park, PA

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

ICDS supports Penn State faculty in catalyzing and leading multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary research teams synthesizing domain expertise with advanced computational and data science approaches to address research questions of scientific and societal importance. This includes a network of 45 co-hired faculty from 28 departments, access to advanced computational infrastructure and access to advanced technical and software engineering consulting.

CENTER OVERVIEW

ICDS catalyzes transformative, interdisciplinary, computational, and data-driven discovery for the benefit of all. The institute provides the nexus for interdisciplinary communities of scholars creating and employing advanced tools in the computational and data sciences to achieve groundbreaking scientific discoveries. Throughout Penn State's colleges and campuses, scientists are using computational and data sciences to accelerate their work, discover new insights, and increase the impact of their research on society. ICDS directly supports a number of research centers at Penn State that are dedicated to researching problems of societal and scientific importance through the application of computational and data sciences. These initiatives bring together researchers and facilitate interdisciplinary collaborations, deepening connections among research thrusts. ICDS provides seed grant funding, identifies areas of future computational and data sciences research, and strengthens grant proposals for major external opportunities.

- Algorithm Development
- Artificial Intelligence
- Big Data
- Cloud Computing
- Data Analysis
- Data Storage
- Data Visualization
- Data-Driven Decision-Making
- High-Performance Computing
- Machine Learning
- Natural Language Processing
- Predictive Modeling
- Statistical Analysis

SOCIAL

Email: icds@psu.edu

Web: icds.psu.edu

LinkedIn: [Penn State Institute for Computational and Data Sciences](#)

FACILITIES OVERVIEW

Roar is the supercomputing system ICDS manages and operates for the Penn State research community. Thousands of researchers, from undergraduate students to distinguished faculty, use Roar each year for cutting-edge work.

RISE — Research Innovations with Scientists and Engineers — is a team of ICDS computational scientists and software engineers who can help you bring the power of high-performance computing to your research projects.

In addition to significant investments in AI, sustainable computing, gravitational research, and more, ICDS provides cutting-edge immersive technologies, knowledge, and skills to the Penn State community.

THE CENTER FOR IMMERSIVE EXPERIENCES

The Center for Immersive Experiences (CIE) at Penn State University is dedicated to advancing fundamental and applied research efforts through the use of immersive technologies. Located in the Pattee Library, the CIE team works with faculty members to support the creation of novel immersive experiences and provides faculty with access to state-of-the-art virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), and mixed reality (MR) equipment. The Center fosters interdisciplinary research by offering seed grants to support transdisciplinary research and diverse outreach activities across all disciplines at Penn State. CIE's mission is to create and foster a hub of digital innovation, leveraging xR technologies, to advance the

intellectual merit and broader impacts of foundational scientific efforts across Penn State. The Center supports local and national outreach efforts aimed at supporting the next generation of workers, leveraging immersive technologies to prepare current and future workers. By providing access to VR/AR/MR hardware and expertise, the Center for Immersive Experiences empowers the Penn State community to explore and harness the potential of immersive technologies to solve complex problems and make a significant societal impact.

THE CENTER FOR APPLICATIONS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND MACHINE LEARNING TO INDUSTRY (AIMI)

AIMI at ICDS and Penn State connects businesses with cutting-edge AI/ML expertise to solve real-world problems and seize market opportunities. Serving both SMEs and large corporations, AIMI focuses on solutions that impact production, manufacturing, and services. As part of the Institute for Computational and Data Sciences, AIMI leverages ICDS infrastructure and services, fosters partnerships with Penn State faculty and industry leaders, and offers fellowships to researchers to promote collaborative projects.

THE CENTER FOR ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE FOUNDATIONS AND SCIENTIFIC APPLICATIONS (CENSAI)

CENSAI at ICDS and Penn State aims to accelerate scientific progress through interdisciplinary AI research. It focuses on literature-based discovery, scientific knowledge representation, experiment planning and optimization, machine learning and causal inference, and human-AI collaboration. Located within the Institute for Computational and Data Sciences, CENSAI provides state-of-the-art AI tools and resources for students, faculty, and staff and fosters interdisciplinary collaboration by offering grants to support innovative AI research and educational activities across various scientific domains.

The **ICDS Project Management Office (PMO)** employs engineering project management best practices to support research programming and computing initiatives that leverage ICDS or national computing resources. Our team aids faculty and researchers in fostering multi-disciplinary and cross-institutional collaborations, promoting seamless communications between technical and research teams, and upholding standards of excellence for high-impact results in both funded and exploratory research.

SUMMARY

The Data Intensive Studies Center at Tufts is a cross-university center focused on enabling data-intensive research, scholarship and education.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Cross-departmental center

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- Data Science M.S.
- Data Analytics M.S.
- Data Science Certificate
- Data Analytics Certificate
- Specializations in:
 - Biomedical statistics
 - Bioinformatics
 - Bayesian statistics
 - Algorithmic fairness
 - Machine learning
 - Agent-based modeling
 - Uncertainty quantification
 - Scientific computing
 - Computational mathematics

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 3
- Professional Staff: 5
- Affiliated Members: 6
- Students: 100

LOCATION

Joyce Cummings Center
177 College Ave.
3rd Floor Suite 336
Medford, MA 02155

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

The Data Intensive Studies Center expresses the idea of a vital hub that cultivates collaborations and fosters a culture where computational, data and statistical sciences are highly valued. The center provides a clear framework that brings together an array of disciplines, working across existing departments, schools, and campuses to facilitate cutting-edge research and to prepare Tufts graduates for a future in which data analytics is increasingly important. As a nexus, the Center also hosts various activities, including forums, mini-symposia, and seminars.

TRAINING AND WORKSHOPS

The Data Intensive Studies Center offers training workshops in data and computing sciences with contributors from several academic units including Tufts Technology Services and Tufts Clinical and Translational Science Institute and the Tufts Data Lab. Short 3-hour workshops as well as multi day 15-hour workshops have been offered on topics such as Bayesian Methods, Bioinformatics, Data Visualization, and Introductory Python Programming. Workshops are open to all students, faculty and staff.

DISCIPLINARY PARTNERSHIPS

Data sciences can enable transformative research in many disciplines. However, initiating such work can be difficult and needs partners and expertise that may be difficult to find. The Data Intensive Studies Center helps Tufts researchers overcome these barriers. Through this effort we seek to accelerate well defined X+Data Sciences efforts on campus that can target high impact research and in appropriate areas large sponsored research efforts e.g. NSF TRIPODS Phase II, NIH BIG Data to Knowledge, AI Institutes. DISC will supports such efforts with a seed grant of up to \$20,000 and access to data scientists, data sets and other expertise at DISC. Through these projects DISC engage faculty, staff and students in cross-disciplinary research.

SOCIAL

Email: disc@tufts.edu

Web: disc.tufts.edu

Tufts
UNIVERSITY

Data Intensive
Studies Center

PIONEERING RESEARCH

SURROGATE MODELING OF THE DROPLET PINCH-OFF VOLUME FOR GAS/LIQUID INTERFACE IN COMBUSTION CHAMBERS

A framework for combining and propagating data and model form uncertainties to estimate the distribution of fuel regression rate from hybrid rocket experiments (Georgalis, Patra (Tufts) with Desjardin group (UB))

Haensch et al. A Geospatial Bounded Confidence Model including Mega-Influencers with an Application to Covid-19 Vaccine Hesitancy, *Journal of Artificial Societies and Social Simulation* 26 (1) 8, 2023.

HALICIOĞLU DATA SCIENCE INSTITUTE

SUMMARY

Founded in 2018 as a fully independent academic unit, the mission of the Halicioğlu Data Science Institute (HDSI) is to establish the scientific foundations of data science, develop new methods and infrastructure, and train students and partners to use data science to solve the world's most pressing problems.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Cross-departmental institute and Department of Data Science

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- Ph.D. in Data Science
- M.S. in Data Science
- M.S. in Data Science (Online)
- B.S. in Data Science
- Undergraduate Minor in Data Science

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 44
- Professional Staff: 15
- Affiliated Members: 187
- Students:
 - Undergraduate: 1,450
 - 7,000+ in data science courses

LOCATION

10100 Hopkins Drive
La Jolla, CA 92093

TALENT PREPARATION IN DATA SCIENCE THROUGH EXPERIENTIAL LEARNING

HDSI's Data Science major preparation is designed to be transdisciplinary by providing a hub of instructional activities that draws faculty and researchers from different disciplines and departments. The training is heavily experiential and enriched with real-world applications by partnering with industry and community organizations that provide access to rich data sets and varied use cases of societal importance while also increasing community engagement and facilitating multiple career pathways.

Experiential learning starts in the first year with an Undergraduate Research Scholarship program and culminates in a senior capstone project designed to showcase mastery across the wide range of mathematical/statistical, technical, and conceptual skills developed throughout the curriculum. The capstone spans the entire data science life-cycle, including assessment of the problem, acquisition of domain knowledge, collection and cleaning of the data, system design, model creation and analysis, discussion of ethical implications, and presentation of results.

PARTNERING WITH THE SAN DIEGO SUPERCOMPUTER CENTER (SDSC) TO INCREASE UNDERSTANDING AND CAPACITY FOR SCALE AND COMPLEXITY

SDSC was founded in 1985 with a \$170 million grant from the NSF Supercomputer Centers program. From 1997 to 2004, SDSC extended its leadership in computational science and engineering to form the National Partnership for Advanced Computational Infrastructure (NPACI), teaming with approximately 40 university partners around the country.

From large-scale networking and high throughput computing expertise to internet research, SDSC is a leader in computing at scale. New initiatives are aimed at the intersection of services for management, analysis, and sharing data at the 10s of Petabytes level. This work supports multidisciplinary programs in academia, industry, and government that address a wide variety of grand challenges from astrophysics and earth sciences to disease research and drug discovery.

HDSI and SDSC are now developing a proposal to form a School of Computation, Information, and Data Science which will be perfectly suited for convergence research and translating data science innovations into practice for solving real problems of societal importance.

SOCIAL

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Web: datascience.ucsd.edu

X/Twitter: @HDSIUUCSD

LinkedIn: www.linkedin.com/school/hdsiucsd

Facebook: www.facebook.com/HDSIUUCSD

CATALYZING LARGE-SCALE INTEGRATIVE RESEARCH PROJECTS

HDSI provides intellectual and operational support that allow researchers drawn from various disciplines to work together in creating new research initiatives with potential for long-term impact. Among these efforts are the recently announced AI Institute, TILOS (The Institute for Learning Optimization at Scale), as well as DARPA efforts on Smart Radio platforms.

TILOS is a National Science Foundation funded National Artificial Intelligence (AI) Research Institute. The TILOS mission is to make impossible optimizations possible, at scale and in practice.

TILOS is a partnership of faculty from University of California, San Diego, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, National University, University of Pennsylvania, University of Texas at Austin, and Yale University. TILOS will pioneer learning-enabled optimizations that transform chip design, robotics, communication networks, and other use domains that are vital to our nation's health, prosperity and welfare. Foundational Research will pursue five main pillars.

Foundational Research will pursue five main pillars:

1. Bridging discrete and continuous optimization
2. Distributed, parallel, and federated optimization
3. Optimization on manifolds
4. Dynamic decisions under uncertainty
5. Non-convex optimization in deep learning

CREATING LEADERS IN DATA SCIENCE THROUGH GRADUATE STUDY

Three graduate programs join the Halicioğlu Data Science Institute's popular undergraduate Data Science programs for an integrated slate of courses and degree programs at all educational levels.

Master of Science: the MS program features courses in the foundational areas that prepare students from diverse backgrounds for a successful career in Data Science. A thesis option exists for students interested in cutting edge research.

Online Masters: the MDS program is designed for working professionals and combines concepts from statistics, computer science, and applications. The fully-online program is offered asynchronously in order to accommodate students with varying work schedules.

Doctor of Philosophy: the doctoral program aims to create leaders in the field of data science who will challenge and expand the boundaries of knowledge in the field. The doctoral program provides a research-oriented education spanning diverse data science areas, such as algorithms, machine learning, artificial intelligence, optimization, statistical methods, and data ethics.

HDSI continues to develop new innovative blended undergraduate-masters programs and joint graduate programs with other Departments, Schools, and Institutes.

THE UNIVERSITY OF CHICAGO

CENTER FOR TRANSLATIONAL DATA SCIENCE

SUMMARY

The Center for Translational Data Science at the University of Chicago is developing the discipline of translational data science and applying it to tackle challenging problems in biology, medicine, healthcare and the environment.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Cross-departmental center

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

The Translational Data Science Institute offers specializations in translational data science and its applications to biology, medicine, healthcare, and the environment.

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 3
- Professional Staff: 75+ research scientists and professional staff
- Affiliated Members: 6

LOCATION

University of Chicago
5454 South Shore Drive
Suite 2A/B
Chicago Illinois 60615

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

The Center for Translational Data Science has developed a number of important “firsts:” including, one of the first large scale data clouds (the NSF supported Open Science Data Cloud (2010-2016)); the first data cloud designed to host biomedical data and approved as a NIH Trusted Partner (the Bionimbus Protected Data Cloud (2013-present)); the first large scale data commons (the NCI Genomic Data Commons (2016-present)); and the first set of services to create data ecosystems for biomedical data (Data Commons Frameworks Services (2020-present)).

Today with our partners, we operate a data ecosystem comprising over a dozen data commons that make over 14 PB of data available to the research community on over 1,000,000 research participants. We provide access to this data via secure and compliant workspaces while protecting privacy.

The NCI Genomic Data Commons, which was developed by CTDS

SOCIAL

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Facebook: www.facebook.com/UChicagoCTDS

YouTube: @uchicagoctds4255

Academic
Data Science
Alliance

Looking for a **service opportunity?** Join an ADSA Working Group!

Serving as part of an ADSA Working Group is a great way to fulfill service requirements for promotion and tenure!

ADSA takes on projects in collaboration with our community members and member organizations. As the ADSA community grows, the diversity of the participants' interests and expertise is increasing at the same time as the ability to manage the work done within the community becomes more complex. ADSA prefers to focus our projects and collaborations around community-driven working groups - focused on developing products by and for academic data scientists.

Each project is developed and managed through working groups made up of community members interested in the topic area. Below you can find what ADSA working groups are active working groups, proposed working groups, and previously generated ADSA products, along with guidelines for how to start up a new ADSA working group to create a product for our community.

Learn More:

tinyurl.com/adsa-working-groups

THE UNIVERSITY OF CHICAGO

DATA SCIENCE INSTITUTE

SUMMARY

The Data Science Institute (DSI) executes the University of Chicago's bold, innovative vision of Data Science and AI. The DSI seeds research on the interdisciplinary frontiers of these emerging fields, forms partnerships with industry, government, and social impact organizations, and supports holistic data science education.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

University-wide Institute

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- PhD in Data Science
- Masters in Data Science
- Masters in Applied Data Science
- Masters of Business Administration and MS in Applied Data Science Joint Degree
- Undergraduate Major & Minor in Data Science

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 47
- Professional Staff: 35
- Affiliated Members: 42
- Students: 760+

LOCATION

Data Science Institute
John Crerar Library Building
5730 South Ellis Avenue, Suite
150 Chicago IL 60637

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

The DSI pursues a distinctive vision of the emerging and evolving field of data science and AI; one that addresses foundational problems across the data life cycle, including the technical, theoretical, ethical, and societal aspects of the collection, manipulation, and use of data and AI. The DSI seeds research on interdisciplinary frontiers of the field, forms partnerships outside of the walls of the university, and supports holistic data science education.

DSI launched three multi-year research initiatives this year: AI for Climate, Data Ecology, and Complementary AI. These initiatives facilitate connections among faculty across the university to solve frontier challenges in data science and AI.

We welcomed the first 7 PhD and 25 research MS students in Data Science. They join the thriving MS in Applied Data Science and undergraduate student community. The education programs are under the purview of The Committee on Data Science.

The Fifth Annual Rising Stars in Data Science Workshop hosted by DSI expanded this year to include the University of California San Diego and Stanford University as collaborating institutions.

AI+SCIENCE EXPANSION AND AWARDS

The AI+Science research initiative funds collaborative research in AI-enabled scientific discovery. Building on a foundation of more than \$20 million in external funding, the initiative expanded this year to include a new NSF-Simons Institute for the Sky (skAI), the Schmidt Faculty Fellowship, and the Pritzker Prize.

Led by Northwestern, the skAI institute will unite researchers from multiple disciplines to develop innovative, trustworthy AI tools for astronomy, which will be used to drive innovation in both fields.

The AI in Science Faculty Fellowship, a program of Schmidt Sciences at UChicago, will host junior faculty from Nigerian universities interested in advancing the adoption of AI in the natural sciences. This program is an extension of the Schmidt Postdoctoral Fellowship Program.

SOCIAL

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Web: datascience.uchicago.edu

LinkedIn: UChicago Data Science Institute

X: @DSI_UChicago

Bluesky: [dsi-uchicago.bsky.social](https://bsky.app/profile/dsi-uchicago.bsky.social)

YouTube: @UChicagoDSI

The Margot and Tom Pritzker Prize for AI in Science Research Excellence recognizes outstanding contributions that jointly advance AI and the natural sciences or engineering. The prize is based on the quality and impact of the research. The Pritzker Prize will include two \$50,000 annual awards.

NEW PHD CERTIFICATE PROGRAM

Coinciding with the launch of the Data Science PhD program, the DSI received a National Science Foundation Innovations of Graduate Education (IGE) grant to support a five year study of a new multi-disciplinary project titled "Transforming Graduate STEM Education: A Study of a Data Science and AI Credential for STEM Doctoral Students." This grant will

help establish a four-course credential that will enable STEM doctoral students to apply data science and AI to research in their fields. Students participating in the credential program will learn how to use data and AI accurately and responsibly, understand its broader impacts on social systems, make and critique data-backed arguments, and become fluent in the latest computation tools. This program will target doctoral students in STEM disciplines outside of data science including astrophysics, genetics, engineering, and neuroscience during their 2nd and 3rd year of study. The research activities will focus on the role that participation in the credential program plays in shifting disciplinary perspectives and graduate students' job search and career direction.

COMMUNITY-CENTERED DATA SCIENCE

Community-Centered Data Science (CCDS) is a core activity of the DSI. This effort is driven by long-term, mutually-beneficial partnerships with social impact and civic organizations. CCDS initiatives include the City Colleges of Chicago-UChicago Preceptor Program, Local Data Journalism Program, Data Science for Social Impact Summer Program, and Data4All high school bridge program.

The 11th Hour Project, part of The Schmidt Family Foundation, funds the Data Science for Social and Environmental Impact Initiative at DSI. The 11th Hour Project serves nonprofits in four main impact areas: energy, food and agriculture, human rights, and marine technology.

The DSI serves as the centralized hub for software and data science for their 300+ grantees across the globe. DSI research staff work to lower the barriers to mission-driven data science through student experiential learning projects, consultation, project-based applications and collaboration.

A new grant from Mastercard Center for Inclusive Growth is funding the exploration of a top-tier research convening for the Society of Impact Data Science and AI. This project will include representatives from universities, industry, and social impact organizations.

MIDAS

MICHIGAN INSTITUTE FOR DATA & AI IN SOCIETY

UNIVERSITY OF MICHIGAN

SUMMARY

MIDAS promotes advancements in data science and artificial intelligence, and enables their transformative use in a wide range of research disciplines to achieve lasting scientific and societal impact. Its faculty community includes 570 methodologists and domain scientists from all schools and colleges at the Ann Arbor campus, and Dearborn and Flint campuses.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Cross-departmental Institute

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

Graduate Data Science Certificate

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Professional Staff: 11
- Affiliated Members: 570
- Students: 80

LOCATION

500 Church Street, Suite 600
Ann Arbor, MI 48109-1042

RESPONSIBLE DATA SCIENCE AND AI

As data science and AI become a major force in science and in society, increasingly complex analytical pipelines working with poorly understood data and AI models pose significant issues of bias, inclusion and fairness, as well as the validity of research outcomes. MIDAS mobilizes researchers to promote responsible and reproducible data science and AI. Our focus areas include:

Responsible AI

In collaboration with campus organizations and Microsoft, MIDAS

supports research on the responsible use of AI, its societal impact, regulation and policy, and translating the output of such research into action. MIDAS also develops guidelines for the responsible use of AI, especially generative AI, in academic research.

Reproducible research

In the past five years, MIDAS has devoted major efforts to develop resources and training to improve the rigor and reproducibility of data- and AI-intensive research. We now lead an NIH-funded training program, in collaboration with two minority-serving institutions, for faculty and staff biomedical researchers across the country to improve the rigor and reproducibility of their research using data and AI and to help them develop their own training effort. "

BUILDING RESEARCH CAPACITY WITH AI

As much as AI promises to transform academic research, a major hurdle is that the pace of AI advancement far exceeds individual researchers' abilities to acquire skills to implement AI in their research. MIDAS offers a variety of training for researchers and cultivate the next generation of research leaders.

Faculty training

MIDAS offers weeklong summer academies to faculty and staff scientists with topics ranging from data science and AI methods introduction to advanced topics and their applications in domain sciences. In addition, MIDAS also offers a yearlong tutorial series on using generative AI for specific research tasks such as coding, data cleaning, data visualization and analysis, and scientific writing.

Postdoctoral training

MIDAS offers three two-year fellowship programs for postdoctoral researchers: the Eric and Wendy Schmidt AI in Science Postdoctoral Fellows program, the Eric and Wendy Schmidt AI in Science African Faculty Fellows program, and the Michigan Data Science Fellows program. These programs provide intensive training and research experience to outstanding researchers who are on their way to be the next generation of research leaders who can leverage AI to achieve research breakthroughs.

SOCIAL

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X: @um_midas

LinkedIn: Michigan Institute for Data and AI in Society

AI IN DOMAIN RESEARCH

MIDAS elevates AI to support existing research strengths and strategic research directions at the University of Michigan. In the past two years, MIDAS has collaborated with a large number of campus organizations and industry partners to showcase the power of AI in specific topics in physical sciences, biomedical sciences, earth and environmental sciences, social sciences and humanities, and engineering, such as Great Lakes research, biodiversity, sustainable transportation, medical imaging research, and challenging social conventions. In addition, MIDAS is invested in developing novel approaches to build institutional capacity to leverage AI for research, and leading strategic research initiatives to harness the power of AI. One example is the Center for Data-Driven Drug Discovery and Treatment Assessment. With a grant from the NSF Industry-University Cooperative Research Centers Program, MIDAS leads this center in collaboration with a dozen of industry partners. The Center focuses on developing ML methods for drug discovery and repurposing; enabling federated ML over encrypted databases; and providing an industry-wide and vendor-agnostic secure data hub for pharmaceutical and patient data.

CROSS-SECTOR COLLABORATION

Academia - industry collaboration

The traditional academic research model is facing significant challenges as resources and talent for AI are increasingly concentrated in industry. With funding support from NSF and Microsoft, MIDAS explores ways to build models of academia - industry collaboration to help academic research remain at the forefront of research and innovation and use science and technology to address societal challenges.

Collaboration with academic institutions

MIDAS has organized seminar series in collaboration with other leading research universities, including the "data science coast-to-coast" series and the "generative AI coast-to-coast" series. In addition, MIDAS organizes the Future Leaders Summit, an annual event to promote collaboration among data science institutes and to support the career development of future research leaders. Participants include PhD students and postdoctoral researchers ranging from major research institutions to minority-serving universities.

MIDAS also promotes **Data and AI for Social Good**. MIDAS researchers and students undertake projects to support data and AI strategies for government and community partners especially those serving marginalized communities, including the City of Detroit and Native American tribal nations.

DATA SCIENCE INITIATIVE

UNIVERSITY OF MINNESOTA

Driven to Discover®

SUMMARY

The University of Minnesota is a powerhouse in cutting edge data science research with many data science activities existing throughout our campuses. The UMN Data Science Initiative's primary focus is university-wide communication, coordination, integration, and amplification of those activities.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

University-wide Initiative

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Professional Staff: 3
- Affiliated Members: 30

LOCATION

Minneapolis, MN

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

Our mission is to unify and amplify data science activities across the University of Minnesota, fostering interdisciplinary research, world-class education, and public-private partnerships. We aim to prepare a diverse, data-literate workforce that pushes the boundaries of what's possible, lower barriers to public-private partnerships and multidisciplinary collaborations, and accelerate the translation of leading-edge research to practice. We strive to serve as a hub for collaboration and innovation in data science and AI.

The DSI provides resources for students and researchers to enhance their skills through training sessions, research showcases, and hands-on workshops. By connecting academics and industry experts, DSI ensures that its work remains relevant and impactful, addressing challenges across sectors like healthcare, agriculture, business, and education.

The DSI builds a cohesive community to tackle complex research challenges and create pathways for innovation through signature events such as the Women in AI & Data Science, Spring Research Workshop, and AI Makerspace Hours.

SOCIAL

Email: umn-dsi@umn.edu

Web: dsi.umn.edu

Instagram: @umndsi

LinkedIn: University of Minnesota Data Science Initiative

RAPID RESPONSE SEED GRANT

The Rapid Response seed grant opportunity to foster innovative research and collaboration in data science and AI. This initiative aims to catalyze projects that address emerging research needs.

DSI FACULTY FELLOWSHIPS

DSI Faculty Fellowships are intended to promote, catalyze, accelerate, and advance UMN-based collaborations in data science and AI research. Faculty with research in data science and AI in all disciplines are eligible for this fellowship. The DSI faculty fellows are expected to nurture and lead interdisciplinary teams to pursue large-scale proposals where DS/AI is central to their success.

DATA SET GRANT PROGRAM

The Data Set Grant program aims to foster research that creates or expands novel data sets, which are crucial for advancing innovative research in diverse fields. This initiative seeks to address the critical need for high-quality data by providing funding and support for projects that generate, enhance, and annotate data sets to fuel cutting-edge research at the UMN.

DATA SCIENCE INITIATIVE GRADUATE ASSISTANTSHIP

The Data Science Initiative Graduate Assistantship program supports UMN PhD candidates pursuing research in Data Science or AI. The program supports approximately ten 12-month research assistantships.

SUMMARY

Funded by a generous gift from Notre Dame alumnus Robert Lumpkins and his wife Sara, the institute is forging connections between intellectual capital, industry domain knowledge, and the leading edge of data science, defining intelligence that goes far beyond 1s and 0s.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

University-wide Institute

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- The Institute is currently designing a Master's degree in Data & Society
- Interdisciplinary Traineeship for Socially Responsible and Engaged Data Scientists (iTREDS)
- Specializations: Socially responsible data science, ethical data science

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 10
- Professional Staff: 19
- Affiliated Members: 189
- Students: 85 undergraduate students graduating from iTREDS program

LOCATION

610 Flanner Hall
Notre Dame, IN 46556

INSTITUTE OVERVIEW

The Lucy Family Institute's Interdisciplinary Traineeship for Socially Responsible and Engaged Data Scientists (iTREDS) program trains undergraduate students at the University of Notre Dame and Saint Mary's College in data science through a lens of social responsibility and community engagement, including rigor and responsibility, ethics, society, and policy.

The mission of the two-year iTREDS program is to educate the next generation of data scientists in a way that ensure ethics and social responsibility are intertwined with delivering data-driven solutions in the real world. Students are encouraged to produce impactful and equitable solutions while appreciating the ethical implications of data science innovation and results.

Through the 15-credit program, iTREDS scholars develop an in-depth data science background as well as communication, critical thinking, teamwork, and other skills necessary for professional development. The program also includes experiential learning opportunities, via a capstone project and summer internship, in which students learn how to effectively engage with stakeholders, understand their needs, assess societal impact, and incorporate utility and value.

MISSION AND VISION

Guided by Notre Dame's Mission, the Lucy Family Institute adventurously collaborates on advancing data-driven convergence research, translational solutions, and education to ethically address society's wicked problems. As an innovative nexus of academia, industry, and the public, the Institute also fosters data science access to strengthen diverse and inclusive capacity building within communities.

The Lucy Family Institute's vision is to become the preeminent intellectual beacon, inspiring collaborative, equitable, and impactful data innovations as a global force for good.

SOCIAL

Email: lucyinstitute@nd.edu

Web: lucyinstitute.nd.edu

X: [@lucy_institute](https://twitter.com/lucy_institute)

LinkedIn: [Lucy Family Institute for Data & Society](https://www.linkedin.com/company/lucy-family-institute-for-data-&-society)

INCUBATION HUB

Centered on the principles of co-inspiration, co-creation, and co-innovation, the Institute serves as an incubation hub that brings together University scholars, industry partners, community organizations, and global partners to innovate and promote ethical, equitable, and impactful use of data in society:

1. Hub for data, platforms for open data sharing;
2. Hub for convening research and education in data and society;
3. Hub for industry co-innovation, engagement, and collaboration;
4. Hub for tackling global challenges in data and society through translational data-driven research.

DATA SCIENCE EDUCATION FOR COMMON GOOD

The Institute's educational initiatives are aimed at preparing students, educators, and professionals to pivot into careers in data-driven fields, and the ethical, socially responsible, and engaged use of data. Programs offer training in data science and use experiential, project-based learning opportunities.

1. Interdisciplinary Traineeship for Socially Responsible and Engaged Data Scientists (iTREDS) for our undergraduate students;
2. Early Bridges to Data Science program for middle and high school students;
3. Summer Education and Engagement for Data Science (SEEDS) for high school students.

POWERFUL CONVERGENCE RESEARCH

The Institute aims to not only push the innovation frontier of fundamental research in data science and artificial intelligence but also spur new directions of interdisciplinary convergence research to inspire sustainable and ethical translation of these innovations:

1. Emerging technology for the future of work;
2. Fusion of data- and domain-driven research in engineering, social, physical, and life sciences;
3. Health and well-being of communities;
4. Socio-technical systems for sustainable societies, including responsible use of AI.

DATA INSTITUTE FOR SOCIETAL CHALLENGES

The UNIVERSITY of OKLAHOMA

SUMMARY

The Data Institute for Societal Challenges (DISC) is creating innovations in data science, artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning (ML), and data-enabled research. DISC fosters the growth of interdisciplinary research teams committed to solving local to global scale challenges.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

We are a cross cutting institute under the Vice President for Research and Partnerships

DEGREE PROGRAMS

OU offers a variety of undergraduate and graduate majors, minors, and certificates in data science and other related fields.

SPECIALIZATIONS

- Data Science Applications
- Human-Guided Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning
 - Human-Computer Teaming
 - Predictive Analytics
 - Decision-Making Environments and Visual Analytics
 - Scalable Software and Hardware Architectures

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Directory Members: 565
- Affiliated Members: 380

LOCATION

5 Partners Place
201 Stephenson Pkwy
Ste 4600
Norman, OK 73019

DISC'S ROLE AT THE UNIVERSITY OF OKLAHOMA

The Data Institute for Societal Challenges (DISC) at the University of Oklahoma (OU) serves as a dynamic hub for innovation and impact, launched in 2020 as a cornerstone of OU's strategic plan. DISC embodies a vision of harnessing the power of data and technology to improve lives and address pressing societal challenges. With a mission to drive transformative, data-driven solutions, the institute fosters collaboration across disciplines, uniting researchers, educators, and practitioners to tackle complex issues in health, energy, national security, and climate modeling. DISC is built on core values of innovation, inclusivity, and excellence. It prioritizes fostering diverse partnerships and creating opportunities for communities to benefit from cutting-edge research. These values guide its efforts to ensure that advancements in artificial intelligence, machine learning, and big data translate into actionable outcomes with tangible benefits. Since its inception, DISC has catalyzed 212 research proposals valued at \$173.96 million, securing \$53.78 million in funding for 81 projects. These achievements demonstrate the institute's unwavering dedication to advancing knowledge, empowering communities, and addressing critical societal needs. By combining a visionary approach with its foundational principles, DISC is shaping a future where data and technology are leveraged for the greater good.

SOCIAL

Email: disc@ou.edu
Web: ou.edu/disc
Facebook: @DISCatOU

FOSTERING COLLABORATION AND INNOVATION IN DATA SCIENCE

Collaboration is at the heart of DISC's mission. The institute partners with external organizations, such as the Stephenson Cancer Center and Tinker Air Force Base, while also fostering a vibrant data science community of 565 affiliates and 380 members. DISC's fifteen Communities of Practice (CoPs) provide platforms for researchers to collaborate and innovate in diverse fields like bioinformatics, earth science, and supply chain optimization, driving forward groundbreaking ideas that tackle significant societal challenges.

DRIVING GLOBAL IMPACT

DISC's impact extends beyond research, with seed funding programs awarding over \$749,566 to 93 research teams and partnerships with international institutions like KAIST and UNIST. As DISC continues to grow, it plays a pivotal role in positioning OU as a leader in data science and AI, driving positive change locally and globally through data-driven solutions and interdisciplinary collaboration.

SUMMARY

The eScience Institute was founded in 2008 with the mission to empower researchers and students in all fields to answer fundamental questions through the use of large, complex, and noisy data. From inception, the eScience Institute has functioned beyond departmental and college walls to exemplify the interdisciplinary breadth and complex dimensions of data science. Today, the Institute has grown to a mature organization with sustained positive impact through our education, research, and community building programs.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Cross-departmental Institute

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- 23 Departments with Graduate Data Science Specializations
- Masters in Data Science
- 7 Departments with Undergraduate Data Science Specializations
- Data Science Minor

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 14
- Professional Staff: 30
- Affiliated Members: 190

LOCATION

Physics/Astronomy Tower (PAT)
6th Floor
3910 15th Ave NE
Seattle, WA 98195-1570

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

The University of Washington eScience Institute, one of the nation's first university data science institutes, grew out of the Moore-Sloan Data Science Environment effort which focused on identifying and tackling impediments to the broad and sustainable adoption of data-intensive discovery. From inception, the eScience Institute has functioned beyond departmental and college walls to exemplify the interdisciplinary breadth and complex dimensions of data science. Today, the Institute has grown to a mature organization with sustained positive impact on the UW community through our education, research, and community building programs. Key eScience personnel now hold leadership roles in the construction, commissioning and operations of federally-funded research initiatives such as Pangeo, the Rubin Observatory, and Interactive Oceans, as well as NSF-funded programs including CloudBank and the West Big Data Innovation Hub.

INSTITUTIONAL SCOPE, STRUCTURE, & ACTIVITIES

The institute comprises a community of innovators in the development and application of the techniques, technologies, and best practices of data science. The eScience conception of data science has always considered the full data science workflow, from project conception to data-driven discovery, and every step in between. With expertise in advanced statistical and computational techniques including artificial intelligence, machine learning, database management, visualization, and research software engineering, we have energized the WRF Data Science Studio into a nexus of data science activity on campus and virtually. We serve campus data science and software engineering needs and propel research forward via multiple channels, from open office hours to quarter-long engagements like the Incubator and Data Science for Social Good programs, to multi-year collaborative grants and centers. Our faculty, postdoctoral fellows, and graduate students are engaging in cutting-edge research pushing the methodology envelope and making new discoveries across a diversity of fields.

SOCIAL

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Web: escience.washington.edu

X: @uwescience

LinkedIn: UW eScience Institute

YouTube: @UWeScienceInstitute

DATA SCIENCE INCUBATORS

The Data Science Incubator enables new science by bringing together data scientists and domain scientists to work on focused, collaborative projects. Each fall, we invite proposals for a quarter-long data-intensive research collaboration focusing on extracting insight from large, noisy, and/or heterogeneous datasets. Over the past 10 years, we have supported 66 projects with collaborators from 28 different departments. Previous incubator projects have led to long-term collaborations, publications, and grant awards.

Launched in 2015, the UW's Data Science for Social Good (DSSG) summer program partners Student Fellows with Data Scientists from the eScience Institute and Project Leads from academia, government, and the private sector, to find data-intensive solutions to pressing societal challenges. Previous projects have used diverse methods to address topics such as public health, homelessness, disaster response, voting rights and transportation. keystones of the DSSG program include project-based discussions and training around data science ethics, human-centered design and stakeholder collaboration.

HACKWEEKS

The hackweek model has emerged within the data science community as a powerful tool for fostering the exchange of ideas in research and computation. In contrast to conventional conferences or workshops, hackweeks are intensive and interactive, facilitated by 3 core components: tutorials on state-of-the-art methodology, peer-learning, and on-site project work in a collaborative environment. This setup is particularly powerful for sciences that require not only domain-specific knowledge, but also effective computational tools and methodologies. The eScience Institute has extensive experience developing and facilitating hackweeks focused in particular domains, e.g. Neurohackademy and the Electrochemical Society HackWeek, as well as around particular datasets, e.g. the ICESat-2 and SnowEx Hackweeks.

RESEARCH SOFTWARE ENGINEERING

The Scientific Software Engineering Center (SSEC) at UW provides researchers with access to full-time professional engineers and state of the art technology to develop high quality, maintainable, and sustainable software. SSEC is staffed with a highly diverse team of software engineers who partner on impactful projects funded by NSF, NIH, DOE, and beyond, infusing them with the software industry's best practices.

SUMMARY

Data science at UWM is built on an inclusive vision. We believe you can apply this work and these skills to all facets of life, be it art, business, health, weather or countless other areas.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Cross-departmental Institute

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- MS in Data Science
- BS in Data Science
- BA in Data Analytics

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Number of affiliated members: 45
- Number of students enrolled: 60

SOCIAL

Email:
datascience-degrees@uwm.edu

Web:
uwm.edu/data-science

LOCATION

3203 N Downer Ave #261
Milwaukee, WI 53211

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

Data science at UWM is built on an inclusive vision. We believe you can apply this work and these skills to all facets of life, be it art, business, health, weather or countless other areas. That's why our data science programs build an appreciation of these broad applications rather than concentrating solely on methods and techniques. The same vision guides how we approach research in data science.

THE NORTHWESTERN MUTUAL DATA SCIENCE INSTITUTE (NMDSI)

The NMDSI is a groundbreaking partnership between Northwestern Mutual, Marquette University and the University of Wisconsin–Milwaukee that contributes to the technology ecosystem and advances southeastern Wisconsin as a national hub for technology, research, business and talent development, while creating an organic pipeline of tech talent in the area.

Our vision is to be a world-class institute that transforms our world through the power of data science. We inspire and cultivate a passion for data science, galvanizing the brightest minds in the Milwaukee region to solve some of the world's most pressing problems and inspire the next generation of data scientists.

Support ADSA's work...

Academic
Data Science
Alliance

Become a Member!

ADSA is a professional association for data science in academia that is not a sub-group of computer science or statistics. We believe data science should be for, and by, everyone. ADSA membership is open to data science initiatives, departments, centers or full institutions and consortia. Membership signals support for **our mission, vision, and values** and supports our team in developing events and resources that benefit the entire data science community. When your school or organization joins ADSA as a Member, everyone can benefit!

ADSA's current member institutions include:

- 50 R1
- 6 R2
- 5 international
- 4 Ivy League
- 17 minority-serving institutions
- 2 two-year colleges

WHY BECOME A MEMBER OF ADSA?

- **Join a community of peers** with your values who face common challenges.
- Access a network of institutions for **student, postdoc, and faculty recruiting**.
- Take advantage of **career development opportunities**.
- Increase the **visibility** of your school and programs.
- Early access to **new resources**.
- Special access to ADSA staff for **consultations and support**.
- Join or propose a new working group to **build resources for the community**.

FY 2024-2025 Memberships

50% off for
2-yr colleges
and MSIs!

ANNUAL DUES:

- **Investor: \$10,000**
 - *Appropriate for:* Large initiatives, multi-university consortia, or well-funded units wishing to signal their support for ADSA and pay forward benefits to other schools.
- **Tier 1: \$5,000**
 - *Appropriate for:* Medium-large units (departments, schools), multi-department programs, or university-wide institutes and centers.
- **Tier 2: \$2,500**
 - *Appropriate for:* Small departments or schools.
- **Evergreen Member:** Commit to 5 years of membership for the price of 4.

Note: Annual membership follows a typical academic fiscal year (July 1 - June 30).

Ready to join?

Learn more at:
tinyurl.com/ADSA-membership

VANDERBILT UNIVERSITY

Data Science Institute

SUMMARY

The Vanderbilt Data Science Institute accelerates data-driven research, promotes collaboration, and trains future leaders. The institute brings together experts in AI and data science with leaders in all academic fields to spark discoveries. The DSI has been using, developing, and training generative AI models since 2019, and our Masters students use the latest technologies in their classes and projects.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Cross-departmental Institute

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- Master of Science in Data Science
- Undergraduate Minor in Data Science

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Number of faculty: 14
- Professional staff: 6
- Affiliated faculty: 224
- Number of students: 82

SOCIAL

Email:
datascience@vanderbilt.edu

Web:
vanderbilt.edu/datascience

X/Twitter: @VUDataScience

LinkedIn: Data Science Institute at Vanderbilt University

Facebook:
@vanderbiltdatascience

Instagram: @vudatascience

LOCATION

1400 18th Ave S
Nashville, TN 37212

DATA SCIENCE EDUCATION

M.S. in Data Science

Our two-year data science degree boasts a customized data science-specific curriculum taught by an interdisciplinary faculty from Medicine, Engineering, Arts and Sciences, Education, and Business. Our program is 46% female and we are committed to enabling gender equality in data science. The Owen Graduate School of Management's highly-ranked Career Management Center supports our students' career goals. Our program is rigorous, practical, experiential, team-oriented, and student-focused.

Our Data Science Team attracts a continual flow of real-world projects for students to participate in both in and out of the classroom. Watch a promo video: <https://bit.ly/vanderbilt-data-science>

Data Science Minor

Vanderbilt's trans-institutional data science (DS) minor provides students of all disciplines an accessible and well-rounded foundation in DS, providing context and experience with the tools of our increasingly data-driven society.

This 19-credit hour interdisciplinary program covers foundational DS skills, from programming to statistics, interweaving ethical considerations of data use and interpretation. With experiential learning opportunities, the minor provides a solid foundation for future professions or graduate study in any field that uses data.

PROFESSIONAL DATA SCIENCE EXPERIENCE

The Data Science Institute at Vanderbilt is actively engaged in data science projects and students are an integral part of those teams. As one of its core groups, the DSI has a professional data science team that engages with researchers, industry, and not-for-profits in a dozen or more projects annually. Each is run using agile processes and best practices. By building teams of staff data scientists, Masters students and undergraduates, the DSI is able to both support the development of cutting-edge tools and approaches, provide real-world experience, and give students experience in fully participating as a team member in a high-functioning data science team.

This emphasis on real-world experience and best practices of team data science is woven in throughout the curriculum. The Data Science in Practice class is now in its third year of teaching students that "Data Science is a Team Sport" with industry best practices using real-world corporate projects. Project classes allow for a focused semester-long team engagement while also introducing new tools.

“
The program's blend of computational skills and statistics opened my eyes to what's possible in data science. I came in with a math background, but now I can confidently tackle complex data projects and clearly present my findings to any audience.

TESSORA STEFAN
M.S.D.S, Class of 2025

INTERDISCIPLINARY WORK

At the DSI, we engage in projects across the academic and industry spectrum. From archaeology to medicine to literature, students have the opportunity to participate in new and ongoing collaborations, or to explore their own. Every Friday the DSI hosts AI Fridays, where researchers drop by for a Deep Dive, hour-long in-depth conversation with data scientists and faculty on a topic of interest. Recent deep dives have included using transformers to study special education classroom interactions to the application of AI in design and engineering problems in industry.

Students have multiple opportunities to explore applications of data science. Our Masters students complete a self-directed Capstone project which is often in partnership with faculty in various disciplines or industry partners. In our Data Science for Social Good Programs, students have an opportunity to make a substantial contribution by applying data science skills, while gaining the opportunity to solve problems across a broad range of areas. Undergraduates can participate in the DSI Summer Research Program to pursue data science-related research with a faculty sponsor.

INDUSTRY PARTNERSHIPS

The DSI is actively engaged with industry through consulting, collaborative data science projects, course-based projects, and capstones. Through its Data Science Team, the DSI provides consults on data science and AI solutions to industry ranging from new startups to multinational corporations. Partners include AllianceBernstein, AWS, Bridgestone, Asurion, The General Insurance, and others.

Students have an opportunity to participate in projects with direct impact on businesses by joining data science teams that tackle scoped projects with our partners. They apply what they've learned in classes while developing new skills that can only be developed working on a team in a business environment. By graduation, students have had the opportunity to work with multiple companies in a real-world team environment, and are ready to step into data roles and immediately contribute.

The Data Science Collaboratory

At Colgate University

SUMMARY

Our goal is to develop a vibrant research community among faculty and students. We aim to provide statistical guidance and resources to researchers across fields increasingly reliant on data science.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

The Data Science Collaboratory is a distributed collaborative of faculty, staff, and students across Colgate University and New York 6 colleges and universities.

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 3
- Professional Staff: 2
- Affiliated Members: 12
- Students: 2

SOCIAL

Email: datascience@colgate.edu

Web: shiny.colgate.edu

X/Twitter: @DataSciCollab

Bluesky:

[@datascicollab.bsky.social](https://bsky.app/profile/datascicollab.bsky.social)

LOCATION

Case Library and Geyer Center for Information Technology
13 Oak Drive
Hamilton, NY 13346

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

The Data Science Collaboratory at Colgate University (the Collaboratory) was established in 2018 to address the gap in statistical research support, with grant funding from the Central New York Library Resources Council New Initiatives Grant. Our main objective is to develop a collection of easy-to-use apps that enhance the teaching and learning of statistics while making it more accessible and engaging for students. We will share our experience and framework for building a multi-institutional Collaboratory in a way that enables smaller colleges and universities to develop their own collaboratories. More broadly, we aim to impact how students and instructor-scholars inculcate data literacy in the classroom and student research by providing easy-to-use statistics tools.

Summer Research Opportunities: Student-initiated fellowships envision research or creative projects supervised by faculty members but proposed by students.

Upcoming Programs: H. G. Wells anticipated that statistical thinking would one day be as necessary for efficient citizenship as the ability to read and write. In 1989, Moore and Roberts argued that the day had come. If it hadn't then, it surely has now. Colgate University is currently developing two new data-science-related programs to help guide students to critically assess and interpret data, allowing them to navigate the increasingly data-driven world and become informed citizens.

Upcoming Statistics Major Program: The field of statistics is continually growing with the ongoing development of novel methodologies and techniques for discovering, manipulating, and analyzing digital information. Introducing a Statistics major program at the university will enable students to contribute and participate in research initiatives, collaborate with professors, and contribute to cutting-edge research by providing quantitative research support.

Upcoming Data Studies Program: The liberal arts education emphasizes general and powerful intellectual methods, is naturally interdisciplinary, and promotes good citizenship through imparting a broad worldview. Data Science, in this sense, deserves a prominent position in the liberal arts. Gathering, organizing, and analyzing data to illuminate the sometimes murky underlying reality is a collection of powerful intellectual methods that can be applied to various contexts. Further, liberal arts students are among those who are most likely to succeed in fully considering the sometimes unintended ethical and societal impacts of their experimental and data collection designs.

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

Elon offers a variety of data focused curricula, including business analytics, data analytics, data science and media analytics. Data Nexus is Elon's data hub. It oversees the institution's Quality Enhancement Plan (QEP) in Data Competency, which highlights the university's continued vision as a leader in undergraduate teaching and students' abilities to be responsible, ethical and informed consumers and producers of data.

The Data Competency QEP focuses on student learning related to foundational data literacies, foundational statistical competencies and advanced data competencies. To advance a data-centric Elon, Data Nexus is supporting faculty in the creation or redesign and promotion of data-designated courses, course sections and academic co-curricular experiences across various disciplinary and interdisciplinary contexts. Since its inception in fall 2023, Data Nexus has approved more than 30 data intensive designed courses and has developed several interdisciplinary micro credentials.

SUMMARY

Data Nexus, Elon University's Data Hub, oversees Elon's Quality Enhancement Plan in Data Competency which highlights Elon's continued vision as a leader in undergraduate education and student success and builds on Elon's ongoing efforts to bolster students' abilities to be responsible, ethical, and informed consumers and producers of data.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

University-wide Initiative

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

Elon University offers a variety of data focused curricula, including Business Analytics, Data Analytics, Data Science, and Media Analytics.

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Students: 6,791 undergraduates

SOCIAL

Email: datanexus@elon.edu
Web: elon.edu/u/academics/data-nexus
X: @DataNexusElon
Instagram: @DataNexusElon

LOCATION

100 Campus Dr.
Elon, NC 27244

FSU

SUMMARY

FSU's Graduate Certificate in Digital Applied Social Science teaches students how to apply ethical frameworks to the collection, processing, analysis, and visualization of digital data. Students gain hands-on experience with innovative computational tools such as network analysis, natural language processing, social simulations, and generative AI.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Different degrees/certificates housed across the university

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- Interdisciplinary Data Science Master's Degree Program
- Certificate in Digital Applied Social Sciences

SOCIAL

Email:
deana.rohlinger@fsu.edu

Web:
cospp.fsu.edu/iss/graduate-certificate-in-digital-applied-social-sciences

LOCATION

College of Social Sciences and Public Policy
113 Collegiate Loop
Tallahassee, Florida 32306-2160

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

Digital Applied Social Science (DASS) is a new certificate that draws on existing expertise in Social Sciences, Communication, and the Information School. We are accepting applications now for the 2025-2026 academic year. The College of Social Sciences and Public Policy is building out a Data for Social Good Initiative, which include an inaugural Design Sprint focusing on relocating Florida residents during hurricanes. The College partnered with the Florida Division of Emergency Management, a D.C. based AI company, faculty from the Emergency Management and Homeland Security program, and FSU's Innovation hub.

Details about the event can be found here:

<https://www.innovation.fsu.edu/rapid-relocation>

HDSI | Harvard Data Science Initiative

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

The Harvard Data Science Initiative (HDSI) represents Harvard's commitment to shaping the new science of data. The HDSI facilitates university-wide engagement to connect people of diverse disciplines across all Harvard schools, to understand the many dimensions of data science, and to propel it forward.

The HDSI works to illuminate the new interdisciplinary pathways that our faculty, students, and partners will use to solve real problems, in a world with critical ethical challenges regarding facts, data, and truth.

Francesca Dominici
Founding Faculty Director, HDSI
Clarence James Gamble Professor of Biostatistics, Population, and Data Science, Harvard T.H. Chan School of Public Health

Stratos Idreos
Faculty Co-Director, HDSI
Gordon McKay Professor of Computer Science, Harvard John A. Paulson School of Engineering & Applied Sciences.

SUMMARY

The Harvard Data Science Initiative (HDSI) was launched in 2017 and has united leading computer scientists, statisticians, and domain experts from law, business, public policy, education, medicine, public health, and myriad academic disciplines to derive meaningful and actionable insights that will shape the world for generations to come.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Cross-departmental Initiative

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 1
- Professional Staff: 10
- Affiliated Members: 130

SOCIAL

Email: datascience@harvard.edu
Web: datascience.harvard.edu
LinkedIn: Harvard Data Science Initiative
Facebook: Harvard Data Science Initiative
Instagram: @thehdsi
YouTube: @harvarddatascienceinitiati3320

LOCATION

Allston, MA

SUMMARY

The Center for Applied Data Science and Analytics (CADSA) coordinates and facilitates interdisciplinary programs in data science; collaborates with other institutes and centers internal and external to Howard University; and expands research and educational linkages that will include internship and placement programs with sponsoring corporations and government agencies.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Cross-departmental Center

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

Masters Degree in Applied
Data Science and Analytics

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 13
- Affiliated Members: 23

SOCIAL

Email: datascience@howard.edu

Web: datascience.howard.edu

LinkedIn: [Howard University Center for Applied Data Science and Analytics](#)

LOCATION

2400 Sixth Street NW
Washington, DC

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

CADSA provides the HU investigator community with the resources needed to develop data-driven insights into research trend directions and how the HU research effort can position itself to both benefit from and influence the developing trend directions. In summary, the CADSA is an HU institutional tool of inquiry that produces new information that can then be used to address important human problems. As a result, the research philosophy of the CADSA will be to inquire, to inform, and to intervene. CADSA will implement this three-fold research philosophy as described below.

INQUIRE

The process of inquiry will involve the probing analysis of new and/or existing data to generate new information. The ultimate outcome of inquiry will be the conversion of data into useful information, the 'inquire' process will be driven by posing pertinent research questions that will provide meaning and understanding to available data from existing sources or emanating from the pursuit of original research.

INFORM

Data that is understood or appreciated in the proper context is viewed as information. Communication with peers, funders, and the public is an important aspect of competitive research, especially research that is focused on problem resolution. The research arm of CADSA will be very active in communicating new information to all relevant stakeholder communities. This is critical to ensure discipline-based and community-based consensus regarding newly generated information and its potential use or applicability for problem resolution.

INTERVENE

Knowledge may be viewed as categorized or organized information. As a result, when new information is considered in the context of relevant categorized/organized existing information, it contributes to the expansion of the knowledge pool and expands the problem-solving potential of the information collective. Problem-solving occurs when relevant knowledge is applied to address a current applicable problem. For problem-solving to occur, knowledge intervention into the current status of problems must occur.

RESEARCH STRATEGY SUMMARY

Knowledge may be viewed as categorized or organized information. As a result, when new information is considered in the context of relevant categorized/organized existing information, it contributes to the expansion of the knowledge pool and expands the problem-solving potential of the information collective. Problem-solving occurs when relevant knowledge is applied to address a current applicable problem. For problem-solving to occur, knowledge intervention into the current status of problems must occur. It should be noted that this research approach is applicable to each of the umbrella research areas of CADSA. Moreover, these umbrella research topics hold the potential to engage interdisciplinary approaches to solving critical challenges to the African American community and the African diaspora.

JAMES MADISON UNIVERSITY®

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

The data science program at JMU is in its infancy but the intended goal is to focus on networks and climate science. To this end, the College of Science & Mathematics is building an Environmental Data Science cohort housed in several departments. The Mathematics & Statistics department is also building specific degree programs in data science.

DATA ANALYTICS MINOR

The minor in data analytics is designed for students majoring in a STEM field who want to gain additional technical competencies in statistical data analytic methods as it relates to their field of study. This minor will provide students with analytical and technical skills in the ethical use of data in research environments, application of statistical and probabilistic thinking to data analysis, data visualization and data management, and application of machine learning techniques to their own field of study.

SUMMARY

James Madison University has data science or data analytics incorporated in various forms in many departments. Starting Fall 2023 the Mathematics & Statistics department was tasked with building degree and other credentialed programs in data science at JMU.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

JMU's Data Science Program is housed within the Dept. of Mathematics & Statistics

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- Data Science concentration to the Statistics major
- Data Analytics minor
- Computational Analytics minor

SOCIAL

Email: mathstat@jmu.edu

Web: jmu.edu/mathstat

X: @JMU

Facebook:

[@JamesMadisonUniversity](https://www.facebook.com/JamesMadisonUniversity)

Instagram:

[@jamesmadisonuniversity](https://www.instagram.com/jamesmadisonuniversity)

YouTube: [DukeDogTV](https://www.youtube.com/DukeDogTV)

LOCATION

Roop Hall, MSC 1911
60 Bluestone Drive
Harrisonburg, Virginia 22807

SUMMARY

I-DISC is a hub to catalyze, incubate & support collaborative multi-disciplinary research in areas related to data, intelligent systems & computing; building upon Lehigh's foundational research expertise in machine learning, AI, optimization, data-driven decision making, high-performance & data-intensive computing, signal processing, data representation, modeling & simulation, robotics, computer vision, business & management technology, privacy & security.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Cross-departmental Center

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- M.S. in Data Science
- M.S. in Business Analytics
- Undergraduate Minor in Data Science
- Certificates:
 - Business Analytics, Data Science & Financial Analytics, Data Analytics, and Data Science

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 3
- Professional Staff: 1
- Affiliated Members:
 - Faculty: 119
 - External Advisory Board members: 9

SOCIAL

Email: idisc@lehigh.edu
Web: idisc.lehigh.edu
X: @LehighDISC
LinkedIn: I-DISC

LOCATION

Building C, Lehigh University
 Mountaintop Campus
 113 Research Drive
 Bethlehem, PA 18015

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

I-DISC is a hub to catalyze, incubate and support collaborative multi-disciplinary research in areas related to data, intelligent systems and computing building upon Lehigh's foundational research expertise in machine learning, artificial intelligence, optimization, data-driven decision making, high-performance & data-intensive computing, signal processing, data representation, modeling & simulation, robotics & computer vision, business & management technology, and privacy & security.

I-DISC is a research institute and does not offer courses or educational programs. However, I-DISC leadership and faculty members are closely involved in relevant programs, including Lehigh's interdisciplinary Master's degree program in Data Science from the Rossin College of Engineering and Applied Sciences. This program has been designed especially for students without a data science background and offers flexibility in timing (as short as one year) and remote as well as in-person options.

At the graduate level:

<https://www2.lehigh.edu/academics/graduate-studies/degree-programs>

- MS in Data Science
- MS in Business Analytics
- Graduate certificate in Data Science & Financial Analytics
- Data Science certificate

At the undergraduate level:

<https://www2.lehigh.edu/academics/majors>

- Minor in Data Science
- Undergraduate certificate in Business Analytics

IDISC.LEHIGH.EDU/RESEARCH

- Mathematical Optimization & Data Science
- Human Centered Computing
- Scalable Systems & Software
- Explainable Graph Learning
- Catastrophe Modeling
- FinTech & Blockchain
- Quantum Computing & Optimization Lab
- Computer Vision
- Machine Learning in Materials Science
- Autonomy & Intelligent Robotics Lab
- Mountaintop Campus Lehigh University

College of Basic and Applied Sciences

MIDDLE TENNESSEE STATE UNIVERSITY

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

The Data Science Bachelor's Degree at MTSU was announced in February of 2020. Even with the challenges of going remote, the program has exceeded enrollment expectations and has a vibrant community of students. This degree program combines classes from several different departments in two different colleges to give students the skills to use data to solve problems. Students gain a core set of knowledge and then choose one of the three cognates to specialize in: Machine Learning, Business Intelligence and Analytics, and Inferential Thinking. There is also enough flexibility in the program that students can complete a minor in a field of interest to them. At the end of the program, students take a capstone course that combines all the knowledge they have gained into one project.

FOSTERING INCLUSIVE EXCELLENCE

MTSU started offering a graduate certificate in Data Science in 2020, and the Master's Degree in Data Science started in Fall 2022.

The graduate certificate is an online program consisting of four courses with "Data Dive" events at the end of each course. During the Data Dives, students work in groups at an all-day event to use the course knowledge to analyze a data set.

The Master of Science in Data Science Program brings computer science, applied mathematics, and statistics together to prepare its graduates for seeking careers in data science or pursuing PhD in relevant areas. The curriculum contains a blend of theory and practice of computer science and applied mathematics in order to draw insights and to extract information from large data.

SUMMARY

Middle Tennessee State University offers Data Science degrees at all levels (BS, MS, and PhD) that emphasize the interdisciplinary nature of Data Science. MTSU also contains the Data Science Institute, which is an applied research focused entity that strives to help its partners solve complex problems.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Our interdisciplinary academic programs at all three levels are housed in the College of Basic and Applied Sciences; the Data Science Institute does research and outreach.

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- BS in Data Science
- Minor in Data Science
- MS in Data Science
- Graduate Certificate in Data Science
- Ph.D. in Computational and Data Science

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 4
- Affiliated Members: 23
- Students (Fall '24):
 - 114 BS
 - 45 Minor
 - 7 Grad. Certificate
 - 63 MS
 - 37 Ph.D.

SOCIAL

Email: datascience@mtsu.edu

Web: mtsu.edu/datascience

X: @mtsudatascience

LinkedIn: MTSU Data Science

Facebook: MTSU Data Science

LOCATION

1301 E Main St
Murfreesboro, TN 37132

DATA SCIENCE ACADEMIC INSTITUTE

SUMMARY

The Data Science Academic Institute at MSU prepares students to meet the growing demand for data science expertise in the context of ongoing digital transformation and artificial intelligence. The institute fosters data science teaching and research within the university under the governance of an intercollege faculty committee.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Cross-departmental Program

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- Minor in Data Science
- Bachelor of Science in Data Science
- Master of Science in Data Science
- Master of Applied Data Science
- Graduate Certificate in Data Science Pedagogy
- Specializations in Business, Computing, Agriculture, Sports Science and more

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 5
- Professional Staff: 1
- Affiliated Members: 148
- Students: 59 undergraduate, 55 graduate

SOCIAL

Email: info@datascience.msstate.edu

Web: datascience.msstate.edu

X: @MsStateDataSci

LinkedIn: Data Science @ Mississippi State University

Instagram: @msstatedatascience

Facebook: @MSStateDataScience

LOCATION

133 Etheredge Hall
Mississippi State, MS 39762

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

The Data Science Academic Institute (DSAI) at MSU innovates in three key ways: its governance model, approach to the field of data science, and delivery of curriculum.

Governance Model

DSAI grows by strengthening the departments that make up the core curriculum, including business information systems, computer science and engineering, mathematics and statistics, and communications. Program quality and innovation is ensured by an intercollege faculty committee composed of representatives from every college.

Definition of Data Science

DSAI approaches data science as the field that advances methods to improve the use of data for human progress. Specifically, these methods allow humans to: represent the world with virtual data objects through a process of datafication; extract insights and facilitate new discoveries about the world by studying these data objects; create artificially intelligent systems that align harmoniously with human intelligence to perform tasks; and increase the performance (scale, scope, and speed) of organizations as they produce or deliver virtual and tangible goods and services.

This definition of data science places the data lifecycle within a contextual framework (see diagram) that emphasizes the role of scientific innovation (A.I. and Computing), people (workforce education and data science literacy), governance (ownership, privacy and confidentiality, and policy), infrastructure (hardware, software, network, storage, and security), ethics (the avoidance of algorithmic bias and a cultural mindset to use data to promote human flourishing), and the strategic goals that guide organizations in specific domains.

Delivery of Curriculum

The undergraduate program produces experts able to apply data science within one of several concentrations. This requires three general areas of coursework: general education (30 hours) to develop critical thinking and writing skills; a program core (63 hours) of computer science, statistics, mathematics, business information systems, communications, and data science courses; and applications of the data science program core in a specific concentration (30 hours). Students engage in a series of five hands-on data science labs including Data Wrangling; Statistical Inference; Data Visualization; Artificial Intelligence; and Cloud, Quantum, and High-Performance Computing. Students also complete a two-semester senior capstone project.

Math, Statistics, and Data Science Department

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

Montgomery College (MC) is a two-year college located outside of Washington, DC. It was ranked by Chronicle of Higher Ed (2018) as the Most Diverse Two-Year College in the continental US and serves approximately 43,000 total students across three campuses. We offer both an AS in Data Science (60 credits) as well as a certificate for working professionals who wish to upskill. For the data science certificate, students must complete five courses (16 credits). All materials for these courses are free and open-sourced for the students. Data tools used include R Studio, Python, Tableau, Github, and SQL. Students completing the associate's degree in data science will take all core courses from the certificate in addition to: Calculus I, Applications in Linear Algebra, Intro to the Study of Ethics, GIS courses, computer science courses, and general education courses. Through partnerships with Washington, DC area agencies and organizations, our students are able to acquire valuable real-world experience in order to facilitate either entry into the workforce or transfer to four-year degree opportunities.

THE CAPSTONE EXPERIENCE

Due to our proximity to Washington DC, our location allows us to partner with many local government and business organizations to provide students with rich capstone experiences. Organizations we have worked with include Walter Reed National Military Medical Center, The National Institutes of Health, NIST, FDA, CFPB, Rockville City Planning Department, and the Montgomery County Executive Office. Past examples of student projects include: using ML to predict an optimal location for a 7th police district in the county, providing surgeons with an analysis of skin flap surgeries for amputees, exploring the use of AI in pretrial bail determinations and the assessment of police officer misconduct, mapping DOT's use of salt on roadways impacts local stream health, and understanding transportation in the county through an equity lens.

SUMMARY

The Data Science Program strives to increase enrollment of diverse students, provide them with the most current technical skills, and promote understanding of the ethical and social justice issues in data science. Our program enables students to acquire real-world experience for entry into the workforce or transfer to four-year degrees.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

The Data Science program is offered by the Department of Math, Statistics, and Data Science with interdisciplinary collaboration from other departments.

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- A.S. in Data Science
- A.A. in General Studies STEM with Data Science Concentration
- A.A. in Business Analytics
- Data Science Certificate

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 7
- Professional Staff: 1
- Affiliated Members: 1
- Students: 131 majors; 240+ in data science courses

SOCIAL

Email:

rachel.saidi@montgomerycollege.edu

Web:

montgomerycollege.edu/academics/programs/data-science/

LinkedIn: Data Science at Montgomery College

LOCATION

51 Mannakee St.
Rockville, MD 20850

NYU

Center for Data Science

SUMMARY

Established in 2013, the NYU Center for Data Science (CDS) is at the forefront of data science education and research. As the home of the world's first data science MS program, CDS equips students and researchers with the tools to harness the power of Big Data.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Cross-departmental Center

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- Undergraduate Major in Data Science
- Undergraduate Joint Majors:
 - Computer Science and Data Science
 - Data Science and Mathematics
- Undergraduate Minor in Data Science
- Master's in Data Science
- PhD in Data Science

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 25
- Professional Staff: 12
- Affiliated Members: ~70

SOCIAL

Email:

datascience-group@nyu.edu

Web: cds.nyu.edu

X: @NYUDataScience

LinkedIn: NYU Center for Data Science

Facebook: @nyudatascience

Instagram: @nyucds

Bluesky:

[nyudatascience.bsky.social](https://bsky.app/profile/nyudatascience.bsky.social)

YouTube:

[@nyudatascience7498](https://www.youtube.com/@nyudatascience7498)

Medium:

nyudatascience.medium.com

LOCATION

60 5th Avenue
New York, NY 10011

ABOUT THE CENTER FOR DATA SCIENCE

The Center for Data Science (CDS) is NYU's focal point for university-wide efforts in Data Science. The Center was established in 2013 and our mission is to advance data science research, provide cutting-edge educational programs, and foster interdisciplinary collaboration across NYU and beyond.

RESEARCH AT CDS

CDS is known for being exceptionally interdisciplinary. Our faculty and researchers specialize in areas such as machine learning optimization and large-scale computation, natural language processing, computational statistics, quantitative methods, responsible data use, system design for large-scale data, theoretical statistics, and the mathematics of data science.

THE CDS MS IN DATA SCIENCE

Through a rigorous curriculum, hands-on projects, and close collaborations with world-class faculty and industry partners, our M.S. in Data Science program equips graduates to become leaders in shaping the future of data science.

The program has three tracks:

- The Industry Concentration, which allows students to pursue a specialization aligned with their career goals and requires industry-targeted coursework, a Practical Training experience, and an internship.
- The Biomedical Informatics (Medical School) Track, which has a biomedicine-based capstone project that is completed with a biomedicine mentor.
- The Data Science Track, which has three "areas of interest":
 - Big Data
 - Mathematics and Data
 - Natural Language Processing

THE CDS PHD PROGRAM IN DATA SCIENCE

Launched in Fall 2017, the pioneering CDS PhD Data Science program has gained recognition as one of the most prestigious and selective data science doctoral programs globally, earning an NSF NRT training grant. Our PhD students have been recognized through an array of fellowships and awards, from industry-sponsored programs like Microsoft Research, Google, and Apple, to academic honors such as the National Science Foundation Graduate Research Fellowship.

The PhD also offers a Medical School Track for those interested in healthcare applications or developing novel theoretical models from medical questions.

THE OHIO STATE UNIVERSITY

TRANSLATIONAL DATA ANALYTICS INSTITUTE

HISTORY AND PURPOSE

The Ohio State University's Translational Data Analytics Institute (TDAI) was established in 2015 as a foundational component of a \$500 million university initiative to address grand challenges—a recognition of big data's significance in answering the most pressing questions in science and solving the most vexing problems of the human condition. TDAI was designed to foster an intellectual community of faculty, staff and students from Ohio State's 15 colleges who engage in the interdisciplinary study, development and application of data science and analytics.

TRAINING AND EDUCATION PROGRAMS

In 2020 TDAI launched a master's degree program in translational data analytics to upskill and reskill working professionals. This program is a partnership between TDAI and Ohio State's Graduate School; Advanced Computing Center for Art and Design; and departments of statistics, design, and computer science and engineering. The MTDA integrates design thinking into foundations of data science, programming, machine learning, and data visualization, uniquely positioning students to be master data storytellers.

TDAI also provides non-traditional training opportunities such as employing undergraduate employee positions in our Data Science Consulting Services and graduate-level summer fellowships in government agencies.

OUTREACH

TDAI's Data Science Summer Camp serves as an exemplar of the Institute's intentional efforts to broaden participation in STEM fields. The camp is a week-long program designed for middle school students to increase exposure to data and analytics earlier in their education using a fun, hands-on approach to learning. The camp is an ecosystem of learning at all levels with TDAI faculty and graduate students designing and teaching modules, and undergraduate data analytics student majors volunteering to help campers learn new analytics and programming skills. The camp strengthens effectiveness of faculty broadening participation, as faculty leverage the camp platform by designing new modules in grant proposals to external funding agencies. The NSF-supported Imageomics Institute was successfully funded to develop camp modules, and TDAI implemented one of these modules in its 2022 camp.

RESEARCH

In addition to administering education and outreach programs, TDAI staff support research with data science services and consulting, scientific community-building logistics assistance, workshop facilitation, proposal development, and more. The institute's 21,000-square-foot facility enables collaboration with labs in residence; a data visualization lab; meeting, workshop and event spaces, and more.

SUMMARY

The Translational Data Analytics Institute is a community of 300+ faculty researchers from 50+ disciplines working at the forefront of interdisciplinary, big data-enabled science, scholarship and creative expression, with an emphasis on discoveries, solutions and insights for the greater good.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

We are a university-level institute that rolls up to the Office of Research

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- Master in Translational Data Analytics (MTDA)
- Ohio State offers other data science-related academic programs that are administered by entities other than TDAI

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 38
- Professional Staff: 10
- Affiliated faculty: 300+
- Students: 42 in the MTDA program

SOCIAL

Email: tdai@osu.edu

Web: tdai.osu.edu

LinkedIn: [Translational Data Analytics Institute](#)

LOCATION

1760 Neil Ave.
Room 350
Columbus, OH 43210

OLD DOMINION UNIVERSITY

SUMMARY

As one of the three academic units in the Interdisciplinary Schools at Old Dominion University, School of Data Science is a new initiative that focuses on educating students in the rapidly growing field of data science, conducting cutting-edge research and serving as a center of AI education and research in the University community.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

New Department

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- M.S. in Data Science & Analytics
- B.S. in Data Science
- Minor in Data Science
- AI in Data Science Certificate

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 10
- Affiliated Members: 80+

SOCIAL

Email:
datascience@odu.edu
Web: odu.edu/datascience
X: @ODUDataScience

LOCATION

4607 Hampton Blvd.
Monarch Hall, Suite 2110
NORFOLK, VA 23529

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

The School of Data Science has an interdisciplinary focus, drawing knowledge and expertise from different disciplines in sciences, business, engineering. Combined with data-centric perspectives on data ethics, data governance and effective communication, the unique curriculum provides students with flexibility pathways to be successful in future careers. The broad collaborative research between School of Data Science faculty with external partners provide students with real-world experience through internships, research collaborations, and industry projects.

RESEARCH AND COLLABORATION

The School of Data Science harbors unique collaborations with federally funded research facilities in the Hampton Roads (HR) region. Its main collaboration partners include:

Thomas Jefferson National Accelerator Facility (Jefferson Lab)

<https://www.jlab.org/>

Langley Research Center

<https://www.nasa.gov/langley/>

Hampton Roads Biomedical Research Consortium

<https://hrbrc.org/>

SINCLAIR DATA CAREER PROGRAMS MAXIMIZE FLEXIBILITY FOR CONCURRENT WORK AND EDUCATION

Technological innovation is accelerating, and innovations that once took years now happen in weeks. The change is forcing organizations to compress education, training, and adoption timelines. This accelerated pace is having a dramatic effect on the workforce, who must learn new skills and become productive almost immediately. Skills-first learning is necessary to support career readiness.

To help address this need, Sinclair's Data Analytics program seeks to soften the barriers between high school, college, and the workforce by creating a system of overlapping rather than sequential pathways:

- High school students earn college credit.
- College students are quickly and regularly engaged in professional development.
- Non-traditional students seeking to upskill or reskill can do so quickly and easily through flexible, multi-modality offerings with certificates or degrees focused on skill building.

STACKABLE PATHWAYS WITH EMBEDDED CERTIFICATES

ASA DATAFEST

Sinclair brings students, faculty, and industry experts together to solve a real-world problem in the annual DataFest competition.

Apprenticeships, internships, service learning, and experiential learning are key elements of a Sinclair College education.

Learn more

ASA DataFest 2024
Media Clip
"Welcome to DataFest"

ASA DataFest Winners & Data Pros

SUMMARY

Sinclair offers 300+ degree and certificate programs, including high demand specialized and technical areas of study. Sinclair consistently ranks in the top community colleges in America, with among the lowest tuition rates in Ohio. Sinclair's student-to-faculty ratio of nineteen-to-one is among the lowest at any Ohio college.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Sinclair's Data Analytics Programs are housed within the Division of Business and Public Services in the Computer Science Department.

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- Associate of Applied Science
- Technical Certificates:
 - Data Analytics
 - Data Literacy Foundation
 - Data Fundamentals

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Number of faculty: 5
- Number of staff: 2
- Affiliated members: 7
- Number of students: 140

SOCIAL

Email:

paul.hansford@sinclair.edu
Email us with #ADSA25

Web:

sinclair.edu/academics/divisions/bps/csc

LOCATION

444 West Third Street
Dayton, Ohio 45402

TEXAS A&M
 Institute of
 Data Science

Empowering Data Science
 Innovation and Education.

SUMMARY

The Texas A&M Institute of Data Science (TAMIDS) pursues new approaches to data science research, education, operations, and partnerships. These approaches cross boundaries to connect elements of Data Science, Artificial Intelligence, and Machine Learning from engineering, technology, science, and the humanities to inform broader social challenges and promote data literacy.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

University institute

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- MS in Data Science
- Data Analytics for Petroleum Industry Certificate

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 5
- Professional Staff: 14
- Affiliated Members: 250
- Students: 150

SOCIAL

Email: tamids@tamu.edu
Web: tamids.tamu.edu
LinkedIn: Texas A&M Institute of Data Science
Facebook: @TamuDataScience
Instagram: @TamuDataScience
YouTube: @TexasDataScience

LOCATION

John R. Blocker Building, Ste 227
 155 Ireland Street, TAMU 3156
 College Station, TX 77843-3156

EXPANDING DATA SCIENCE, AI, & MACHINE LEARNING

Texas A&M has long been known for being at the forefront of research and innovation, from the first-of-its-kind data processing center in the 1960s to leading the nation's engineering research expenditures in 2024. TAMIDS continues this legacy of promoting multi-disciplinary collaboration and education through programs like our internal seed grant programs, scholarships, fellowships, Data Science STEW (Seminars, Tutorials, and Educational Workshops), and student competitions.

EDUCATION INITIATIVES

The Master of Science in Data Science (MSDS) program uses an interdisciplinary approach to connect STEM with the humanities and give students a solid foundation in mathematics, statistics, computer science, AI, and machine learning. This program prepares students for various career options associated with data science, including consulting, finance, government agencies, healthcare and pharmaceuticals, marketing, technology development, and more! The Undergraduate Certificate in Data Analytics for the Petroleum Industry was created to prepare students for advanced data analytics and machine learning in the petroleum industry. This certificate allows students to work on real-world technical problems in the energy industry. TAMIDS Training offers boot camps, webinars, tutorials, grants, and more to help students, researchers, and faculty develop advanced skills through hands-on experience in data science, AI, and machine learning.

PARTNERSHIP AND ENGAGEMENT OPPORTUNITIES

TAMIDS partners with industries, student organizations, state and federal agencies, national labs, and other academic institutions to enhance student engagements, including sponsoring capstone projects, hackathons, professional development, and scholarships.

Our partners collaborate with Texas A&M's top experts to advance fundamental and applied data science, AI, and machine learning research. Our visiting research program supports scholars from universities, research labs, and industry to collaborate with TAMIDS and the broader data science community.

TEXAS STATE [®]

CENTER FOR ANALYTICS AND DATA SCIENCE

VISION

To be a globally recognized leader in analytics, data science and artificial intelligence research, empowering the world with data-driven innovations that solve complex challenges and transform lives starting with Texas Innovation Corridor.

MISSION

CADS is an interdisciplinary hub that advances analytics, data science and artificial intelligence research and education by fostering collaboration among researchers, students and industry partners. It trains faculty, enhances workforce readiness and provides technology and solutions for scientific, societal, and business challenges.

OBJECTIVES

- Foster interdisciplinary research projects utilizing analytics, data science, and AI.
- Provide training, education, and mentorship to build a diverse and skilled data and AI workforce.
- Engage with community and industry partners at local and international levels to create impactful and responsible AI and data driven solutions.

SUMMARY

Texas State University is a public student-centered Hispanic-Serving Institution dedicated to excellence and innovation in teaching, research, and service since 1899. More than 40,000 undergraduate and graduate students of which 43 percent are first generation, choose from over 200 bachelor's, master's, and doctoral degree programs.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

TXST CADS is a university-level, interdisciplinary research hub for data-intensive research, analytics and data science education, training, and outreach programs.

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- Bachelor Minor in Data Analytics
- M.S. in Data Analytics and Information Systems
- Specializations in business administration, computer science, engineering, health information management, and geography

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 1
- Professional Staff: 1.5
- Affiliated Members: 40
- Students:
 - 121 (M.S.)
 - 66 (B.S. Minor)

SOCIAL

Email: cads@txstate.edu

Web: cads.txst.edu

X: @TXST_CADS

LinkedIn: Texas State University Center for Analytics and Data Science (TXST CADS)

LOCATION

San Marcos, TX 78666

SUMMARY

The Berkeley Institute for Data Science (BIDS) provides a space for open scholarship, open source, and interdisciplinary collaboration on AI in science and society.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Cross-departmental Institute

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

BIDS facilitates interdisciplinary research, sustains and maintains open source infrastructure projects, develops and delivers training programs, and convenes expert knowledge transfer through events, cross-disciplinary discussion groups, public lectures, and seminars.

PROGRAM STATISTICS

Professional Staff: 14
Affiliated Members: 83

SOCIAL

Email: bids@berkeley.edu
Web: bids.berkeley.edu
LinkedIn: Berkeley Institute for Data Science (BIDS)
YouTube: youtube.com/UCBIDS
BlueSky: ucbids.bsky.social

LOCATION

Berkeley, California

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

BIDS' programs and initiatives are designed to facilitate collaboration across an increasingly diverse and active data science community of domain experts – from the life, social, and physical sciences, and the humanities – as well as methodological experts from computer science, statistics, and applied mathematics. Since its launch in 2013, BIDS has cultivated an environment of open inquiry and discovery for data-intensive research, and we continue to seek new and creative ways to cross traditional academic boundaries and engage a diverse community of researchers representing a wide array of disciplines.

INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH

BIDS supports innovative cross-disciplinary research for faculty, staff, postdoctoral fellows, and graduate and undergraduate students in a variety of fields across the life, health, social, and physical sciences, the humanities, and in computer science, statistics, and applied mathematics.

OPEN SOURCE RESEARCH SOFTWARE

BIDS contributes to open source, open science, and open data resource communities in support of academic research, and is home to the Berkeley Open Source Program Office.

TRAINING PROGRAMS

The Berkeley Computational Research for Equity in the Legal System Training Program is a five-year multi-disciplinary training program in the social sciences, computer science and statistics that leverages faculty expertise in the law and social science of criminal justice systems, data science, and the social implications of AI.

The Berkeley Computational Social Science Training Program recruits predoctoral students representing a variety of degree programs and expertise areas in the social sciences. Fellows develop advanced computational and data science analytics skills to address urgent needs in biomedical, behavioral, social and clinical research.

CENTER

Founded in 2023, the Center for Cultural Analytics is a joint initiative between UC Berkeley Humanities Faculty, the School of Information, and BIDS. It develops and refines computational methods as its members interrogate cultural production across a wide range of disciplines. The research focuses on the data-driven analysis of cultural phenomena.

The University of Chicago
Center for Cardiovascular Data Sciences
ccds.uchicago.edu | ccds@uchicago.edu

ABOUT CCDS

The Center for Cardiovascular Data Sciences (CCDS) provides a singular point of contact for cardiovascular researchers at the University of Chicago to obtain clinical datasets and perform analytics.

CCDS links together several clinical electronic health record systems to provide clients with a streamlined query process that has been used to support recruitment for clinical trials, healthcare registries, quality improvement projects, business development initiatives, basic science, and more.

Our analysts specialize in advanced queries with complex inclusion and exclusion criteria and have developed expertise in cross-platform computing to extract meaningful information from widely disparate datasets.

Our in-house statistician works together with our analysts and with clients to provide a seamless process for grant applications, analysis design, sample size and power calculations, hypothesis testing, machine learning, publication support, and more.

Nearly all cardiovascular faculty at the University of Chicago have used CCDS for their research, quality improvement, or business development needs. As CCDS continues to grow, we look forward to growing our collaborations as well.

Contact us if you would like to collaborate with one of our cardiovascular faculty members.

SUMMARY

The Center for Cardiovascular Data Sciences (CCDS) supports clinical research within the Heart and Vascular Center at the University of Chicago Medical Center. CCDS curates, tabulates, and queries data from several diverse electronic health record platforms, assists with recruitment for clinical trials, and offers statistical services in support of research.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

University-wide Center

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 1
- Professional Staff: 3

SOCIAL

Email: ccds@uchicago.edu

Web: ccds.uchicago.edu

LOCATION

5341 S Maryland Ave.
Chicago, IL 60637

UNIVERSITY OF ILLINOIS CHICAGO

SUMMARY

UIC's data science major allows you to choose from among nine concentrations: bioinformatics, business analytics, computer science, data processing, science and engineering, health data science, industrial engineering, social technology studies, statistics, and urban policy analytics.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Degree-granting program housed within the computer science department

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- B.S. in Data Science

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Professional Staff: 3
- Students: 184

SOCIAL

Email: cs-datascience@uic.edu
Web: cs.uic.edu/undergraduate/data-science-major
LinkedIn: University of Illinois Chicago College of Engineering
Instagram: @uicengineering
YouTube: @UICengineering

LOCATION

Chicago, IL

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

Data science at UIC is a multidisciplinary major that builds a strong foundation and gives you the option to specialize in a field of your choice. The nine concentrations offered to data science majors are made up of courses that come from five UIC colleges: the College of Engineering, the College of Liberal Arts and Sciences, the College of Business, the College of Applied Health Sciences, and the College of Urban Planning and Public Affairs. Featured faculty from computer science include Abolfazl Asudeh, Gonzalo Bello, Lu Cheng, Barbara Di Eugenio, Andruid Kerne, Sidharth Kumar, Bing Liu, G Elisabeta Marai, Sourav Medya, Fabio Miranda, Michael E. Papka, Natalie Parde, Stavros Sintos, Xiaorui Sun, Ouri Wolfson, Philip S. Yu, Xinhua Zhang, Elena Zheleva, and Brian Ziebart.

THE INSTITUTE FOR DATA, ECONOMETRICS, ALGORITHMS, AND LEARNING

UIC is part of IDEAL, a multi-institution and transdisciplinary institute sponsored by NSF that focuses on key aspects of the theoretical foundations of data science. It includes more than 75 researchers across computer science, electrical engineering, mathematics, statistics, economics, operations research, and law. Members include Northwestern University; Toyota Technological Institute at Chicago; the University of Chicago; Loyola University Chicago; and Illinois Institute of Technology, in partnership with members of the Learning Theory team at Google.

ELECTRONIC VISUALIZATION LABORATORY

UIC's Electronic Visualization Laboratory (EVL) is an interdisciplinary research laboratory in the UIC College of Engineering's Computer Science department. EVL specializes in collaborative visualization, virtual reality, visual data science, and advanced computing and networking infrastructure, and enables scientists and engineers to uniquely manage the scale and complexity of their data.

UNIVERSITY OF ILLINOIS URBANA-CHAMPAIGN

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

The University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign takes an interdisciplinary approach to data science. The new Office of Data Science Research (ODSR) is a campus-wide convening organization that facilitates collaborations, resource sharing, and public engagement focused on data science research activities at the University of Illinois. The National Center for Supercomputing Applications (NCSA) provides computing and data resources to campus and the nation as well as having strong programs in the application of computing and data science in a wide variety of application areas, including hosting AI institutes in digital agriculture and astronomy.

In education, there is an abundance of opportunities for students to engage with data-driven solutions within their chosen degree program. This cross-campus approach is mirrored in a set of innovative "CS+X" undergraduate degree programs where students take courses in both computer science and X, where X ranges from mathematics to music. A similar new series of programs named "X+DS" provide future data science professionals with first-hand experience in real use cases. Initial tracks include accountancy, astronomy, business, finance, and information science.

These programs are supported by a shared open-source curriculum that focuses on core concept literacy and real-world examples. Other programs on campus include an online Master of Science in Data Science in the Siebel School of Computing and Data Science; an MS with a data science track in Civil and Environmental Engineering; the department of Statistics offers a Certificate in Data Science; Engineering offers a data science and engineering concentration at the doctoral level, and the College of Liberal Arts & Sciences offers a data science scholars program.

THE SCHOOL OF INFORMATION SCIENCES (ISCHOOL)

The School of Information Sciences (iSchool), which considers the sociotechnical context in which data is produced and consumed, also offers a data science and analytics professional pathway in the Master of Science in Information Management program. The iSchool is the administrative home for a campus-wide Master of Science in Bioinformatics, an undergraduate Minor in Informatics, and a PhD in Informatics. Focusing on industry, the Gies College of Business offers a Master of Science in Business Analytics, and an Accounting Data Analytics Graduate Certificate.

THE CARLE ILLINOIS COLLEGE OF MEDICINE

The Carle Illinois College of Medicine (the world's first engineering-based college of medicine) immerses students in the use of data to improve patient care and outcomes along with core clinical knowledge.

There are multiple registered student organizations at Illinois with data science interests, including chapters of Women in Data Science (WiDS), Women in Computer Science (WCS), Women In CyberSecurity (WyCyS), Hack4Impact, as well as the Illinois Data Science Club, Data Science and Artificial Intelligence Society, and Analytics in Business Club.

SUMMARY

The Office of Data Science Research (ODSR) is a campus-wide convening organization that facilitates collaborations, resource sharing, and public engagement focused on data science research activities at the University of Illinois.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

We're a campus-level interdisciplinary research institute, reporting to the Office of the Vice Chancellor for Research and Innovation

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- Undergraduate Major in Data Science
- Undergraduate Minor in Data Science
- MS in Data Science (SCDS)
- Certificate in Data Science (Statistics)
- Specializations:
 - MS with a data science track (Civil and Environmental Engineering)
 - Doctoral data science concentration (Engineering)
 - Data science scholars program (Liberal Arts & Sciences)

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Number of core professional staff: 240
- Affiliated researchers: 131

SOCIAL

Email: data-science-research@illinois.edu

Web: odsr.illinois.edu

LinkedIn: [Office of Data Science Research](#)

LOCATION

Urbana, IL

UNIVERSITY OF MARYLAND,
BALTIMORE COUNTY

DEPARTMENT OF INFORMATION SYSTEMS

SUMMARY

UMBC is a top-ranked national university with an inclusive culture that connects innovative teaching and learning, research across disciplines, and civic engagement. Whatever your passion, at UMBC you'll find a program that challenges and excites you and a community that supports you.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Department housed within the College of Engineering and Information Technology

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- Ph.D. in Information Systems
- Ph.D. in Human-Centered Computing
- MS in Information Systems (either on campus or online)
- MS in Human-Centered Computing
- BS in Information Systems
- BA in Business Technology Administration
- Online post-bacc certificates:
 - Foundations in Information Systems
 - Artificial Intelligence
 - Cybersecurity Informatics
 - Data Science Informatics
 - User Experience Design

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 40
- Professional Staff: 6
- Students: 2000+

SOCIAL

Email:

informationsystems@umbc.edu

Web:

is.umbc.edu

LinkedIn:

UMBC Department of Information Systems

Facebook:

@IsDepartmentAtUmbc

Instagram:

@umbc_is

LOCATION

1000 Hilltop Circle ITE 404

Baltimore, MD 21250

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

The Department of Information Systems is part of The College of Engineering and Information Technology (COEIT) at UMBC. We currently offer a variety of degrees and certificates for undergraduate and graduate students, including a U.S. News-ranked Online M.S. in Information Systems and specializations in data science.

Through our curriculum, Information Systems students investigate societal impact, keeping humans in the loop and dealing with real and imminent challenges facing society. With the help of our faculty members, students study, design, develop, and evaluate information technologies to address the needs of a broad range of individuals and organizations.

PROGRAM SPECIALIZATIONS

Data in all of its forms are being generated and consumed at unprecedented speed and volume, with the significant advancement in information and communication technologies, new opportunities are emerging, as well as numerous threats. Our world-renowned faculty work diligently to be at the forefront of these advancements in the classroom, research labs and in the field seeking impactful change and opportunities for our students and community.

We have a nationally ranked 100% Online MS program offering the following tracks: Artificial Intelligence, Cybersecurity, Data Science and UX Design. These tracks allow our students to focus on in-demand skills while completing their degree. For our undergraduates interested in leadership roles, we are now offering a Minor in Management through our BTA program. This path will set students up for success as they pursue careers managing people, projects, contracts and organizations.

Center for **DATA SCIENCE**

Manning College of Information & Computer Sciences

DATA SCIENCE FOR THE COMMON GOOD

CDS is leading efforts to provide education and research pathways for aspiring data scientists to apply their knowledge and skills to benefit society. Data Science for the Common Good™ (DS4CG) is a summer program that trains aspiring data scientists to work on real-world problems that benefit the common good. Our teams of computer science students collaborate with nonprofit organizations and government agencies working in public health, education, environmental conservation, and more. DS4CG harnesses growing student interest in social-good causes and connects it to partner organizations that stand to benefit from the students' growing data science expertise.

DS4CG serves organizations that lack staff capacity to exploit state-of-the-art analysis and modeling of their business data. Ideal DS4CG projects incorporate analysis and integration of very large volumes of data, with different types and formats. DS4CG students compile, organize and clean these datasets, mathematically explore their statistical properties, build predictive models and forecasts, and visualize the results. Project deliverables can include actionable data-driven insights, presentations, reports, demos, and proof-of-concept software tools.

Learn more here:

<https://ds.cs.umass.edu/industry/data-science-common-good>

WHAT PEOPLE ARE SAYING ABOUT DS4CG

"An amazing program and a great learning opportunity. Be sincere and dedicated to the project goals, work as a team towards achieving them and grab every opportunity to learn something new!" - 2024 Student Participant

"They were able to both produce the needed data analysis tools and thoroughly document their process so we could reproduce the work in the future if needed. The documentation was their initiative (not something we thought to ask for), and was very helpful." - Partner at Media Cloud

"A great experience to be able to learn from your teammates and mentors and get real experience on a software project." - 2024 Student Participant

"Interdisciplinary research is challenging, and the program is a gem that both the college and university should strive to support." - Partner at UMass Amherst Computer Science

"The program provided a valuable chance for me to delve into research and connect with like-minded individuals on campus." - 2024 Student Participant

SUMMARY

The Center for Data Science fosters research, education, industry collaboration, and public service to make UMass Amherst a destination and partner-of-choice for research in artificial intelligence and data science. We help companies and organizations meet their growing demand for well-trained data scientists, promote economic development, and support working data scientists in Western Massachusetts and beyond.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

The Center for Data Science is housed within the Manning College of Information and Computer Sciences

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- Masters Concentration in Data Science
- Certificate in Statistical and Computational Data Science

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 43
- Professional Staff: 14
- Students: ~ 378

SOCIAL

Email:

cds-info@cs.umass.edu

Web: ds.cs.umass.edu

X: @UMassDataSci

LinkedIn: UMass Amherst Center for Data Science

LOCATION

740 North Pleasant Street
Suite A205
Amherst, MA 01003

Penn Arts & Sciences

Data Driven Discovery

SUMMARY

Penn's School of Arts and Sciences launched the Data Driven Discovery Initiative in 2021 to promote the development and use of data science in the physical sciences, life sciences, social sciences, and humanities.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Cross-departmental Center

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- Data Science and Analytics (DASA) Minor
- Survey Research and Data Analytics Minor
- Digital Humanities Minor
- Data Analytics and Psychological Sciences, BAAS
- Data Analytics and Social Sciences, BAAS
- Data Analytics, Certificate
- Data Science Concentration, MPA

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Professional Staff: 4
- Affiliated Members: 39

SOCIAL

Email:
ddd-info@sas.upenn.edu

Web:
web.sas.upenn.edu/data-science

LOCATION

McNeil Building 558
3718 Locust Walk
University of Pennsylvania
Philadelphia, PA 19104-6286

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

The Data Driven Discovery Initiative (DDDI) is the University of Pennsylvania's hub for data science research and education in the School of Arts and Sciences (SAS). We support an undergraduate minor, events, speaker series, research forums, data bootcamps, postdoctoral fellowships, and faculty seed grants focused on data science for social good. Our affiliated centers across Penn include IDEAS, RDDS, the Warren Center, Wharton Statistics, Price Lab, the Population Studies Center, PORES, and the Sociology Methodology Working Group.

TRAINING AND EDUCATION

DDDI manages the Data Science and Analytics minor, which provides undergraduates across SAS with a rigorous foundation in data science. DDDI also supports year-round training programs for undergraduates, including our Summer Data Science Hangouts series with faculty and postdoc-led presentations and tutorials.

RESEARCH

DDDI funds faculty projects that use data science and AI to address societal challenges in health, justice, climate, education, employment, and beyond. We also host fellowship programs for postdocs who use data science and AI to advance research across disciplines in SAS or bridge SAS and Engineering. Fellows receive funding, engage in DDDI activities, and collaborate with faculty and students.

GOERGEN INSTITUTE FOR DATA SCIENCE AND AI

RESEARCH

The Goergen Institute for Data Science and Artificial Intelligence (GIDS-AI) is the center for interdisciplinary data science and artificial intelligence (AI) research at University of Rochester (UR). The Institute brings faculty from all seven schools of UR together, with the common goal of pursuing data science and AI research opportunities with a focus on the following themes:

1. Foundations of machine learning and AI
2. Imaging, optics, and computer/human vision
3. Life sciences and biomedical data science
4. Health analytics and digital health
5. Human-data-system interfaces/computational reality (including human-computer interaction, augmented and virtual reality (AR/VR), robotics)
6. Computational social science
7. AI for physical sciences

In addition, the GIDS-AI seed funding program supports collaborative data science research efforts at UR with the goal of attracting major external funding.

EDUCATION

GIDS-AI offers three degree programs, a Bachelor of Arts (BA)/Bachelor of Science (BS) program in data science, a Master of Science (MS) in data science, and an advanced certificate in data science targeted at working professionals. GIDS-AI is also launching an online professional MS program in Healthcare AI and Data Science, which will admit its first cohort in Fall 2025.

ECONOMIC IMPACT

GIDS-AI houses the New York State Center of Excellence (CoE) in Data Science and Artificial Intelligence. Funded by the New York State Department of Economic Development's Division of Science, Technology, and Innovation (NYSTAR), the CoE supports economic development in New York by sponsoring data science and AI collaborative research projects and supporting internships for data science students at small, regional companies and startups. Over the last three years, the Center has generated over \$100 million of economic impact for New York State.

COMMUNITY OUTREACH

Throughout the year, GIDS-AI organizes various data science and AI events for the University of Rochester community, including research seminars, hackathons, and meetups. The Institute also supports two summer programs centered on computational social science and undergraduate STEM research, respectively.

SUMMARY

Established in 2015, the Goergen Institute for Data Science and Artificial Intelligence (GIDS-AI) is University of Rochester's integrative data science and artificial intelligence (AI) hub. The Institute offers a variety of data science degree programs, supports interdisciplinary data science and AI research, and fosters industry-academia data science and AI collaborations.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Cross-departmental Institute

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- BA, BS, MS in Data Science
- Online MS in Healthcare Data Science & AI
- Advanced Certificate in Data Science
- BA/BS specializations: biology, economics and business, political science, and more
- MS specializations: genomics, health and biomedical sciences, business and social science, and more

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 8
- Professional Staff: 6
- Affiliated Members: 101
- Students:
 - 187 BA/BS
 - 80 MS
 - 6 Advanced Certificate

SOCIAL

Email:

gids-info@rochester.edu

Web: hajim.rochester.edu/dsc

X: @UofRDataSci

LinkedIn: Goergen Institute for Data Science (GIDS)

YouTube: @CoEDataScience

LOCATION

1200 Suite, Wegmans Hall
University of Rochester
Rochester, NY 14627

USC Viterbi

School of Engineering
Data Science Program

SUMMARY

Located in the heart of Los Angeles, the school is a global center for arts, technology and entrepreneurship that connects students from 64 countries. The Viterbi School of Engineering is consistently in the top 10 graduate engineering programs in the U.S. News and World Report rankings.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Program housed within the Department of Computer Science

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- B.A. Data Science
- M.S.
 - Applied Data Science
 - Communication Data Science
 - Spatial Data Science
 - Public Policy Data Science
 - Healthcare Data Science
 - Environmental Data Science
 - Communication Data Science Dual Degree with Tsinghua University
 - Cyber Security Engineering
- Graduate Certificates in Data Science Foundations and Applied Data Science
- Foundations of Data Science Minor

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 5
- Professional Staff: 25
- Affiliated Members: 8
 - Students: 550 graduates; 80 undergraduates

LOCATION

941 Bloom Walk
Los Angeles, CA 90089

PROGRAM OVERVIEW: DATA SCIENCE FOR ALL

Our interdisciplinary Data Science programs are designed to be accessible to students with no programming or computer science background, and are joint programs with other schools at USC. Carefully designed introductory courses on computational thinking and programming enable students to take advanced electives in machine learning, user experience design and strategy, knowledge graphs, and scalable data systems. Students learn to work on teams through experiential learning in course-long projects, hands-on homeworks, class exercises in groups, and capstone classes. Many students take internships during their studies, either in research labs in the engineering school or in local tech companies.

SOCIAL

Email: datasci@usc.edu
Web: datascience.usc.edu
X: @CSatUSC
Facebook: @USCViterbi
Instagram: @USCViterbi
YouTube: @USCViterbi

THE UNIVERSITY OF TEXAS AT EL PASO
DATA SCIENCE
 COLLEGE OF SCIENCE

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

This program is open to qualified individuals from many disciplines who require training on applying data in their fields. The program emphasizes the application and development of data science methodologies, incorporation of real-world applications through industry and government collaborations, and development of students' professional skills, such as communication and collaboration. The program, designed in consultation with regional industry partners, prepares students to work in both academia and industries where there are still critical shortages of data science talent.

UTEP DATA SCIENCE COLLABORATIONS

Faculty and students in the data science program regularly collaborate on research projects in partnership with other divisions at UTEP and outside institutions.

DATA ANALYTICS LAB

The Data Analytics Lab offers data, statistical, and mathematical analysis and modeling to internal (UTEP) and external customers. This lab focuses on data analytics projects that involve external partnerships, seeks to involve students in the Data Science PhD program, supports professional development, and provides service to organizations that cannot afford a full-time data scientist. Its goal is to promote interdisciplinary research, while increasing publications and grants.

SUMMARY

The Department of Mathematical Sciences at The University of Texas at El Paso (UTEP) houses data science degrees at the bachelors, masters, and doctoral levels. The programs emphasize the analysis of big data using novel methods that are grounded in theory.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Our program is housed within the department of Mathematical Sciences and has a diverse faculty from programs/units across campus

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- Undergraduate Minor and Concentration in Data Science
- BS in Mathematics with Concentration in Data science
- MS in Statistics and Data Science
- PhD in Data Science
- Graduate Certificate in Big Data Analytics

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 17, with 3 additional funded positions to be filled
- Professional Staff: 1
- Affiliated Members: 26
- Students: 75

SOCIAL

Email: mathdpt@utep.edu
Web: utep.edu/science/math/academic-programs/graduate/datascience

LOCATION

Bell Hall Building
 500 W. University Ave.
 El Paso, TX 79968

SUMMARY

The University of Toronto Data Sciences Institute is a multidivisional and multidisciplinary hub for data science research, training, and partnerships. Our mission is to accelerate the impact of data sciences across disciplines to address pressing societal questions. We facilitate collaboration and the development and application of new methodologies and tools.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

University-wide institutional strategic initiative

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- Data Sciences Certificate
- Machine Learning Software Foundations Certificate
- Data Science Certificate for Doctoral Students

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Professional Staff: 11
- Affiliated Members: 1,600
- Students:
 - 35 Graduate Student Fellows
 - 25 Postdoctoral Fellows
 - 126 Undergraduates

SOCIAL

Email: info.dsi@utoronto.ca
Web: datasciences.utoronto.ca
X: @UofTDSI
LinkedIn: Data Sciences Institute, University of Toronto

LOCATION

700 University Avenue, 10th floor
Toronto, Ontario
Canada

CATALYZING CROSS-DISCIPLINARY RESEARCH & TRAINING

We focus on the following strategic objectives to:

- Shape the evolution of the field of data science including the development of novel methodologies
- Catalyze opportunities for convergence of knowledge domains and equitable solutions
- Cultivate inclusive skills for success
- Foster and catalyze knowledge mobilization to advance the public good

EMERGENT DATA SCIENCES

Supporting emergent areas of data science is a core activity of the DSI that drives its mission of bringing people together for collaborative generation and application of new ideas. DSI funds a broad span of activity that can lead to the development of innovative data science methodologies, deep connections with computation and applied disciplines, new training programs, collaboration, knowledge mobilization, and impact beyond the academy.

Current programming:

1. Causal Inference: Bringing together data science and causal inference for better policy recommendations
2. Galvanizing Data Science Applications in Early-Stage Drug Discovery
3. Toward a Fair and Inclusive Future of Work with ChatGPT
4. Advancing Aging and Neurodegeneration Research through Data Science

DATA SCIENCE CERTIFICATES

The DSI Data Science Certificates, a national initiative powered by Palette Skills and funded by the Government of Canada, offer affordable, flexible and rigorous technical skills training, paired with critical job readiness support, for hundreds of professionals. Given the need for data science training across a range of sectors, the certificates are designed to empower participants with the skills needed to succeed in cutting-edge careers.

The DSI also offers not-for-credit Data Science Certificate for Doctoral Students that provide in-demand data science skills in industry that can enhance student career opportunities in their chosen fields. The Certificate is suitable for students from a broad range of academic disciplines with no prior data science experience. Learn more at <https://datasciencecertificate.ca/>

UNIVERSITY OF UTAH ONE-U RESPONSIBLE AI INITIATIVE *at the* SCIENTIFIC COMPUTING & IMAGING INSTITUTE

RESPONSIBLE AI INITIATIVE

In fall 2023, the University of Utah launched a research initiative that aims to responsibly use artificial intelligence (AI) technology to tackle societal issues. This initiative will advance AI and its applications in ways that achieve societal good while also protecting privacy, civil rights, and civil liberties, and promoting principles of accountability, transparency, and equity. The One-Utah Responsible AI Initiative (One-U RAI) brings together the applied research and technological expertise, advanced cyberinfrastructure, and workforce needed to lead the region and nation in achieving societal good. Through One-U RAI, the University of Utah is building talent and expertise in AI research, increasing computing power and resources, and engaging the broader community through partnerships and public events. In 2024, One-U RAI launched distinguished visitor, faculty fellowship, and post-doctoral fellowship programs, which will be followed with focused cluster hires for the 2026 academic year. Along with the Center for High Performance Computing, One-U RAI is housed within the Scientific Computing and Imaging (SCI) Institute.

SYNERGISTIC ACTIVITIES

In support of the broader data-enabled research ecosystem, the University of Utah has several ongoing data science and AI activities. The Utah Center for Data Science (UCDS) leads, organizes, and manages data science resources and research efforts at the University of Utah. The Data Science and Ethics of Technology (DATASET) Initiative engages foundational questions about the role of data in society. The Data Exploration and Learning for Precision Health Intelligence (DELPHI) and Digital Health Initiatives catalyze interdisciplinary biomedical data science research to drive innovation in health and medicine. Digital Matters serves as the locus for computationally enhanced humanities and arts research and pedagogy, with a strength in cultural criticism and theory.

SUMMARY

The One-U Responsible AI Initiative is a university-wide effort aimed at responsibly leveraging AI to address critical local, regional, and global challenges and benefit humanity.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Cross-departmental Center

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- Data Science BS
- Information Systems BS
- Bioinformatics BS
- Business Analytics MS
- Computing MS & PhD
- Information Systems MS
- Certificates in Computational Linguistics, Data Fluency, and Data Science (UG); Data Science, Deep Learning, Business Analytics, Information Systems, and Informatics (Grad)
- Specializations: Biomedical Engineering, Biomedical Informatics, Computing, Population Health Sciences, Professional Masters in Science and Technology

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 7
- Professional Staff: 3
- Affiliated Members: 140
- Students: 135

SOCIAL

Email: rai@utah.edu

Web: rai.utah.edu

X: @OneU_RAI

LinkedIn: One-U Responsible AI Initiative

Bluesky: uusci.bsky.social

LOCATION

Salt Lake City, UT, USA

WASHINGTON STATE UNIVERSITY

Data Analytics

SUMMARY

Our students are trained in concentrated domain knowledge, advanced statistical, data, and computer science skills. This combination enables WSU graduate to effectively work in teams and easily communicate with colleagues and managers to solve problems.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Degree-granting Program in Data Analytics

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- B.S. in Data Analytics
- Data Science Certificate coming Spring 2025
- Specializations in: Actuarial sciences, agriculture and environmental systems, business, computation, data visualization, economics, general, and other sciences like life science, physical, and social sciences

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 7
- Professional Staff: 3
- Affiliated Members: 5
- Students: 237

SOCIAL

Email:

wsu.dataanalytics@wsu.edu

Web: data-analytics.wsu.edu

LinkedIn: [WSU Data Analytics](https://www.linkedin.com/company/WSU-Data-Analytics)

Instagram: [@dataanalytics.wsu](https://www.instagram.com/dataanalytics.wsu)

LOCATION

Everett, Pullman, and Vancouver, WA

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

Washington State University (WSU) recognizes the increasing demand for data analytics professionals and equips its students with the skills needed for success. The program ensures that graduates have a strong foundation of data theory and practice, understand the context and domain of data, and are proficient in data methods and applications. Students also learn about the responsibilities of professional data analysts, including legal and ethical considerations related to security and privacy, and the principles of data usage. Upon graduation, they will be able to effectively communicate their expertise and operate in both academic and professional settings, excelling as both team members and leaders.

GIVE YOURSELF A COMPETITIVE EDGE

Internships

WSU Data Analytics (DA) is one of the few career-launch certified programs in Washington. Career Connect Washington unites career-connected learning statewide, offering numerous benefits. Students gain hands-on experience in their future fields, while employers benefit from intern support. This partnership can also reveal new career opportunities. Our internship program is particularly advantageous, providing practical experience, application of coursework in real-world scenarios, and opportunities to build valuable skills and networks for future career success.

Mentorships

DA students can take part in our mentorship program that offers invaluable guidance and support with an experienced mentor. The program can provide opportunities to enhance personal and professional development, gain insights into the data analytics field, and build a strong network of connections for future career prospects.

Transdisciplinary Institute *in Applied* Data Sciences (TRIADS)

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

TRIADS supports transdisciplinary research teams who are using data science tools to address critical problems facing society. To achieve this, we aim to create an open, inclusive, and vibrant community of researchers that is welcoming to all fields and many ways of studying and understanding the world. At the core of our mission is to be question-driven and to provide value to the community of researchers we serve, in return for their time and engagement.

TRIADS activities include:

- Supporting data-informed transdisciplinary studies by providing resources for novel research in the form of seed grants, programming/software development, grant writing support, and more.
- Building a robust community for collaborative research across disciplines by hosting workshops and conferences, co-sponsoring seminars, and convening for social events.
- Identifying and pursuing external funding from government, nonprofit, and private sector sources.
- Offering training opportunities for WashU faculty, staff, and students on using data science tools

SUMMARY

At TRIADS, our mission is to explore new datasets and new techniques to better understand and address critical problems facing society today. We create and support transdisciplinary collaborations among scholars to connect big data to big questions.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

A signature initiative of the WashU Arts & Sciences Strategic Plan, TRIADS is led by faculty co-leads Bo Li and Tammy English, with support from faculty, staff, grad students, and postdocs.

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 2
- Professional Staff: 8
- Affiliated Members: 42

SOCIAL

Email: triads@wustl.edu
Web: triads.wustl.edu

LOCATION

420 Jolley Hall
Washington University in St. Louis
St. Louis, MO 63130

WILLIAM & MARY

DATA SCIENCE

SUMMARY

Data Science at William & Mary comprises academic offerings at the undergraduate and graduate level and a growing research portfolio. Through these activities we prepare students for careers that explore patterns in large data sets and identify potential trends and insights, and advance the state of science in this pursuit.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Data Science is an autonomous unit within the Department of Computer Science.

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- B.S. in Data Science
 - Specializations in Artificial Intelligence, Data Applications, Algorithms, and Spatial Data Analytics
- Ph.D. in Data Science
- Graduate Certificate in Data and Computer Sciences

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 10
- Professional Staff: 2
- Affiliated Members: 12
- Students: 341

SOCIAL

Email: datascience@wm.edu

Web: ds.wm.edu

X/Twitter: @WMdatascience

LOCATION

540 Landrum Drive
Williamsburg, VA 23185

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

The Data Science program at William & Mary is blending on our tradition of liberal arts education with the highly technical issues at the core of the emerging data science academic domain, to produce well-rounded technically-skilled graduates who also possess a deep understanding of the implications of big data and algorithms on our society. Accordingly, our offerings combine in-depth knowledge of highly technical subjects (e.g. Machine Learning, Programming) with additional broader curriculum requirements (ranging e.g. from courses related to the ethical aspects of the use of data to ones that address application-specific issues).

SOCIETAL IMPLICATIONS OF DATA SCIENCE: GOING BEYOND METHODS

Data Science at W&M provides a novel learning environment. We push students beyond methods and towards critically considering the implications of big data and algorithms on our society.

Topics in Data Science are constantly evolving, and so do our courses. Example issues drawn from previous coursework have included:

- How big data and algorithms are influencing sentencing in the legal system
- How algorithms choose - intentionally or not - who to save in a car crash
- How websites such as match.com are impacting the future of human genetics

WINSTON-SALEM STATE UNIVERSITY

The Center for Applied Data Sciences

PROGRAM OVERVIEW

The goal of The Center for Applied Data Science (CADS) at WSSU is to foster research and education in data-driven knowledge discovery. We aim to bring together computer scientists and domain scientists with complex Data Science problems to promote and accelerate data-intensive discovery and education. We also focus on leveraging the power of data to help change lives and impact our local community, while also fostering greater diversity and inclusion in the rapidly growing field of data science. The center received its inaugural funding of 1.5M in the Fall of 2020 for three years funded by the UNC Research Opportunities Initiative (ROI). Currently, 30 faculty, students, and staff are supported by CADS under the leadership of Debzani Deb, the founding director of CADS.

FACULTY ADOPTER AWARDS

The center's Faculty Adopter Awards support enthusiastic faculty across various disciplines who are willing to infuse data science and AI concepts and skills into their existing courses, and are able to quantitatively and qualitatively assess the impact of their interventions. Since 2021, more than 20 WSSU faculty received this award and developed relevant course modules impacting about 400 students at WSSU. Students from Arts, Education, Science, Social Science, Business and Health Science departments are exposed to AI & data analysis and gained hands-on experiences using relevant tools and techniques.

CADS RESEARCH PROJECTS

CADS focuses on interdisciplinary research and bridging the gap between domain experts and computer scientists to maximize the power and practicality of data science. CADS received further fundings from NASA, NSF and Mozilla Foundation to advance its research projects. Current projects are: exploring use of LLM and data science to enhance accessibility to scientific repository; investigating healthcare disparities and the prominent factors that cause them; applying mobile crowdsensing data to improve healthcare efficiency and worker safety; developing a 2-year data science certification for non-cs majors and assessing its impact; exploring the impact of injecting AI Ethics modules in Arts, humanities and social science disciplines; exploring geographic, exploring spatial injustices.

DEI AND OUTREACH

CADS expect that the various educational and research mentorship efforts will expose women, minority, and underrepresented students to data science & AI content and skills that may influence their choice about further education and future careers, therefore increasing the size and diversity of the future STEM workforce and changing lives and communities for the better. CADS regularly organizes student research showcases, training workshops, and K-12 camps designed to raise awareness and spark interest in data science and AI among local middle and high school students.

COMMUNITY COLLABORATION

While CADS' work is occurring in academic settings, the practical outcomes will have a lasting and far-reaching impact on the local community. We are eager to team with local businesses that might benefit from data science as they pursue investment and commercialization of their products. We also invite academia, industry, nonprofit, and government agency participation in our annual symposium and monthly seminars to increase awareness of data science. The Center gives us all a chance to do something very special together - prepare our young people for a bright future, improve lives through work that also bolsters the economy, and advance the cause of racial justice and equity throughout the Triad and North Carolina.

SUMMARY

Founded in 1892, Winston-Salem State University is a public Historically Black College and University (HBCU) and a University of North Carolina (UNC) institution, where 76% of the student population are African Americans or Hispanic/Latino, 73% are female, and 23% are first generation college students.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

Institution-wide Initiative

DEGREES, PROGRAMS, AND SPECIALIZATIONS

- Interdisciplinary Data Science Minor for Undergraduates
- Certificate in Data Analytics for Graduates

PROGRAM STATISTICS

- Core Faculty: 1
- Professional Staff: 2
- Affiliated Members: 6
- Students:
 - Data Science Minor: 5
 - Certificate Program: 6
 - Graduate & Undergraduate Assistants: 10

SOCIAL

Email: debd@wssu.edu

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LinkedIn: Center for Applied Data Science (CADS) - WSSU

YouTube: @CADSWSSU

LOCATION

Winston-Salem, NC, USA